

D1.5 Deployment & Integration Report

WP1 Pilots Planning and Execution
FDEUSTO
Report
Public

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CONTENT

Executive summary.....	5
1 Introduction.....	6
2 Baseline updates.....	9
3 State of the level of development and implementation of the sensors and eco-solutions	9
3.1 Status of the sensor layer	9
3.2 Status of the Eco-Solutions	10
3.2.1 Operation and Planning.....	11
3.2.1.1R1: Operation and Management Module.....	11
3.2.1.2R2: Collection Module.....	12
3.2.1.3R3: Planning Module	13
3.2.1.4R4: Circular Economy Module.....	14
3.2.2 Apps	14
3.2.3 Educational Materials	15
3.2.4 Social Actions	16
3.2.5 Treatment Plants	17
3.2.6 Waste4Think Story Map	19
4 Social Action Plan Implementation.....	23
4.1 Summary of the Social Action Programme status	23
5 KPIs monitoring.....	23
5.1 Methodology updates or improvements.....	23
5.2 Integral waste management evaluation indicators.....	23
5.2.1 Halandri	24
5.2.2 Seveso.....	33
5.3 Eco-solution specific indicators.....	41
6 Lessons learnt.....	42
6.1 Cascais.....	42
6.2 Halandri	43
6.3 Seveso.....	45
6.4 Zamudio.....	46
7 Policy Feedback.....	48
7.1 Cascais.....	48
7.2 Halandri	49
7.3 Zamudio.....	49
Revision tables	51
Annexes of Deliverable D1.5	55

TABLES

<i>Table 1 Relation of Milestones and results reports foreseen for Waste4Think project</i>	6
<i>Table 2 Expected results of Waste4Think</i>	7
<i>Table 3 Scheduling foreseen for the update of the Waste Management KPIs (where grey cells denote when the KPIs will be updated)</i>	8
<i>Table 4 Results of the Waste Management KPIs for Halandri (September 2018)</i>	27
<i>Table 5 Evolution of the High Level KPIs with respect to the baseline in Halandri</i>	30
<i>Table 6 Results of the Waste Management KPIs for Seveso (April 2018)</i>	36
<i>Table 7 Evolution of the High Level KPIs with respect to the baseline in Seveso</i>	38
<i>Table 8 Economical KPIs of the expected products/services of Waste4Think per partner (In grey pending information)</i>	41

Glossary

F

FORBI

Biomass product result from the Biomass Treatment Plant (R19).

G

Grant Agreement (GA)

Contractual document signed by all the project partnership which defines the rights and obligations of the Consortium regarding the EC.

Geographic Information Systems (GIS)

Is a system designed to capture, store, manipulate, analyse, manage, and present spatial or geographic data.

K

Key Performance Indicators (KPIs)

Indicator for quantifying the overall impact of the Waste4Think project

P

PAYT (Pay-As-You-Throw)

strategy that allows applying the Polluter Pays Principle for household waste through the implementation of a variable fee structure

S

Sustainability Assessment Model

waste management chain that involves the following stages in the waste management generation, collection, treatment and final disposal, as well as the definition of the set of the Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) for the evaluation of the impact of the different ecosolutions implemented in Waste4think

W

WESTE methodology

set of Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) specifically designed in Waste4Think to holistically assess the efficiency of the system as well as the monitoring of the strategic and operational objectives in each pilot from an economic, environmental and social perspective under a Life cycle approach

Z

Zero Waste Ecosystem

is one entity or group of entities that develop their activity in such a way that minimizes the potential negative impacts on the environment

Zero Waste Event

an event that has been designed, organized and developed with the aim of no generating wastes

Executive summary

This deliverable summarizes the status of the project at Milestone 3 (month 30 of the project) where Deployment & Integration stage of the project is expected to be fulfilled. According to the Grant Agreement (GA) the Deployment & Integration stage comprise the following activities:

The solutions developed in this project will be integrated between themselves and with the already deployed system in the four pilots (all systems reach beta stage at Month 28).

Municipal regulations are defined.

Monitoring and assessment of the evolution of the KPIs based on real data.

The present deliverable describes the status of the project according to the foreseen status at Milestone 3 in terms of:

- Baseline updates (Section 2): Cascais baseline is the only baseline which requires to be updated. However, the new characterization has not been carried out at Milestone 28.
- Development and implementation of the eco-solutions (Section 3): A revision of the development and implementation status at Milestone 3 in comparison with the planned status has been made. The Waste4Think Story Map (described in Deliverable D1.4) has been used to report the status of the eco-solutions.
- Social Actions implementation (Section 4): A review of the status of the implementation of the social actions which comprises the environmental programme of the pilots is shown in this Section. To this purpose, the output of the Social Action Module (the module of the Result R3: Planning Module for the design, planning and monitoring of the Social Actions) has been used. The public database about Social Actions can be consulted in [Zenodo Waste4Think Community](https://zenodo.org/record/1745487) (DOI 10.5281/zenodo.1745487).
- Monitoring of the Waste4Think KPIs (Section 5):
 - KPIs of the waste management systems of Halandri and Seveso at Milestone 3 have been calculated using the methodology described in Deliverable D1.3. In the case of Seveso the main aim is to evaluate the impact of the Zero Waste events and the involvement of the Virtuous household. As for Halandri the interest is on the impact of the collection of nappies and biowaste and their subsequent valorisation.
 - The first KPIs related to the eco-solutions have also been reported.
- Lessons learnt (Section 6): main knowledge acquired during this period related to the experiences in the pilot sites is summarized in this Section.
- Policy feedback (Section 7): main legal barriers pilots have found during implementation of the actions.

1 Introduction

Pilots execution progress of the 4 pilot sites in Waste4Think (Cascais, Seveso, Zamudio and Halandri) will be analysed along the project by 4 deliverables corresponding to the milestones of the project (Table 1).

Table 1 Relation of Milestones and results reports foreseen for Waste4Think project.

Milestone	Month	Deliverable
M2	18	D1.4 Preparatory Actions Report
M3	28	D1.5 Deployment & Integration Report
M4	34	D1.6 Preliminary Test Report
M5	40	D1.7 Full Test Report

The aim of this set of deliverables is to present the overall progress of the pilots during the project execution summarizing the actions taken as well as the progress made in every pilot with respect to the baseline. In particular, these periodic reports will contain the following structure:

Section 2 Baseline updates. Although the baseline of the pilots is established in D1.3, its updates (if necessary) will be incorporated in these progress reports.

Section 3: A description of the sensors that have been deployed at every pilot site and their location and the state of the technologies to be deployed at the pilot sites. Table 1Table 2 summarizes the results expected in Waste4Think.

Table 2 Expected results of Waste4Think.

	<p>R1 - Operation & Management Module R2 – Collection Module R3 – Planning Module R4 – Circular Economy Module</p>
	<p>R5 - Food App: Promotion of food waste prevention R6 - Local Trade App: Promotion of local trade, eco- tourism and cooperative actions R7 - Citizen App: Promotion of transparency and citizen empowerment, communication with waste managers.</p>
	<p>R8 – Innovative Teaching Units: Educational materials about waste management. R9 – Sorting Game: Game that teaches on the importance of waste sorting R10 - Eco-design Game: Introduction to the eco-design. R11 – Planning Game: Game to raise awareness and to train on the integral waste management system. R12 – Virtual City Game: Game that provides training on the Circular Economy principles R13 – Eco-Design solutions: Co-creation of eco-products and services. R14 – Planning solutions for the co-creation of integral waste management strategies. R15 – Circular Economy solutions for the co-creation of Circular Economy strategies</p>
	<p>R16 – Economic instruments: Legislation about PAYT and incentive schemes. R17 – Innovative awareness actions: web tools and awareness campaigns. R18 – Best Practices Book</p>
	<p>R19 – Pre-dried and shredded bio-waste (FORBI): Valorisation of kitchen/food waste in a circular economy concept R20 - Bio-fuel: Valorisation and treatment of nappies for bio-fuel production.</p>

Section 4: A summary of the social actions carried out and their impact.

Section 5: A review in terms of the KPIs with respect to the project baseline following the sustainability model defined in D1.3, as well as any modification in the KPIs methodology if necessary. Table 3 shows the foreseen scheduling to monitor the waste management KPIs of the pilot sites.

Table 3 Scheduling foreseen for the update of the Waste Management KPIs (where grey cells denote when the KPIs will be updated).

Pilot site	D1.4 Milestone 2 (Month 18)	D1.5 Milestone 3 (Month 28)	D1.6 Milestone 4 (Month 34)	D1.7 Milestone 5 (Month 40)
Cascais	No significant change of the system	Change in the collection system (containers and lorries), use of Apps	Preliminary test	Full scale
Halandri	Biowaste collection in operation	Educational materials in schools and use of Apps. Nappies collection	Preliminary test	Full scale
Seveso	PAYT under implementation	Zerowaste events, virtuous households and use of Apps	Preliminary test	Full scale
Zamudio	No significant change of the system	Change in the collection system (containers and lorries). Educational materials in schools and use of Apps	Preliminary test	Full scale

Section 6: As a result of the assessment of the project progress, each deliverable will also incorporate the lessons learnt and recommendations for the coming period (or postproject period in case of *D1.7 Full test report*).

Section 7: As a result of the barriers that pilots are finding for the implementation of the actions each deliverable will also incorporate a section with the aim to inform EC about these barriers.

This deliverable is directly related to the following deliverables of the project:

D1.1 Pilots planning documentation which includes the legislation framework of the pilots as well as the description of the functional and non-functional requirements of the eco-solutions.

D1.3 Sustainability assessment models with information about the waste management systems of the pilot sites as well as the baseline and the main objectives.

D.4.1 Implementation of R17: non-ICT Innovative Social Actions and *D.4.2 Implementation of R17: ICT based Innovative Social Actions* with the detailed environmental programmes of the pilot sites and their scheduling.

D2.7 Technical documentation of R3: Planning Module where Social Actions Module is described.

Finally the public data model of the Social Actions with all the information regarding the implementation of the Social Actions can be consulted in [Waste4Think Zenodo Community](https://zenodo.org/communities/waste4think/) (DOI 10.5281/zenodo.1745487).

2 Baseline updates

Cascais baseline should be updated as some mistakes in the methodology of the characterization were detected. However, the new characterization has not been carried out at Milestone 28 and consequently data are not still available.

3 State of the level of development and implementation of the sensors and eco-solutions

This section will summarize the status of the deployments of the eco-solutions and the monitoring system (sensors deployed) in each pilot at Milestone 3 of the project.

3.1 Status of the sensor layer

According to the Grant Agreement, at the end of this phase we should have achieved:

“The solutions developed in this project will be integrated between themselves and with the already deployed system in the four pilots (all systems reach beta stage at M28”

Annex II Actions to Carry out for each
Eco-innovative Solution in Every Pilot and Phase

Annex 1 shows how these general guidelines are distributed into the different sensors and pilot sites (ref) and the actual status at Milestone 3 (stat), as well as the estimated values for Milestone 4 (estim). In this table, the rows at the top represent the planned, actual and estimated status of the development of every sensor. Please note that some sensors have had to be developed and are prototypes (as no other solution near market have been found). On the other hand, the bottom of the table provides information about the integration of the sensors per pilot site.

In general, the components of the sensor layer that are commercial products are already installed and tested. Its integration is ahead of schedule. The main exception to this is the smart container in Zamudio, specifically the electronic lock. First, some problems to find a commercial solution that fits all functional requirements (FR) requested in this pilot site arisen as was explained in D1.4. A solution was found (see Deliverable D2.1 for details) and some development was needed by FDEUSTO and the provider of the

solution as no commercial solution fulfils the functional requirements. Despite overcoming this technical issue, some new difficulties have arisen during the tendering process due to the entry into force of two new regulations about public tendering^{1,2} as well as other considerations regarding maintenance conditions which needed to be revised because of the high technological risk of the new smart containers. In the meanwhile in order to minimize the possible consequences of this delay, the integration of the e-lock reader and waste weighting system in the Truck Data App has progressed in the following way. On one hand, the prototype of the Truck Data App has been completed and is being testing under real conditions in one lorry. On the other hand, the integration of the Truck Data App with the e-lock is being tested with prototype e-locks. At this moment the tender is almost ready to be published and the new containers are expected by March 2019.

A slight delay has also arisen in the integration of the e-lock in Cascais regarding the configuration of the e-locks (white or black list, opening schedules,...) from Mawis to the e-lock. However, as the collective PAYT, which is already implemented in Cascais, is based on volunteers, this functionality is not a priority for the moment. More details about the sensors can be found in the technical Deliverables D2.1 Technical documentation of R1 and D2.2 Implementation of the sensors for R1, R2 and R3.

3.2 Status of the Eco-Solutions

This Section presents the planned status of the implementation of the functional requirements of the eco-solutions accordingly to the Grant Agreement as well as the status of their deployment in each pilot site at Milestone 3. Please note that some functional requirements have to be provided by different technical solutions that are going to be tested at different pilot sites (in order to assess their replicability). In this sense every implementation could be in different stages at the different pilots' sites. Only the one that has the most advanced status is provided.

The following sections summarize the status of every type of eco-solutions:

1. Operational and Planning
2. Apps
3. Educational Materials
4. Social Actions
5. Treatment Plants

¹ Ley 9/2017, de 8 de noviembre, de Contratos del Sector Público, por la que se transponen al ordenamiento jurídico español las Directivas del Parlamento Europeo y del Consejo 2014/23/UE y 2014/24/UE, de 26 de febrero de 2014. <https://www.boe.es/buscar/act.php?id=BOE-A-2017-12902>

² Ley 9/2017, de 8 de noviembre, de Contratos del Sector Público, por la que se transponen al ordenamiento jurídico español las Directivas del Parlamento Europeo y del Consejo 2014/23/UE y 2014/24/UE, de 26 de febrero de 2014. <https://www.boe.es/buscar/act.php?id=BOE-A-2017-12902>

3.2.1 Operation and Planning

According to the Grant Agreement, at the end of this phase we should have achieved:

“R1, R2 and R3: Back-end: Integration tests. IT-tools: Initial tests with preliminary data from back-end.

R4: Continue the development.”

Annex II Actions to Carry out for each Eco-innovative Solution in Every Pilot and Phase

Annex 2. shows how these general guidelines are distributed into the different functional requirements that have to be implemented and their testing at the pilot sites, as well as their status at Milestone 3 and the estimation for Milestone 4. In general, the back-end should receive information from the different sensors while the rest of tools should have been in beta quality. Any eco-solution has been expected to be deployed in any pilot site (apart from the identification system of users in Seveso needed to deploy the PAYT since Milestone 2).

Details about these tools could be found in Deliverables D2.1 to D2.10. Next we provide a detailed description of the status and main deviations detected for every component.

3.2.1.1 R1: Operation and Management Module

Most functionalities are in beta status and are under integration or testing in the pilots as expected and the Fiware Context Broker has been populated with most information about the waste management systems of the pilots.

However, some deviations have arisen:

- Incidents reporting has been implemented but not tested under real conditions in Zamudio. The possibility of including graphical evidences and requests of the collection of bulky waste are still pending.
- The detection of anomalies in the waste generation patterns is not still possible as not enough historical data are available.
- Another feature that has not started its implementation is the Citizen Behaviour Tracking.

On the contrary, some functionalities are ahead of schedule:

- The user's identification systems of Cascais, Zamudio and Seveso are under production.
- The retrieval of collection route information by the Truck Data App developed by FDeusto is under testing in one lorry in Zamudio. In Cascais, currently, the collection data from the trucks are already stored and managed in MawisU2 except for the FMS data (truck's engine data). Another on-board computer is being used by the staff in Cascais. In January 2019, it is planned to swap

the current devices by the new mini-Operands. The same collection data will be gathered together with the FMS data from the engine.

- Fallback solution for the publishing of information to the Fiware Context Broker are already implemented for the cases of: R19, R20, composting plants, waste characterization.
- The vision-based system for supporting the detection of improper as part of the Truck Data App of FDeusto is already implemented and tested in one lorry.
- The Rules Manager tool (Sandwich) is already developed and is being tested within the Waste4Think architecture

More details about the components of R1 are available in *D2.1 Technical Documentation of R1: Operation and Management Module*.

3.2.1.2 R2: Collection Module

The optimization of the routes depending on the fill level is under production from Milestone 2 in Cascais. The rest of functionalities to manage waste collection with the MiniOperand from Moba, in terms of software, are ahead of the plan and have reached production status. Notwithstanding, it is not tested with the mini-Operand on the field yet. Nowadays, in Cascais such functionalities are managed (in the trucks) with a different device. With the MiniOperands installed, it will be finally an integrated solution within the W4T developments.

More details can be found in Deliverable D2.5. Technical Documentation of R2: Collection Module. The implementation results could be consulted in Deliverable D2.6 Implementation of R2: Collection Module foreseen by March 2019.

Regarding the Invoicing Module, the possibility of using Softline's tool (Wintarif, which is under production from Milestone 2 in Seveso) in Zamudio and Cascais was evaluated, but finally discarded due to the high level of technological and legal integration needed. On one hand, taxes are a critical component of the municipalities that have strong legal restrictions (information sharing, integration with other restricted systems, etc.) that could not be technically cost-effective to fulfil for partners not familiarized with the local legislation. On the other hand, given the critical nature of the system, local and quick accessible support in the maintenance phase is going to be needed. It is not clear that an SME could provide support in the local language demanded by the different pilot sites (Euskara/Spanish, Italian and Portuguese at least; Greek probably latter on). Finally, the integration of Wintarif with the software already in place in all pilot sites is probably more expensive (considering both the set-up during the project and the maintenance after the project) than the creation of a new module from scratch. However, although each software is highly dependent on the ecosystem implemented in every pilot, they will be based on the architecture defined by Softline considering the minimum requirements of the data input, data output and the algorithms of the

invoice module. This supporting approach of Softline is intended exactly to provide an integrated methodology to the project solutions.

The details of the particular implementations for Cascais and Zamudio is explained next.

In the case of Cascais, the communication between MawisU2, the e-lock provider and the gamification CityPoints App is under integration. Even though it is not fully integrated, the PAYT approach has been tested. EMAC is able to consult all the information now from Mawis 2.0 to download it and issue the collective PAYT (integration with the gamification CityPoints App). However, since the implementation of an individual PAYT in Cascais is still being considered in the agenda of Waste4Think, progress in the Invoicing Module in Cascais will move forward until discussing with ERSAR (Waste and Water Regulatory Body in Portugal) the possibilities of implementing this scheme. More details about the status of PAYT in the pilots will be available in Deliverable D5.3 New regulations to implement PAYT systems by March 2019.

In the case of Zamudio, there is a delay in the integration due to a change in the provider of the municipal database, so the discussion about the integration was postponed until the new contract (July 2018). The integration was accepted and validated by the water utility responsible for delivering the invoices to the citizens. A new proposal regulation for the hotel industry, shops and homes has been already validated. The proposal is still to be validated by the industry. It will be validated by January 2019 with the final approval of the regulation.

More information about Invoicing Modules are available in Deliverable 5.1 Technical Documentation of the Invoicing Module for R2.

3.2.1.3 R3: Planning Module

As set in D1.4 several modules that were planned to be in other parts of the architecture now are considered part of the Planning Module. In particular, the Green Procurement tool (previously in R1), Mid Term Planning tool (previously in R2) and the part of the Invoicing module to formulate the PAYT algorithm (previously in R2) are now part of the Planning module (R3) as these tools refers to the planification of actions.

The implementation of some functional requirements is delayed. Please note that we have been prioritizing the implementation of all functional requirements needed to perform the baseline and the monitoring of the actions (nowcasting) as these are needed by other task:

- In the case of What-if scenarios the logic behind the software simulations and the visualizations have been prioritized over the implementation of the scenario configuration tools. Currently, what-if scenarios can be customized according to a configuration file.
- The Green Procurement module has not yet reached the beta status at this stage.

On the contrary, some functionalities are ahead of schedule.

- In the case of Seveso, the short term planning for the management of activities, vehicles and human resources in the waste collection cycle has already been implemented and is currently under production
- Simulation of the transport means and route collection is in RC status.
- On the other hand, the necessity of developing a tool for the design and monitoring of Social Actions has arisen. This tool can later help feed the simulation engine with information about the impact of prevention campaigns, and also feed both the Circular Economy module and the Observatory to track the evolution in the waste management system depending on the Social Actions implemented on each moment.

The details of all the planning modules can be found in Deliverable D2.7. The implementation results could be consulted in Deliverable D2.8 Implementation of R3: Planning Module by March 2019.

3.2.1.4 R4: Circular Economy Module

According to the Grant Agreement, by Milestone 3, a beta implementation of the Circular Economy Planning Module and an update of the technical documentation should have been available. However, the module has a slight delay in terms of implementation. At the moment, the final version of technical documentation is done, the data model has been adapted with the Social Actions module, so that when they become best practices they are linked to this database as well as D1.2 database being spreaded with new best practices including domestic ones to also feed the Citizen App.

Following the Grant Agreement, a RC version of the Circular Economy Planning Module will be available for Milestone 4, including Deliverable D2.10, as long as it is possible, been tested in one of the pilots.

3.2.2 Apps

According to the Grant Agreement, at the end of this phase we should have:

“Continue the development.”

Annex II. Actions to Carry out for each
Eco-innovative Solution in Every Pilot and Phase

Annex 3 shows how these general guidelines are distributed into the different functional requirements of the apps that have to be implemented and their testing at the pilot sites, as well as their status at Milestone 3 and the estimated status for Milestone 4. In general, all functional requirements should have reached beta status.

Apps are slightly delayed. In order to overcome this delay, a new approach based on a tight integration with the rest of eco-solution in the web platform has been developed for the citizen App and Local trade

App, which have been also merged into a unique App to ease market penetration as target groups are the same.

Most functionalities will be available to be tested in the pilot sites by December 2018: information about clean points, waste containers, social actions, waste management system (information already available in Fiware, Deliverable D2.1 Technical Documentation of R1: Operation and Management Module), as well as the forms to report incidences and publish good examples of sustainable behaviour. However, those functionalities related to PAYT implementation in Zamudio (My behaviour section in the App) will have to wait until the availability of the smart containers.

More details about the apps can be found in Deliverable D4.11 Technical Documentation of the Apps of R5, R6 and R7. The Apps will be available by March 2019 with more information in Deliverable D4.12 Implementation of the Apps of R5, R6 and R7.

3.2.3 Educational Materials

According to the Grant Agreement, at the end of this phase we should have:

“Initial implementation without real-data.”

Annex II. Actions to Carry out for each
Eco-innovative Solution in Every Pilot and Phase

Annex 4 shows how these general guidelines are distributed into the different functional requirements that have to be implemented and their testing at the pilot sites together with their status at Milestone 3 and the estimated status at Milestone 4. In general, all functional requirements should have reached beta status except the functional requirements related to the citizen science actions. Nevertheless, in this case, the learning materials should have been integrated with the curriculum of Hallandri and Zamudio.

As explained in D1.4. an internal change has been made regarding the serious games over this plan. It was agreed to speed up the implementation of the Sorting Game and Eco-Design game in order to start earlier with the Social Actions that use them. To this end, most efforts have been focused on the development of these games reaching a higher level of development (1 in the case of the Sorting Game) that is under final approval testing in the 4 pilots. However, in the case of the Eco-design game, although an RC version is ready the localisation to each pilot has required more time than anticipated.

The implementation of the Virtual City and Planning game was delayed but has caught up. Especially with respect to the planning that have progressed to a beta version Virtual city is currently still in prototype but is still expected to have a RC in March 2019.

Regarding R8, at M28 the 4 STEM Lessons are available in final version and tested in Real Conditions in Zamudio pilot.

About the 6 Digital Projects, 2 of them are also in final version and ready to be tested by pilots involved (Zamudio and Halandri). The 4 remaining ones are available in a “Alfa” version. Final integration is missing and also a follow-up testing by pilots.

In reference to Mobile Games, 3 of them are in Beta version and ready to be tested by corresponding pilots (Zamudio and Halandri). The remaining one is in design phase and expected to be released by January. 2019.

Finally, the only group of functional requirements that is delayed is the one related to the Citizen Behaviour Tracking (Learning Analytics). At this moment only the Learning Analytics KPIs for the Sorting Game are defined.

More details about Learning materials can be found in Deliverables *D4.3 Implementation of R8: STEM lessons*, *D4.4 Implementation of R8: Digital Learning Materials*, *D4.5 Technical Documentation of the Serious Games (R9-R12)*, *D4.6 Implementation of R9: Sorting Game*, *D4.7 Implementation of the R10: Eco-design Game*.

3.2.4 Social Actions

According to the Grant Agreement, at the end of this phase we should have:

“Definition of actions dependent on data with help of R3.
Continuation of IT tools independent actions.”

Annex II. Actions to Carry out for each
Eco-innovative Solution in Every Pilot and Phase

Annex 4 shows how these general guidelines are distributed into the different functional requirements that the Social Actions have implemented and the status of their testing at the pilot sites as well as their status at Milestone 3 and estimation for Milestone 4. In this case, we should give a slightly different interpretation to the levels on the table. In general, all objectives should have reached beta status except for those that are related to the monitorization methodology of the social actions and the identification of the best practices that should be in production status.

In general terms the Social Actions are according to the plan. In particular, all the pilots have initiated or deployed almost all the non ICT Social Actions foreseen. Regarding those actions based on the already developed ICT tools, they have also been started. For more information about the status of each particular Social Action please refer to Section 5 of this deliverable. Note also that the Social Actions Module belonging to R3 is already implemented and under testing in the four pilot sites which facilitates the monitoring of the Social Actions as can be seen in Section 4.

More details about the Social Actions definition can be also found in Deliverables *D4.1 Implementation of R17: Non ICT innovative Social Actions* and *D4.2 Implementation of R17: ICT based innovative Social Actions*.

3.2.5 Treatment Plants

According to the Grant Agreement, at the end of this phase we should have made the:

“Construction of the plants.”

Annex II. Actions to Carry out for each
Eco-innovative Solution in Every Pilot and Phase

Annex 5 shows how these general guidelines are distributed into the different functional requirements that the New Treatment Plant have implemented and the status of their testing at the pilot sites as well as their status at Milestone 2. As before, in this case, we should give a slightly different interpretation to the levels on the table using a unique criterion shown in this Annex. In general, all functional requirements should have reached α status.

These eco-solutions (R19 and R20) are ahead of plan, several of the functional requirements have already achieve 1 status.

Regarding “Biomass product result from the Biomass Treatment Plant” (R19), the Municipality of Halandri examines source separation and separate collection of the Household Food Waste (HFW), aiming to evaluate the generated biomass called FORBI (Food Residue Biomass) product as a potential feedstock for alternative processes aiming at the recovery of high-grade materials and/or energy. Participating citizens (almost 1000) were provided with special collection bins and bags. The technical requirements of the pilot are presented in *D3.1 Technical Documentation of R19*.

The pre-sorted HFW are collected twice a week, the special designated trucks by the end of the project will be equipped with a CNG system capable of running on both diesel and biogas generated from FORBI, for the evaluation and demonstration of the cyclic economy concept.

The collected HFW is transferred to the waste management facility of the municipality, where it undergoes drying and shredding, to produce a “biomass product” called FORBI in a special dryer/shredder. The dryer/shredder has a capacity of 380L; daily the dryer/shredder processes two cycles of 150kg each.

The generated product FORBI is evaluated on NTUA premises, as a potential feedstock for high TRL alternative uses. The three valorisation alternatives of FORBI amount to production of:

1. Gaseous biofuels (methane, hydrogen and HYTHANE)
2. compost and
3. pellets

For the production of gaseous biofuels, FORBI is used as the key feedstock for both lab-scale and pilot-scale bioreactors aiming at biohydrogen and/or biomethane and biohythane production.

The experimental analysis is developed in NTUA (assessment of biomethane, biohydrogen and biohythane potential and both laboratory and pilot scale reactor experiments).

A two-stage anaerobic process which consists of: a pilot-scale anaerobic unit with a 4 m³ methane bioreactor and a biohydrogen production anaerobic bioreactor. The hydrogen producing bioreactor operates under a retention time of a few hours and is fed with a FORBI suspension, while the methane producing one operates at higher retention time, typically 20 days and is fed with the hydrogen bioreactor's effluent. The whole process is controlled by PLC (Programmable Logic Controller). The pilot plant will operate to produce (a) hythane which is a mixture of hydrogen and methane, roughly 15/85% respectively in a two-stage process and (b) an extra stream of methane. The biogas production from this pilot plant is estimated at about 1 m³/d. Purification and compression of the biogas (methane and/or hythane), is to take place through a special unit (removing carbon dioxide, hydrogen sulfide and moisture and then compressing the biogas to 200 bars) leading to bioCNG (Compressed Natural Gas) production. Two collection trucks will be available to consume the produced bioCNG as alternative fuel to diesel/gasoline in order to reduce the transportation cost (biowaste converted to biofuel which is then used for operating the collection vehicle to close the loop) while protecting the environment through the substitution of fossil fuels.

-NTUA develops pelletization by using the dried/shredded food waste which involves the processes of segregating, crushing, and mixing high and low heat value organic waste material and solidifying it to produce fuel pellets. Pellets can be used for heating plant boilers and for the generation of electricity. They can be provided as a good substitute for coal and wood for domestic and industrial heating purposes.

-Production of compost from the biomass product, green waste and the solid fraction of the digestate is tested. The quality of the generated compost is assessed in existing composting reactors (Lab reactor 28L) and 280L composter respectively at NTUA and at larger scale: 4 tonnes. This last experimental composting is taking place on the premises of a collaborating company.

The main objective of R19 is to define the complete procedure of the collection system (truck, bins and route for the Municipality of Halandri within the Waste4Think project) - the technical specifications of the pilot plant (operation, instrumentation and control) as well as the best methodology for HFW collection (bins, trucks and collection routing). Finally, NTUA continuously develops and evaluates the generated FORBI (Food Residue Biomass) product as a potential feedstock for the valorisation following the 3 high TRL alternatives for the recovery of high-grade materials: gaseous biofuels (methane, hydrogen and Hythane), pellets and compost.

Regarding R20 (Biofuels and Compost Production From Disposable Nappies) functional requirements have reached level β (All functionalities are implemented but some of them do not behave as expected. Obvious bugs have been found. The system is being tested in lab conditions.) Currently, the Waste Treatment Unit (WTU) is operating at the premises of University of Patras and is being optimized for its full

scale operation at its final location. The final location of the WTU has changed, since various issues (mainly political, legal and some minor technical ones) have occurred, that seem to prevent us from installing the treatment unit in a nursery. More specifically, a new law (no 4549/2018, 14/6/2018) changing the procedures for Environmental Permits has been released. The appropriate degrees for its implementation have not yet been issued, and the directorate responsible for issuing these permits has not yet been defined. Also, a new decree (Presidential Decree 59, 29/7/2018) regulating the land uses has been released, and we are still uncertain of its implications. Under these circumstances the administration proposed the change of the WTU location in order to avoid any opposition that would target Waste4Think because of its popularity and widespread acclaim.

Therefore, the original planning has changed and the WTU will be installed in the municipality's gym facilities. The proposed location is about 50 meters away from the dryer/shredder unit, there is no legal issue, and several uses will be examined for demonstration, i.e. feeding the biogas in the gym's boiler, feeding a separate boiler to heat an isolated gym's room and other options which we are still under examination. The collection and transportation of the nappies is easy and effortless for the municipality. There are also technical advantages in such a solution. Notably, the gym's facilities provide a much stronger power supply and ease of operation at any time of the day, plus some other minor technical benefits.

In addition, in order to meet the needs for the management/treatment of nappies and not particularly the co-treatment of nappies with expired food products, as initially posed at the beginning of Waste4Think, both partners (UPatras and GreenTech) responsible for R20 proposed to perform lab tests for an adequate period (eg. 3-4 months) in Work Package WP3. Implementation of alternatives for the recovery of high-grade materials and then proceed with the pilot scenario (WP1. Pilots planning and execution) as an extra scenario and not in replacement of the ones that have been studied and discussed up until now. This will not jeopardize the operation of the pilot plant or the Grant Agreement obligations. This situation has resulted because the various stakeholders have already identified various solutions for the management of expired food products, without however completely solving the issue, but there is not any alternative solution for the treatment of nappies. The latter waste stream is currently led to landfills or incineration, and its organic content is not valorised. Since the specific problem is differentiated to the original co-treatment problem due to the nappies hydrolysate characteristics, a different type of anaerobic reactor (UASB high-rate) is required compared with the CSTR-type reactors, used so far.

More details about the design of the Treatment Plants can be found in Deliverables D3.1 to D3.3.

3.2.6 Waste4Think Story Map

As set out in Deliverable D1.4, a web application has been designed to facilitate the monitoring of the project activities in a more agile and intuitive way.

The table of contents with the different sections included in the application is provided below:

1. European context
2. Waste4think Goals
3. Partners
4. Pilot site:
 - 4.1 Zamudio
 - 4.2 Cascais
 - 4.3 Seveso
 - 4.4 Halandri
1. 20 eco-innovative solutions:
 - 5.1 Operation and planning tools:
 - 5.1.1 Operation and Management Module
 - 5.1.1.1 Observatory
 - 5.1.1.2 Complex event processing (sandwich)
 - 5.1.1.3 Pilot data Ingestion
 - 5.1.1.3.1 Characterization
 - 5.1.1.3.2 Treatment deposit plant
 - 5.1.1.4 Waste management KPIs
 - 5.1.1.4.1 Cascais
 - 5.1.1.4.1.1 Baseline (Month 12). KPIs Results (02/2017)
 - 5.1.1.4.2 Halandri
 - 5.1.1.4.2.1 Baseline (Month 12). KPIs Results (12/2015)
 - 5.1.1.4.2.2 Monitoring (Month 17)
 - 5.1.1.4.2.3 Monitoring (Month 28)
 - 5.1.1.4.2.4 Evolution of the High level KPIs with respect to the baseline and monitoring (11/2018)
 - 5.1.1.4.3 Seveso
 - 5.1.1.4.3.1 Baseline (Month 12). KPIs Results (04/2017)
 - 5.1.1.4.3.2 Monitoring (Month 17)
 - 5.1.1.4.3.3 Monitoring (Month 28)
 - 5.1.1.4.3.4 Evolution of the High level KPIs with respect to the baseline and monitoring (04/2018)
 - 5.1.1.4.4 Zamudio
 - 5.1.1.4.4.1 Baseline (Month 12). KPIs Results (06/2017)
 - 5.1.2 Collection Module:
 - 5.1.2.1 Collection Optimization:
 - 5.1.2.1.1 Seveso
 - 5.1.2.1.2 Cascais
 - 5.1.2.2 Truck Data App
 - 5.1.3 Planning Module
 - 5.1.3.1 Environmental Impact Transport of Waste Collection (Geosimulation)

- 5.1.3.2 Zero Waste
- 5.1.3.3 Social Action
- 5.1.4 Circular economy module:
 - 5.1.4.1 Circular economy
- 5.2 New treatments
 - 5.2.1 Bio-fuel and Compost Production Plant
 - 5.2.2 Predried and shredded Bio-Waste
- 5.3 Educational materials
 - 5.3.1 Serious games
 - 5.3.1.1 Sorting game
 - 5.3.1.2 Eco-desing game
 - 5.3.1.3 Mayor's table
 - 5.3.1.4 Virtual city game
 - 5.3.2 Learning materials:
 - 5.3.2.1 Digital projects:
 - 5.3.2.1.1 After the concert
 - 5.3.2.1.2 Where is wastey?
 - 5.3.2.2 Steam Lesson:
 - 5.3.2.2.1 What has happened? _1
 - 5.3.2.2.2 What has happened? _2
 - 5.3.2.2.3 How can the guilty be found?
 - 5.3.2.2.4 Wastey blues us
 - 5.3.2.3 Mobile Games:
 - 5.3.2.3.1 Owaste
 - 5.3.2.3.2 Sunflower
 - 5.3.2.3.3 Treasure machine
- 5.4 Citizen science
 - 5.4.1 Halandri
 - 5.4.2 Zamudio
- 5.5 Apps
- 5.6 Prevention and Best practices:
 - 5.6.1 Best Practices
 - 5.6.2 Best Practice Book
 - 5.6.3 Economics Instruments
 - 5.6.3.1 Seveso
- 1. Zenodo. Community Waste4think

The application in the form of website is not available for public use because confidential information is contained. For this reason, a reduced version in PFD format of the StoryMaps for the project Waste4Think is included in the Annex 6 of this deliverable.

4 Social Action Plan Implementation

4.1 Summary of the Social Action Programme status

Following the methodology described in *D1.4 Preparatory actions Report*, in this section the Social Actions carried out until Milestone 3 are included.

In Annex 7 the Gantt Chart for the Social Actions implementation and the status at Milestone 3 are included. This Gantt Chart is an update to the planning calendars foreseen in Deliverable *D4.1 Implementation of R17: non ICT Innovative Social Actions*. Please note that this Gantt will be updated in further versions of D4.1 and in Deliverable *D4.2 Implementation of R17: ICT based Innovative Social Actions*, if necessary. It includes the planification of those actions supported by the eco-solutions developed in Waste4Think. The qualitative description including lessons learnt of the Social Actions and the quantitative results carried out until Milestone 3 can be consulted in Annex 8 in the data model with the previous mentioned new methodology and will be published in the Waste4Think Community in Zenodo together with the qualitative results.

Finally the public data model of the Social Actions with all this information can be consulted in [Waste4Think Zenodo Community](https://zenodo.org/doi/10.5281/zenodo.1745487) (DOI 10.5281/zenodo.1745487).

5 KPIs monitoring

5.1 Methodology updates or improvements

During this period no updates has been made in the WESTE methodology for the monitoring of the pilots.

5.2 Integral waste management evaluation indicators

According to the pilot planning and the environmental programme of each pilot site the set of KPIs defined for the integral waste management evaluation will be calculated and reported when significant changes in the management system would be expected, as it is shown in Table 1.

At this stage of the project, the main changes in the waste management systems have been:

- Seveso: Consolidation of the PAYT implementation, zero waste events and involvement of Virtuous Households
- Halandri: Collection of biowaste and its valorisation into biofuel and compost
- Cascais: Collective PAYT implementation
- Zamudio: Zerowaste events and ecosystems, new collection system is delayed due to a delay in the tendering process

More details about the Social Actions status can be found in Section 4.

In this report only results of the monitoring at Milestone 3 for Seveso and Halandri are included. In the case of Cascais the characterization is being carried out during the elaboration of this report and results will be included in D1.6. In the case of Zamudio, the characterization has been postponed due to the delay in the tendering process of the containers. However, as important social actions are being carried out in this stage a new characterization will be made in the following weeks that will be included in D1.6. The database with the last updated results of the characterizations will be available in [Waste4Think Zenodo Community](#).

5.2.1 Halandri

Since Month 17 where the baseline waste generation characterization was developed a new waste collection circuit was introduced in the Municipality of Halandri: Paper & Cardboard (yellow bin). On September 2018 an in-depth composition characterization took place, following the above mentioned approach:

The waste circuits (WCC) analysed were the following:

1. Residual waste (green bin)
2. Recyclables, general (blue bin)
3. Paper and Cardboard (yellow bin)

Five collection points were chosen as the sampling locations. The criteria for choosing the specific points were the following:

1. There should be exactly one bin of each WCC, in each of the points.
2. Only residential building should be around the chosen points (no businesses, schools, public buildings etc.)

In the morning of the 12th of September (day 0) the bins in the selected collection points were emptied. Then for seven consecutive days (13/9-19/9, days 1-7) the bins in the selected collection points were collected and transported to the MRF of Aspropyrgos to carry out the composition analysis:

1. Each WCC was split into the 33 W4T waste fractions (as listed in the document “*Procedure for the calculation of the baseline and pilots progress*”)
2. The initial samples, as well as the different fractions were weighted each day.
3. After splitting the total amount of waste into the several waste fractions, the waste remained were passed over a 10mm sieve. The materials that did not pass the sieve were distributed among the groups. The material that passed was considered as Fines.

The total masses of the samples were: 320kg from the residual waste, 151.5 kg from the recyclables and 40 from the Paper & Cardboard waste collection circuit.

The separate waste collection streams of the Municipality of Halandri are: residual waste (green bin), recyclables (plastic, metal, paper, glass) (blue bin). Paper/cardboard (yellow bin) started in 2017. Household Food Waste (brown bin) is also separately collected for approximately 250 households participating in the W4T pilot-scale programme. Other specific waste streams separately collected are: used tires, batteries and accumulators, end-of-life vehicles (ELVs), waste of electric and electronic equipment (WEEEs). A more detailed description of the pilot can be found in Annex D of deliverable D1.1.

Based on the results of the characterization, it is estimated that food waste corresponds to 40% of the household waste, thus may be diverted from landfilling (which is the waste management approach for the residual waste) if the collection system of food waste introduced in Waste4Think is extended to the whole population. This can be increased further if recyclables collection is improved in terms of quality, as the residues from the blue bin are also led to the landfill today.

The main observations extracted from the characterization are as follows:

1. The level of impurities in the basic waste collection streams is low:
 - a. For the residual waste (considering that food waste separate collection is only in pilot-scale, thus food waste is not an impurity in the residual waste collection circuit): 17.94%
 - b. For the Recyclables/General: 12.28%
 - c. For the Paper & Cardboard: 5.14%
2. The households of the Municipality of Halandri achieved, based on the characterization, an extremely high recycling rate: 75%

Since, M17 where the baseline characterization the following can be observed:

1. The Paper & Cardboard waste circuit which was introduced after the baseline, is highly pure.
2. The impurities in the Recyclables/General waste circuit are much lower.

3. Based on the experience gained from the baseline characterization, we carried out a much more detailed characterization, developing a much more accurate understanding of the waste composition.

It is proven that the Social Actions and Campaigns carried out in the Municipality of Halandri the last months, led to an improved overall efficiency of the separate collection scheme.

Table 4 summarizes the results of the update of the KPIs for Halandri for month 28 (September 2018) and Table 5 shows its comparative with the baseline.

Table 4 Results of the Waste Management KPIs for Halandri (September 2018)

ID Objectives	KPIs (High Level)	High Level KPIs Results	KPIs (Intermediate and Low Level)	Intermediate and Low Level KPIs Results	RESIDUAL WASTE		SEPARATE COLLECTION CIRCUITS						Cartography additional information (GIS) Code Index Map
					WCC1-WCC4		WCC5	WCC6	WCC7	WCC8	WCC9	WCC14	
					Residual Waste		Green Waste	Bulky and Green	Recyclables General (Blue Bin)	Paper/Cardboard (Yellow Bin)	Glass	Biowaste pilot	
					Domestic + commercial		domestic-commercial-public	Domestic-Commercial	Domestic-Commercial	Domestic	Domestic-Commercial	Domestic	
Collective (street green bins)		kerbside	kerbside	Collective (street blue bins)	kerbside	Street blue bells	collective closed bins						
O.1	T.1. Average reduction of municipal waste generation	N/A	T.1.2. Real amount (level) of waste generated (RAG) (waste characterization %)	Biowaste 43%; Paper and cardboard 13%; Glass 4%; Plastics 8%; Metals 2%; Complex packaging 2% Textiles / shoes 1%; Nappies 1%; 10mm sieved fractions 2%; Others (aggregated) 24%	Biowaste 62%; Paper and cardboard 6%; Glass 1%; Plastics 7%; Metals 2%; Complex packaging 2% Textiles / shoes 1%; Nappies 1%; 10mm sieved fractions 2%; Others (aggregated) 15%	Biowaste 72%; Paper and cardboard 0%; Glass 0%; Plastics 0%; Metals 0%; Complex packaging 0% Textiles / shoes 0%; Nappies 0%; 10mm sieved fractions 8%; Others (aggregated) 20%	Biowaste 28%; Paper and cardboard 0%; Glass 0%; Plastics 0%; Metals 0%; Complex packaging 0% Textiles / shoes 0%; Nappies 0%; 10mm sieved fractions 0%; Others (aggregated) 72%	Biowaste 2%; Paper and cardboard 27%; Glass 22%; Plastics 27%; Metals 8%; Complex packaging 3% Textiles / shoes 3%; Nappies 0%; 10mm sieved fractions 0%; Others (aggregated) 7%	Biowaste 0%; Paper and cardboard 95%; Glass 1%; Plastics 2%; Metals 0%; Complex packaging 1% Textiles / shoes 0%; Nappies 0%; 10mm sieved fractions 0%; Others (aggregated) 0%	Biowaste 0%; Paper and cardboard 0%; Glass 96%; Plastics 3%; Metals 1%; Complex packaging 0% Textiles / shoes 0%; Nappies 0%; 10mm sieved fractions 0%; Others (aggregated) 0%	Biowaste 98%; Paper and cardboard 0%; Glass 0%; Plastics 0%; Metals 0%; Complex packaging 0% Textiles / shoes 0%; Nappies 0%; 10mm sieved fractions 0%; Others (aggregated) 2%	N/A	
			T.1.3. Annual generation rate (aGR) (Kg/inhab/year)	576,35	338,65	11,13	97,84	87,92	32,52	0,54	0,66	3.3.1, 3.3.2, 3.3.3, 3.3.4, 3.3.5	
O.2	T.2. Increase of the average of urban waste sorted	N/A	T.2.3. Total gross separate collection (gSC) (ton)	17.635,21	N/A	826	7259	6523	2413	40	49	N/A	
			T.2.4. Net separate collection rate (nSC rate) (%)	N/A	N/A	9,98%	63,16%	43,45%	37,44%	0,00%	0,00%	N/A	
			T.2.5. Gross separate collection rate (gSC rate) (%)	41,24%	N/A	12,52%	68,48%	49,53%	39,47%	2,18%	0,28%	N/A	
			T.2.2. Level of impurities (improvers) (imp) (%)	N/A	17,9	20,3	7,8	12,3	5,1	100,0	100,0	N/A	
			T.2.1. Amount of waste collected (WC) (ton/year)	42.760,21	25125	826	7259	6523	2413	40	49	3.3.1, 3.3.2,	

												3.3.3, 3.3.4, 3.3.5
			T.1.1. Estimated biowaste treated by community/home composting (kg or ton)	-	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A
0.2	T.3. Decrease of the average of waste sent to final disposal	N/A	T.3.1. Primary waste destination (rwPD) (ton)	42.760,21	25125	826	7259	6523	2413	40	49	N/A
			T.3.2. Dry recyclables to primary destination (dPD) (ton)	16.760,21	N/A	N/A	7259	6523	2413			N/A
			T.3.3. Organic recyclables to primary destination (oPD) (ton)	875,00	N/A	826	7259	N/A	N/A	40	49	N/A
			T.3.4. Residual waste to primary destination (rwPD) (ton)	25125	25125	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A
			T.3.5. Destination recycling (DREC) (Kg)	LI	LI	LI	LI	LI	LI	LI	LI	N/A
	T.1. Average reduction of municipal waste generation	N/A	review T.1.2 and T.1.3									N/A
	T.2. Increase of the average of urban waste sorted	N/A	review T.2.3, T.2.4, T.2.5, T.2.2, T.2.1 and T.1.1									N/A
0.3	S.1. Number of people saying that have modified their habits (end of project)	N/A	S.1.1. Number of people saying that have modified their habits regarding prevention	0	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A			N/A
			S.1.2. Number of people saying that have modified their habits regarding separate collection	0	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A			N/A
0.4	S.2. Increase the easy access to the separation facilities	N/A	T.4.1. Ratio accessibility residual waste to recyclable waste	0,38 (median)	Proximity (good)	LI	LI	Proximity (median)	LI	LI	LI	N/A
			T.4.2. Accessibility to collection system (m)	N/A	46	LI	LI	120	LI	LI	LI	N/A
			T.4.3. Accessibility to the recycling centres (Km)	25	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A			7.2
			S.2.1. Collection points accessible to disability people	LI	LI	LI	LI	LI	LI	LI	LI	N/A
0.4	T.4. Kilometres saved by the project	N/A	T.4.4. Distance km of the collection route (km)	1087	751	-	-	336	-	-	-	6.3.1, 6.3.2
0.4	E.1. GHG emissions saved by the project	N/A	T.5. Life Cycle Assessment (LCA)	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A			N/A
0.4	S.3. Increase of green jobs created	N/A	S.3.1. Green jobs created	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	N/A
0.4	S.4. Increase of legislative changes proposed	N/A	S.4.1. Legislative changes proposed	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	N/A

O.4	S.5. Increase of Zero Waste Events	N/A	S.5.1. N° of Zero Waste Events	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	N/A
O.4	S.6. Increase of Zero Waste Eco-Systems	N/A	S.6.1. N° of Zero Waste Eco-Systems	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	N/A
O.4	S.7. Increase of Green Public Procurement	N/A	S.7.1. N° of Green Public Procurement	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	N/A
O.4	C.1. Decrease of the average of the urban management cost	N/A	C.1.3. Management Cost (MC) (€)	331,00	183,00		0	148,00	0,00			N/A
			C.1.3.1. Collection and transport cost (CTC) (€)	263,00	138,00		0	125,00	0,00			N/A
			C.1.3.2. Final management costs (FMC) (€)	68,00	45,00		0	23,00	0,00			N/A
			C.1.3.3. Other common costs (oCO) (€)	LI	LI	LI	LI	LI	LI			N/A
			C.1.1. Budget applied to awareness and prevention campaigns (€/year)	LI	LI	LI	LI	LI	LI			N/A
			C.1.2. Treatment gate fee (€/ton treated)	LI	LI	LI	LI	LI	LI			N/A

Table 5 Evolution of the High Level KPIs with respect to the baseline in Halandri

Amount of waste collected (ton/year)	RESIDUAL WASTE	SEPARATE COLLECTION CIRCUITS						TOTAL ton/year
	WCC1-WCC4	WCC5	WCC6	WCC7	WCC8	WCC9	WCC14	
	Residual Waste	Green Waste	Bulky and Green	Recyclables General (Blue Bin)	Paper/Cardboard (Yellow Bin)	Glass	Biowaste pilot	
	Domestic + commercial	domestic-commercial-public	Domestic-Commercial	Domestic-Commercial	Domestic	Domestic-Commercial	Domestic	
Collective (street green bins)	kerbside	kerbside	Collective (street blue bins)	kerbside	Street blue bells	collective closed bins		
Baseline (04/2017)	24166,00	850,00	7268,00	7277,00	0,00	33,00	0,00	40090,90
Monitoring (09/2018)	25125,00	826,00	7259,00	6523,00	2413,00	40,00	49,00	42760,21
T.2. Increase of the average of urban waste sorted (T.2.1. Amount of waste collected (WC) (ton/year)	959	-24	-9	-754	2413	7	49	2669,314
%	3,97	-2,82	-0,12	-10,36	#DIV/0!	21,21	#DIV/0!	6,66

Annual generation rate (Kg/inhab/year)	RESIDUAL WASTE	SEPARATE COLLECTION CIRCUITS						TOTAL
	WCC1-WCC4	WCC5	WCC6	WCC7	WCC8	WCC9	WCC14	
	Residual Waste	Green Waste	Bulky and Green	Recyclables General (Blue Bin)	Paper/Cardboard (Yellow Bin)	Glass	Biowaste pilot	
								Kg/inhab/year
Baseline (04/2017)	325,72	11,46	97,96	98,08	0,00	0,44	0,00	540,37
Monitoring (09/2018)	338,65	11,13	97,84	87,92	32,52	0,54	0,66	576,35
T.1. Average reduction of municipal waste generation (T.1.3. Annual generation rate (aGR) (Kg/inhab/year)	-12,93	0,32	0,12	10,16	-32,52	-0,09	-0,66	-35,98
%	-3,82	2,91	0,12	11,56	-100,00	-17,50	-100,00	-6,24

Impurities (%)	RESIDUAL WASTE	SEPARATE COLLECTION CIRCUITS					
	Residual Waste	Green Waste	Bulky and Green	Recyclables General (Blue Bin)	Paper/Cardboard (Yellow Bin)	Glass	Biowaste pilot
Baseline (04/2017)	25,71%	20,26%	7,76%	45,09%	0,00%	4,00%	0,00%
Monitoring (09/2018)	25,71%	20,26%	7,76%	45,09%	4,00%	4,00%	0,00%
T.2. Increase of the average of urban waste sorted (T.2.2. Level of impurities (improvers) (imp) (%)	lacking indicator	lacking indicator	lacking indicator	lacking indicator	4%	lacking indicator	lacking indicator

Impurities (kg)	RESIDUAL WASTE	SEPARATE COLLECTION CIRCUITS					
	Residual Waste	Green Waste	Bulky and Green	Recyclables General (Blue Bin)	Paper/Cardboard (Yellow Bin)	Glass	Biowaste pilot
Baseline (04/2017):	83,74	2,32	7,60	44,23	0,00	0,02	0,00
Monitoring (09/2018)	87,06	2,26	7,59	39,64	1,30	0,02	0,00
T.2. Increase of the average of urban waste sorted (T.2.2. Level of impurities (improvers) (imp) (Kg)	3,32	-0,07	-0,01	-4,58	1,30	0,00	0,00

5.2.2 Seveso

Waste characterizations have been carried out in April 2017 (baseline), November 2017 (monitoring 1) and April 2018 (monitoring 2) in order to assess the change related to the most important change of waste management in Seveso: the beginning of PAYT implementation, which started on the May 1st, 2017, and its consolidation during 2018.

One of the key considerations related to the further evolution of the system after the first monitoring performed in Nov 17 are the following:

- Impurities in residual waste (which means recyclable waste fraction incorrectly delivered in residual waste), after reducing from 65,2% (baseline) to 47.9% (monitoring 1, Nov 17) increased again, getting back to 63.9%
- Impurities in light packaging increased a little bit, from 28.8% to 29.2%.

These results lead to an interesting conclusion: there has been a sort of “rebound effect” after the first month of PAYT, and citizens seem to have forgotten some of the first good habits they learnt during the first months of PAYT implementation.

If we look at total amounts (kg/capita), these data combined show that the amount of residual waste stayed at the same level (from 58.1 to 60.7 kg/capita) and light packaging increased (from 29.9 to 34.1 kg/capita). Food waste impurities increased again a little bit, So, the absolute value of impurities returned (+12.6 kg/ca) almost at the same level of the baseline, even if total separate collection maintained at higher levels.

In other words, citizens “performed better” in separating, keeping residual waste per capita level low and maintained the quality of light packaging (at the same level of monitoring 1) but forgot the lessons learnt about the amount of recyclables that can still be moved away from residual waste to correctly separated fractions.

		Residual waste	Light packaging	Food waste	Totals
kg/capita	Baseline apr 17	71,7	30,7	67,17	
kg/capita	Monitoring nov 17	58,1	29,9	68,82	
kg/capita	Monitoring apr 18	60,7	34,1	72,16	
% impurities	Baseline apr 17	65,2%	17,9%	1,6%	
% impurities	Monitoring nov 17	47,9%	28,8%	2,8%	
% impurities	Monitoring apr 18	63,9%	29,2%	3,1%	

kg/capita	evolution apr 17 - nov 17	-18,9	+3,1	+0,9	-14,9
kg/capita	evolution nov 17 - apr 18	+11,0	+1,3	+0,3	+12,6

Table 6 Results of the Waste Management KPIs for Seveso (April 2018) summarizes the results of the update of the KPIs for Seveso for month 17 (April 2018) and

Table 7 shows its comparative with the baseline.

Table 6 Results of the Waste Management KPIs for Seveso (April 2018)

ID Objectives	KPIs (High Level)	High Level KPIs Results	KPIs (Intermediate and Low Level)	Intermediate and Low Level KPIs Results	RESIDUAL WASTE	SEPARATE COLLECTION CIRCUITS					Cartography additional information (GIS) Code Index Map
					WCC1-WCC4	WCC5-WCC6	WCC7-WCC8	WCC9	WCC10		
					Residual Waste	Light packaging	Food waste	Paper and cardboard	Glass		
					Domestic + commercial (+ street dustbins)	Domestic-Commercial	Domestic-Commercial	Domestic-Commercial	Domestic-Commercial		
					Door to door	Door to door	Door to door	Door to door	Door to door		
O.1	T.1. Average reduction of municipal waste generation	N/A	T.1.2. Real amount (level) of waste generated (RAG) (waste characterization %)	Biowaste 29%; Paper and cardboard 15%; Glass 9%; Plastics 8%; Metals 2%; Complex packaging 0% Textiles / shoes 2%; Nappies 1%; 10mm sieved fractions 5%; Others (aggregated) 28%	Biowaste 6%; Paper and cardboard 20%; Glass 0%; Plastics 19%; Metals 1%; Complex packaging 0% Textiles / shoes 12%; Nappies 7%; 10mm sieved fractions 21%; Others (aggregated) 13%	Biowaste 0%; Paper and cardboard 6%; Glass 0%; Plastics 61%; Metals 6%; Complex packaging 4% Textiles / shoes 0%; Nappies 0%; 10mm sieved fractions 0%; Others (aggregated) 23%	Biowaste 93%; Paper and cardboard 0%; Glass 0%; Plastics 0%; Metals 1%; Complex packaging 0% Textiles / shoes 0%; Nappies 1%; 10mm sieved fractions 4%; Others (aggregated) 1%	Biowaste 0%; Paper and cardboard 97%; Glass 0%; Plastics 0%; Metals 0%; Complex packaging 0% Textiles / shoes 0%; Nappies 0%; 10mm sieved fractions 0%; Others (aggregated) 3%	Biowaste 0%; Paper and cardboard 0%; Glass 86%; Plastics 0%; Metals 0%; Complex packaging 0% Textiles / shoes 0%; Nappies 0%; 10mm sieved fractions 0%; Others (aggregated) 14%	N/A	
			T.1.3. Annual generation rate (aGR) (Kg/inhab/year)	397,31	60,71	34,13	72,16	46,30	39,97	3.3.1, 3.3.2, 3.3.3, 3.3.4, 3.3.5	
O.2	T.2. Increase of the average of urban waste sorted	N/A	T.2.3. Total gross separate collection (gSC) (ton)	7.707,28	N/A	801,1542428	1693,924542	1086,934118	938,1434488	N/A	
			T.2.4. Net separate collection rate (nSC rate) (%)	N/A	N/A	80%	51%	75,962%	99,410%	N/A	
			T.2.5. Gross separate collection rate (gSC rate) (%)	84,39%	N/A	113%	53%	78,07%	115,59%	N/A	
			T.2.2. Level of impurities (impropers) (imp) (%)	N/A	63,9	29,2	3,1	2,7	14,0	N/A	
			T.2.1. Amount of waste collected (WC) (ton/year)	9.132,50	1425,219633	801,1542428	1693,924542	1086,934118	938,1434488	3.3.1, 3.3.2, 3.3.3, 3.3.4, 3.3.5	
	T.1.1. Estimated biowaste treated by community/home composting (kg or ton)	193,92	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A			
O.2	T.3. Decrease of the average of waste sent to final disposal	N/A	T.3.1. Primary waste destination (rwPD) (ton)	9.132,50	1425,219633	801,1542428	1693,924542	1086,934118	938,1434488	N/A	
			T.3.2. Dry recyclables to primary destination (dPD) (ton)	6.013,36	N/A	801,1542428	N/A	1086,934118	938,1434488	N/A	
			T.3.3. Organic recyclables to primary destination (oPD) (ton)	1.887,84	N/A	N/A	1693,924542	N/A	N/A	N/A	
			T.3.4. Residual waste to primary destination (rwPD) (ton)	1425,219633	1425,219633	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	
			T.3.5. Destination recycling (DREC) (Kg)	LI	LI	LI	LI	LI	LI	LI	N/A
O.3	T.1. Average reduction of municipal waste generation	N/A	review T.1.2 and T.1.3							N/A	
	T.2. Increase of the average of urban waste	N/A	review T.2.3, T.2.4, T.2.5, T.2.2, T.2.1 and T.1.1							N/A	

	sorted									
	S.1. Number of people saying that have modified their habits (end of project)	N/A	S.1.1. Number of people saying that have modified their habits regarding prevention	0	N/A					N/A
			S.1.2. Number of people saying that have modified their habits regarding separate collection	0	N/A					N/A
O.4	S.2. Increase the easy access to the separation facilities	N/A	T.4.1. Ratio accessibility residual waste to recyclable waste	1 (maximum)	100 % accessible (door to door for all fractions)					N/A
			T.4.2. Accessibility to collection system (m)	N/A	100 % accessible (door to door)					N/A
			T.4.3. Accessibility to the recycling centers (Km)	1,2	N/A					7.2
			S.2.1. Collection points accessible to disability people	100% accessible	100 % accessible (door to door)					N/A
O.4	T.4. Kilometres saved by the project	N/A	T.4.4. Distance km of the collection route (km)	6727	1435	1339	1319	1315	1319	6.3.1, 6.3.2
O.4	E.1. GHG emissions saved by the project	N/A	T.5. Life Cycle Assessment (LCA)	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A
O.4	S.3. Increase of green jobs created	N/A	S.3.1. Green jobs created	0	0					N/A
O.4	S.4. Increase of legislative changes proposed	N/A	S.4.1. Legislative changes proposed	2	0					N/A
O.4	S.5. Increase of Zero Waste Events	N/A	S.5.1. N° of Zero Waste Events	9	0					N/A
O.4	S.6. Increase of Zero Waste Eco-Systems	N/A	S.6.1. N° of Zero Waste Eco-Systems	0	0					N/A
O.4	S.7. Increase of Green Public Procurement	N/A	S.7.1. N° of Green Public Procurement	0	0					N/A
O.4	C.1. Decrease of the average of the urban management cost	N/A	C.1.3. Management Cost (MC) (€)	LI	LI	LI	LI	LI	LI	N/A
			C.1.3.1. Collection and transport cost (CTC) (€)	LI	LI	LI	LI	LI	LI	N/A
			C.1.3.2. Final management costs (FMC) (€)	LI	LI	LI	LI	LI	LI	N/A
			C.1.3.3. Other common costs (oCO) (€)	LI	LI	LI	LI	LI	LI	N/A
			C.1.1. Budget applied to awareness and prevention campaigns (€/year)	10000	Sensitization campaigns managed by GELSIA					N/A
			C.1.2. Treatment gate fee (€/ton treated)	LI	LI	LI	LI	LI	LI	N/A

Table 7 Evolution of the High Level KPIs with respect to the baseline in Seveso

Amount of waste collected (ton/year)	RESIDUAL WASTE	SEPARATE COLLECTION CIRCUITS					TOTAL ton/year
	WCC1-WCC4	WCC5-WCC6	WCC7-WCC8	WCC9	WCC10	Estimated biowaste treated by community/home composting	
	Residual Waste	Light packaging	Food waste	Paper and cardboard	Glass		
	Domestic + commercial (+ street dustbins)	Domestic-Commercial	Domestic-Commercial	Domestic-Commercial	Domestic-Commercial	Domestic	
	Door to door	Door to door	Door to door	Door to door	Door to door	Door to door	
Baseline (04/2017)	1684,21	719,92	1576,85	1046,68	903,06	0,00	8912,65
Monitoring (04/2018)	1425,22	801,15	1693,92	1086,93	938,14	193,92	9132,50
T.2. Increase of the average of urban waste sorted (T.2.1. Amount of waste collected (WC) (ton/year) (after PAYT)	- 258,99	81,23	117,07	40,25	35,08	193,92	219,85
%	-15,38	11,28	7,42	3,85	3,88		2,47

Annual generation rate (Kg/inhab/year)	RESIDUAL WASTE	SEPARATE COLLECTION CIRCUITS				TOTAL
	Residual Waste	Light packaging	Food waste	Paper and cardboard	Glass	Kg/inhab/year
Baseline (04/2017)	71,75	30,67	67,17	44,59	38,47	379,68
Monitoring (04/2018)	60,71	34,13	72,16	46,30	39,97	397,31
T.1. Average reduction of municipal waste generation (T.1.3. Annual generation rate (aGR) (Kg/inhab/year)	11,03	-3,46	-4,99	-1,71	-1,49	-17,63
%	18,17	-10,14	-6,91	-3,70	-3,74	-4,44

Impurities (%)	RESIDUAL WASTE	SEPARATE COLLECTION CIRCUITS			
	Residual Waste	Light packaging	Food waste	Paper and cardboard	Glass
Baseline (04/2017)	65,22%	17,93%	1,58%	2,70%	14,00%
Monitoring (04/2018)	63,94%	29,21%	3,06%	2,70%	14,00%
T.2. Increase of the average of urban waste sorted (T.2.2. Level of impurities (improvers) (imp) (%)	-1%	11%	1%	0%	0%

Impurities (kg)	RESIDUAL WASTE	SEPARATE COLLECTION CIRCUITS			
	Residual Waste	Light packaging	Food waste	Paper and cardboard	Glass
Baseline (04/2017):	46,79	5,50	1,06	1,20	5,39
Monitoring (04/2018)	38,82	9,97	2,21	1,25	5,60
T.2. Increase of the average of urban waste sorted (T.2.2. Level of impurities (improvers) (imp) (Kg)	-7,97	4,47	1,15	0,05	0,21

	Increase of legislative changes proposed (n°)
Baseline (04/2017):	0
Monitoring (04/2018)	2
S.4. Increase of legislative changes proposed (S.4.1. Legislative changes proposed)	2

	Increase of Zero Waste Events (n°)
Baseline (04/2017):	9
Monitoring (04/2018)	9
S.5. Increase of Zero Waste Events (S.5.1. N° of Zero Waste Events)	0

5.3 Eco-solution specific indicators

At this stage most eco-solutions have reached a beta stage and have started to be tested, so that some KPIs have started being collected.

Please note that the KPIs of the social actions (R17) are explained in Section 5.

Table 8 summarizes the economical KPIs for the results (product or services) identified per partner at Milestone 3. More details can be found in Deliverable D1.3 (public document) about the estimation of these KPIs and in Deliverable D1.6 about the Exploitation plan of the results.

This economic KPIs have been included to check at a glance if proposed results are profitable or not. The idea is to keep these KPIs updated as the different variables for the results become clearer (costs to incur, price per service, etc...). If any or some of these KPIs are not good enough, partners will set specific measures to obtain the expected results.

Attending to Table 8 the economic KPIs show partners are quite conservative. At the beginning of the commercialisation of the integral solution the expected incomes are moderated but costs are overvalued. A moderated scenario is better when doing financial forecast but much more when different partners come together to commercialise an integral solution as all partners are responsible in the same rate.

The integral solution will be profitable if partners involved make their solutions profitable as well so the control and monitoring of these economic KPIs at individual level are directly related to the integral solution financial viability.

Partners are working to have these KPIs completed and updated.

Table 8 Economical KPIs of the expected products/services of Waste4Think per partner (In grey pending information)

KPI	Title	FDEUSTO	ARS	ENBIO	NTUA	UPATRAS/G REENTECH	SGI	SOFTLINE	MOBA	VWG	BCN	ENG
KPI-C.1	ROI (Return on Investment) at year 2 (%)	-8%	-6%			292%	-35%	0%				46%
KPI-C.1	ROI (Return on Investment) at year 5 (%)	25%	75%			275%	211%	30%				279%

KPI-C.2	Payback year	4	5		5	5		4		1
KPI-C.3	TOTAL CAPEX (€)	25.000,00	15.000,00		134.450,00	0,00		60.400,00		
KPI-C.4	TOTAL OPEX (€)	1.078.395,33	211.299,32		118.303,97	325.493,28		1.390.330,20		1.311.940,55
KPI-C.5	Incomes forecast at year 2 (€)	198.500,00	37.000,00		75.000,00	40.400,00		290.300,00		199.500,00
KPI-C.5	Incomes forecast at year 5 (€)	284.500,00	99.000,00		75.000,00	200.800,00		396.800,00		2.309.461,88
KPI-C.6	Break-even point (AVERAGE) (€)	198.636,17	30.866,88		119.387,51	54.526,29		253.558,89		81.418,67

In the case of the rest of the KPIs of eco-solutions, as the implementation is still under an early stage, the measures made until now are not representative and have not been included in this report. However, for the next period (fulfilment of Milestone 4 Preliminary Tests) these KPIs will be included in Deliverable D1.6 Preliminary Test Report.

6 Lessons learnt

6.1 Cascais

- Collective waste collection can be transferred directly to an also collective PAYT system. This is useful for a gradient transformation between a collective system and a full individualized PAYT method. Citizens are used to a given system and not fully aware of the involved costs (most of them don't even know it is a payed service).

- Citizens are interested in promoting a better environment. However, they do not understand the weight of their own eco footprint, namely the impact of the waste produced (individually). We must commit to a message that gives responsibility to each one of us, but also provide a solution which help to increase recycling and reduce waste production at household levels.
Hence, it is much better and more impactful to ensure people also understand the economic impact. Not all understand the environmental impacts, but the loss of economic benefits is a calculation easy to understand and usually strikes a message.
- When promoting a PAYT System, ensure that you have a close, individualized and direct approach with each citizen. Each one of us is different with different priorities. As such, we can change our message accordingly.
- Provide as much benefits as possible to citizens, not only at the beginning of the project, but also during it. People tend to forget or let go of an innovative approach in the long term as it requires new habits and usually not easier ones. Make sure people are reminded of the project and the importance of their participation at least once a month. Give away more prizes, more eco events, more benefits.
- Equipment wise, make sure you make it easier as possible. A RFID key reader without the need to insert in any slot is easier than the ones which need so. It is cleaner and easier for the citizen. Also consider a QR code for citizens who forgot the key but have their cell phone!
- Control the awards if a gamification method is used. Some people take all awards leaving few for others. This can demotivate people.
- It seems that bin placement and proximity are key for citizens to recycle. It is much more comfortable and now there are no excuses for not separating the waste.
- Free bags for organic waste separation are useful and welcome. It is a free addition as a benefit to citizens. But it can only go so far. Citizens must be informed of the relevance to sort our biowaste constantly.
- Gamification is also a useful method to provide PAYT methods if the city does not want to change regulations or charge more to citizens. It is an interactive way to bring all citizens of younger ages.

6.2 Halandri

A key fact to take into account when trying to interpret the Halandri experience, is that initially the municipality has a low level of adoption of good practices in waste management, albeit a little better than most municipalities in Greece.

- The first volunteers have all the characteristics of early adopters: often they already have implemented their own solutions to waste management issues, they tend to communicate horizontally and show peer-to-peer behaviour, they are visionary and tend to propose solutions, they tend to take risks and accept new solutions proposed to them, they stick to new solutions and participation to a new system is by itself a moral incentive.
- Peer-to-peer activities seem to be very effective at initial stages and good collaboration with early adopters is crucial.
- In a municipality with a low initial level of adoption of good practices, introducing a lot of changes at the same time instead of one solution at a time seems to have good results. In Halandri, Waste4Think is accompanied by the introduction of a separate collection system for paper/cardboard (yellow bin), home composting activities and sensitization campaigns for recycling. This way, a household can opt to adopt one of these changes, and the change in behaviour acts cumulatively. Of course, the process restructuring necessary to implement these changes simultaneously needs to be addressed.
- The small size of the brown bins in Halandri (120 lt) means that they are easily stolen. This actually happened: by the 10th day of the installation of the first 80 120 lt brown bins, 30 were stolen. We solved this problem by acquiring padlocks and using them to secure the bins in fixed spots, i.e. traffic signs, trees etc. Since then, we have had only rare occurrences of thefts. However, we have reached the conclusion that 120 lt bin is very easy to steal, and we should opt for larger 360 lt bins for future tenders.
- Proximity to the bin is key. We found out that people who lived more than 60 meters away from a bin are much less prone to actually volunteer to the program. So we established a “60 meters at maximum” approach to design the distribution of the brown bins for the next phase.
- We find that most people tend to dispose kitchen biowaste 2-3 times per week. During the summer months this number increases, but not significantly.
- RFID tags to track each bin's id must be designed in such a way as to be easily removed and installed by collection personnel, since bins are regularly replaced for washing.
- A lockable bin for collection seems to be necessary, since every bin that for some reason was left open (i.e. malfunctioning lock) was filled with impurities from improper use by non-participants.
- The determination of the administration of the municipality to push for change is crucial, since a) a strong message has to be transmitted to the citizens, and b) significant changes in the internal processes of the waste management services are necessary and idling forces are prevailing.
- Shop owners are much more hesitant to adopt new solutions compared with households and do not feel that adoption of good waste management habits will attract more customers or help their business. In this case, introduction of fines is perhaps something to be more thoroughly examined.

6.3 Seveso

- The implementation of PAYT in Seveso allowed an increase of about 5 percentage points of separate collection, allowing to reach the highest level (80-82% separate collection) in Italy compared to other best performers. However, it's important to highlight the fact that the preliminary testing phase (without PAYT) where RFID bags were delivered to citizens just for monitoring purposes, allowed to raise separate collection of at least other 5 points, from 72% to 77%.
- The deployment of PAYT has been to some extent difficult due to some specific reasons. One was data exchange between providers. The fact of having three different data sources / processing softwares (one for the vending machine delivering rolls of bags, one for the reading and transmission of bags read on the vehicle, and the invoicing software) caused huge delays due to misunderstandings between providers. It was solved in the end but it appears that the Municipality always has to rely on external enterprises in this respect, waiting for their feedback and willingness. Also, some problems of delays when it comes to send the invoice to citizens were experienced for both political and technical reasons.
- PAYT was actually not very well perceived by citizens, in the sense that most of them probably didn't even realize, experiencing a slight variation with respect of the previous flat tax based on coefficients. This is intrinsic to the mechanism of PAYT: when you start with an already high separate collection rate, residual waste is low. So, it's not possible to apply a high unit price, also in order to avoid bad behaviours like littering.
- The huge amount of data collected was actually not used to all its potential. More mechanisms towards Know-As-You-Throw are needed to inform citizens about their individual generation, especially addressing the less sensitive ones.
- The fact of having municipal elections in the mid of the project was a risk factor. Luckily, the implementation of all relevant actions including PAYT was carried out before the election. The change of Mayor, together with the urgency of starting the new contract with the municipal waste collection company, caused a period of disconnection with the activity of the project. Generally speaking, for the successful application of a PAYT scheme is necessary the strong commitment of the decision makers.
- Applying PAYT needs a heavy engagement of municipal employees (environment and tribute offices). They often lack time and competences; so it's almost always necessary to engage an external support (consultancy) that in the case of W4T was part of project but in the other cases has to be paid by the Municipality.
- Furthermore, the local police office should collaborate for territory monitoring (littering, abandonments, sanctions, etc.), but in the Seveso pilot, the collaboration was not so successful.

- The fact of having relevant stakeholders being not directly partners of the project (e.g. the municipal waste collection company GELSIA) caused various misunderstandings and delays, especially when it comes to asking them data, labour or detailed information.
- Social actions were performed with a manifold approach:
- The experience of ecoevents was positive specially to spread towards a huge number of citizens the new concepts introduced with the PAYT scheme in particular the maximization of separate collection and the prevention of waste production.
- The funny-door-to-door activities were in part very positive in particular with the communication events in public spaces (specially to solve punctual doubts and questions on PAYT). Another key activity was the presence of Legambiente operators near the RFID bags dispensers for citizens (located near municipal offices) in order to explain how to gain the bags and to answer to specific questions on PAYT.
- In other cases, the funny door-to-door was not so successful and in particular in schools and in parishes (in fact their waste tax significantly increased). In these cases, the communication activities should be repeated periodically in order to overcome the lack of commitment of stakeholders involved.
- Furthermore, there're some areas of the Municipality, where separate collection is very hard. In particular, poor people living in some degraded courts in the city center are completely out-of-control from the point of view of the waste management. In these areas, soft communication actions, like funny-door-to-door, are not feasible and it's frequently needed the local police intervention.
- Virtuous family's action was meaningful because demonstrated that the separate collection rate in Seveso can still increase until reaching 95%-98%. In fact in these selected families (different by number of components and type of dwellings), with a specific communication action, the separate collection became very high.

6.4 Zamudio

To buy Zamudio's containers has been **waiting for electronic locks IP 67 on the market** (Full protection against contact, dust penetration protection and protected against water penetration by immersing it), because the containers with IP 65 or IP 66 are sensitive to high ambient humidity and cleanliness by jet with water and detergents therefore they are not suitable for Zamudio. In 2012 electronic lock was put with IP 64 and organic containers. When winter came with high ambient humidity there were problems with the locks. Some locks were changed to IP 65, but it wasn't enough either. Today organic containers are open waiting for the new containers. In the sheet it is established that the containers will have to have IP 67 lock.

It is known that with the features that are going to have the containers to be placed in Zamudio is not going to solve the **accessibility issues**. But, in the case that some person had accessibility problems he would be made a door-to-door pick up or he would be given a **solution Ad hoc**. It may be a possible solution to place the containers one meter below the ground level making a hole in the ground so that the door is accessible to a person in a wheelchair.

In the case of Zamudio, most citizens have a **Citizen Card** They use to access different facilities in the village and are already **accustomed to use** the card and as you know that through the card takes a control tend to be more careful with the facilities. Therefore, this existing situation in the future will facilitate the use of cards to open the containers.

- **Organic matter container (biowaste, brown)**

In the case brown container at the beginning of the project was doubted whether to put **Chamber or not** and in the end, it was decided that no.

By putting chamber the container is **Hinders the contribution of improper** Because you are limiting the maximum volume that you will be able to deposit. In addition, **partially avoids the smell coming out** of the organic deposited in the container and the visual access to it.

But at the same time it is **Hindering** that the **Large generators** Take large quantities, especially food trade, which would force us to duplicate organic containers, one without chamber for the big generators and one with chamber for the rest. In addition to this form **the door weighs** More being able to be this an impediment for a certain part of the population, like the old people.

- **Residual fraction container (grey)**

By having chamber, we are doubted by the fact that the **open and/or close the door** of the container **excessive force is necessary** and this can be a problem in the case of older people or people with little strength. To try to solve the problem **the maximum force at 25 Newton is limited in the spread**, pending a few last tests with a dynamometer to accurately establish that force in Newton.

The **chamber It will be 25 liters and can be delimited in the future to 15 or 20 liters** as you move forward with the PAYT. It has developed a chamber Modulated to which two pieces of 5 litres of volume are added or removed each one.

- **Paper-cardboard container (blue)**

It has been **Delimited container mouth** so that the cardboard is folded and so that no bags are thrown. The greatest doubt has been whether **open the door up or down** and at the end it will open downwards. Because if the door opens up closes itself and so would never be open, but would have to hold the door to deposit the waste and if it opens downward could be open, but we

thought people would close it because But It would affect them in the rate and in this way they would not have to hold the door to deposit the waste.

- **Glass container (green)**

When you put the lid with a lock to the mouth of the glass container, we saw that there was a problem with the hook or nail of the lock that is inside the container and to which the part of the lock is fastened on the cover. This piece protrudes, so hitting with the glass you are depositing could break the same or cause it to fall to the ground.

The container is a glass container that is used in companies but modified for Zamudio.

- **Light packaging container (yellow)**

This fraction is not managed by the Commonwealth, so it is not in our hands, but the management company, Garbiker, the next sheet will ask for a change and that the containers can be fitted with a lid with electronic lock.

- **Oil Containers (orange) and reusable (white)**

The containers of the two fractions are metallic and have chamber so we will have no trouble putting the electronic lock. It has been successfully tested. In a first phase is not expected to put the electronic lock because they do not affect the PAYT. If at a later stage to get information and carry out incentive campaigns.

7 Policy Feedback.

7.1 Cascais

Limitation on implementation of individual PAYT scheme

Individual PAYT systems are not allowed in Portugal due to legal consideration which impedes different payment values on waste services per citizen. Currently, the legal framework is recognized in the Law nº 194/2009 published in 20th August 2009. This means that we must ensure the same pricing to all citizens, regardless of their waste sorting levels. Hence, the only variable tariff is according to contract permission. In the case of Cascais, this tariff is a percentage of the water consumption, but is it the same percentage to all citizens.

To surpass this impediment, the Cascais Waste4Think team proposed the best solution, meaning the closest to a full PAYT. We have developed a collective system which citizens will all contribute for the neighbourhood performance. Hence, the recycling levels of the neighborhood define the benefits for participating citizens. There is no differentiated payment, meaning the legality is maintained. What

happens is that citizens who recycle more, and contribute more to the project get more benefits in the form of a gamification app. Each month, the individual contribution is assessed and duly communicated the values by an “environmental balance.”

7.2 Halandri

Limitations on installation of nappies treatment unit in a nursery

A small diversion regarding the installation of the nappies treatment unit has been identified. We have identified a number of issues (mainly political, legal and some minor technical ones) that seem to prevent us from installing the treatment unit in a nursery:

A new law (no 4549/2018, 14/6/2018) changing the procedures for Environmental Permits has been released. The appropriate degrees for its implementation have not yet been issued, and the directorate responsible for issuing these permits has not yet been defined.

Also, a new decree (Presidential Decree 59, 29/7/2018) regulating the land uses has been released, and we are still uncertain of its implications.

These issues have created a transitional “grey zone” regarding the legality of the installation of the unit, for which the appropriate directorates of the municipality cannot yet express a solid opinion.

In such an environment, there is a strong possibility for a political backlash from the opposition in the municipal council, given that it is election year. The administration’s fear is the opposition would target Waste4Think because of its popularity and widespread acclaim.

We propose that we change the original planning and install the nappies treatment unit in the municipality’s gym facilities. The proposed location is about 50 meters away from the dryer/shredder unit, there is no legal issue, and we can demonstrate a number of uses, i.e. feeding the biogas in the gym’s boiler, feeding a separate boiler to heat an isolated gym’s room and other options which we are still examining. The collection and transportation of the nappies is easy and effortless for the municipality.

There are also technical advantages in such a solution. Notably, the gym’s facilities provide a much stronger power supply and ease of operation at any time of the day, plus some other minor technical benefits.

7.3 Zamudio

Limitation on the reuse of food waste generated in public schools

There are two legal/political barriers. First, Educational Department of Basque Government manage any issue related with public schools, even school meal caterings. On the other hand, if any healthy problem

happens through whole donation chain, catering company will be the responsible of it and they are not willing to take any risk.

We know that there are some private schools that they are already collaborating with AUNAR NGO in order to reuse generated food waste. As some Healthy Local Department recognized, AUNAR's receive&deliver protocol does not have any sanitary risk neither for donors or for end users.

Zamudio public school and Txorierrri public high-school shown interest in contributing with their surpluses, but as other public schools, they could not participate. The prohibition does not come from Basque Government Heathy Department. As far as we know, Educational Department do not want to take any risk, even knowing that the donation process is a very well tested action.

If there were any legal possibility like the Good Samaritan Law of the USA, or the most recent law in Italy, many catering companies would make the effort to donate their surpluses. Another possibility would be to advance in parallel in the creation of bilateral agreements, between schools and catering (success case of Auzolan in the Basque territory).

Finally, during next course will be created a platform against the food waste where they take part both private and public entities (including Basque Government, NGOs, companies, etc.); similar to the European Platform against the food waste (hosted by EC).

Limitation on implementation of community composting

By 10th April 2018, Basque Government published a new community composting regulation for public participation and at the moment it does not affect to Zamudio because it is in the public participation phase. It can be said that two batches of compost have already finished their process and we are in the process of doing the analytics to see that compost suitable for the use of Zamudio public gardens has been achieved. The capacity of the installed composting plant was 8 m³ (divided in 8 modules of 1 m³). The composters will be used for the eco-events and in the future for the play gardens that will be built in the next camp.

Revision tables

External Reviewer nº #1

DATE 11/12/2018

Issue	Yes	No	Score (1=low to 5=high) Comments	Comments
Is the format of the document correct?	X		5	
Does the format of the document meet the objectives of the work done?	X		5	It addresses the information required in GA
Does the index of the document Collect precisely the tasks and issues that need to be reported?	X		5	
Is the content of the document clear and well described?	X		5	
Does the content of each section describe the advance done during the task development?	X		5	
Does the content have sufficient Technical description to make clear the research and development performed?	X		5	The vocabulary used is very clear and understable
Are all the figures and tables numerated and described?	X		5	
Are the indexes correct?	X		5	
Is the written English correct?	X		5	Some words have been corrected but in general it is written properly.
Main technical terms are correctly referenced?		X	5	There are no references for technical issues, only for legal basis
Glossary present in the document?	X		5	

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External Reviewer n° #2

DATE 11/12/2018

Issue	Yes	No	Score (1=low to 5=high) Comments	Comments
Is the format of the document correct?	X		4	
Does the format of the document meet the objectives of the work done?	X		5	
Does the index of the document Collect precisely the tasks and issues that need to be reported?	X		5	
Is the content of the document clear and well described?	X		5	
Does the content of each section describe the advance done during the task development?	X		5	
Does the content have sufficient Technical description to make clear the research and development performed?	X		4	
Are all the figures and tables numerated and described?	X		5	
Are the indexes correct?	X		5	
Is the written English correct?	X		5	
Main technical terms are correctly referenced?	X		5	
Glossary present in the document?	X		5	

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External Reviewer n° #1

DATE 12/12/2018

Issue	Yes	No	Score (1=low to 5=high) Comments	Comments
Is the format of the document correct?	X		4	
Does the format of the document meet the objectives of the work done?	X		5	
Does the index of the document Collect precisely the tasks and issues that need to be reported?	X		5	
Is the content of the document clear and well described?	X		5	
Does the content of each section describe the advance done during the task development?	X		5	
Does the content have sufficient Technical description to make clear the research and development performed?	X		4	
Are all the figures and tables numerated and described?	X		5	
Are the indexes correct?	X		5	
Is the written English correct?	X		5	
Main technical terms are correctly referenced?	X		5	
Glossary present in the document?	X		5	

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Annexes of Deliverable D1.5

Annex 1 Planning for the development and integration of the sensor layer and status at Milestone 3

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The dissemination of results herein reflects only the author's view and the European Commission is not responsible for any use that may be made of the information it contains

	2016												2017												2018												2019											
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	Use case analysis						M1	Preparatory Actions						M2	Deployment & Integration						M3	Preliminary Test			M4	Full Test			M5																			
	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12	19	20	21	22	23	24	25	26	27	28	29	30	31	32	33	34	35	36	37	38	39	40	41	42												
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DEVELOPMENT STATUS																																																
S1							B	1						RC	1						RC	1			1	1																						
S2							B	1						RC	B						RC	RC			1	1																						
S3							1	1						1	1						1	1			1	1																						
S4							B	RC						RC	RC						RC	RC			1	1																						
S5							B	1						1	1						1	1			1	1																						
S6							1	1						RC	1						RC	1			1	1																						
S7							B	α						RC	RC						RC	1			1	1																						
S8							B	∅						RC	B						RC	RC			1	1																						
S9							B	1						RC	RC						RC	1			1	1																						
S10							B	RC						RC	RC						RC	RC			1	1																						
S11							B	RC						RC	RC						RC	RC			1	1																						
S12							B	α						RC	α						RC	RC			1	1																						
S13							B	α						RC	α						RC	RC			1	1																						
IMPLEMENTATION STATUS																																																
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S5							D	T						P	P						P	P																										
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S10							€	T						I	T						T	T																										
S11							€	I						I	T						T	T																										

STATUS description

Integration of Sensors

- ∅ The sensor have not been selected yet or the purchase have not started.
- € A tender, or similar procedure, have been sheduled to acquire the sensors.
- D Sensor have been installed but no integration with the rest of the components have started.
- I Sensors are being integrated with the rest of solutions at the pilot site.
- T Sensors have been deployed and have been integrated. Tests are being carried out in real conditions.
- P Sensors have been deployed and work as expected.

Development

- ∅ The device has been designed but it was not started its assembly
- α Not all functionalities are implemented or some of them are in a "Wizard of Oz" type of implementation (the function exists but behaves trivially). Only partial test could be made.
- B All functionalities are implemented but some of them do not behave as expected. Obvious bugs are been found. The system is been tested in lab conditions.
- RC All functionalities are implemented and behaves as expected. Obvious bugs have been ironed out. The system is been tested in real conditions.
- 1 All functionalities are working as expected. The system have been tested in real conditions.

Annex 2. Level of development and implementation of the Operation and Planning tools expected per period and per pilot based on the fulfillment of every functional requirement and status at Milestone 3

2016												2017												2018												2019											
1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12
Use case analysis						M1	Preparatory Actions						M2	Deployment & Integration						M3	Preliminary Test						M4	Full Test						M5													
1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12	19	20	21	22	23	24	25	26	27	28	29	30	31	32	33	34	35	36	37	38	39	40	41	42												
ref stat												ref stat												ref Estimate												ref Estimate											

DEVELOPMENT STATUS																																																									
R1_FR1	To monitor the waste generation													α	α													B	B													RC	1													1	1
R1_FR1.1	Allow to identify the users to the collection system													α	α													B	RC													RC	1													1	1
R1_FR1.1.1	Allow to identify the users by an ID card (NFC)													α	α													B	1													RC	1													1	1
R1_FR1.1.2	Allow to identify the user by an iBag (RFID) (D2D system)													1	1													1	1													1	1													1	1
R1_FR1.1.3	Allow to identify the bin by a RFID tag													α	1													B	RC													RC	RC													1	1
R1_FR1.2	Monitor the delivery of waste (control access)													α	α													B	B													RC	RC													1	1
R1_FR1.2.1	Control the access to the containers with a black list mechanism													α	α													B	B													RC	RC													1	1
R1_FR1.2.2	Control the access to the containers with a white list mechanism													α	α													B	RC													RC	1													1	1
R1_FR1.2.3	Locks must be reprogrammables													α	∅													B	RC													RC	1													1	1
R1_FR1.3	Allow to characterize the waste deposited													α	α													B	B													RC	RC													1	1
R1_FR1.3.1	Identify the type of waste deposited (information of manual characterizations)													RC	α													1	1													1	1													1	1
R1_FR1.3.2	Provide help in the identification of the improper waste when emptying the bin/bag													α	α													B	RC													RC	1													1	1
R1_FR1.3.3	Get the amount of waste deposited													α	α													B	B													RC	RC													1	1
R1_FR1.3.4	Get the time when the waste is generated (deposited or surplus)													α	α													B	B													RC	RC													1	1
R1_FR1.3.5	Get the localization where the waste is deposited													α	1													B	B													RC	RC													1	1
R1_FR1.3.6	Get the number of iBags delivered to users													1	1													1	1													1	1													1	1
R1_FR1.3.7	Monitoring the waste deposited in Eco-events													α	∅													B	B													RC	RC													1	1
R1_FR1.4	Get information about the state of the deposit point and composting plants													α	∅													B	B													RC	RC													1	1
R1_FR1.4.1	Allows the monitorization of the filling level (Bins)													α	∅													B	B													RC	1													1	1
R1_FR1.4.2	Allows the monitorization of the temperature (Composting)													α	∅													B	B													RC	1													1	1
R1_FR1.4.3	Allows the monitorization of the moisture (Composting)													α	∅													B	B													RC	1													1	1
R1_FR1.5	Provide a fallback solution to publish information in the context broker													α	B													B	RC													RC	1													1	1
R1_FR2	Get information of a collection route																									B	B													RC	RC													1	1		
R1_FR2.1	Get the total fuel consumption of a collection route													α	1													B	B													RC	RC													1	1
R1_FR2.2	Estimate the total environmental impact of a collection route													α	B													B	B													RC	RC													1	1
R1_FR2.3	Get the GPS Trace of a collection route													α	1													B	1													RC	1													1	1
R1_FR2.4	Get the FMS information from the CAN BUS													α	1													B	B													RC	RC													1	1
R1_FR2.5	Get the total weight of waste collected													α	1													B	1													RC	1													1	1
R1_FR2.6	Get the places where the bin have been collected													α	1													B	1													RC	1													1	1
R1_FR2.7	Get the time when the bin have been collected													α	1													B	1													RC	1													1	1
R1_FR2.8	Allow to emit a certification of the work done during the shift													α	α													B	B													RC	RC													1	1
R1_FR3	Allow to report issues													α	α													B	B													RC	RC													1	1
R1_FR3.1	Allow to report the overfill of a container													α	1													B	B													RC	RC													1	1
R1_FR3.2	Allow to report vandalizing of a container													α	1													B	B													RC	RC													1	1
R1_FR3.3	Allow to report incorrect use of a container or bag													α	1													B	B													RC	RC													1	1
R1_FR3.3.1	Allows to report the presence of improper waste													α	1													B	B													RC	RC													1	1
R1_FR3.3.2	Allows to detect if a container is not inventoried													α	1													B	B													RC	RC													1	1
R1_FR3.3.3	Allow to report a missing container													α	1													B	B													RC	RC													1	1
R1_FR3.4	Allow to take evidences (photos or videos) of the incidences													α	α													B	α													RC	RC													1	1
R1_FR3.5	Allow to request of specific collections (bulky waste)													α	∅													B	α													RC	RC													1	1
R1_FR4	To display the state of the waste collection system													α	α													B	B													RC	RC													1	1
R1_FR4.1	Allow to show the state of the waste collection system													α	α													B	B													RC	RC													1	1
R1_FR4.1.1	Allow to show the {past, current, planned} state of the system													α	α													B	B													RC	RC													1	1
R1_FR4.2	Detect anomalies in the waste generation patterns													α	∅													B	∅													RC	B													1	1
R1_FR4.3	Allows to personalize the monitoring system													α	α													B	B													RC	RC													1	1
R1_FR4.3.1	Allows to filter the information provided by time, type and geographical distribution													α	∅													B	B													RC	RC													1	1
R1_FR4.3.2	Allows to select and configure the KPIs to show													α	α													B	B													RC	RC													1	1
R1_FR4.3.3	Allows to define alerts													α	∅													B	B													RC	RC													1	1
R1_FR4.4	Allows to create automatic reports in PDF, Excel and CSV													α	∅													B	∅													RC	RC													1	1
R1_FR4.5	The system must be able to crawl the web to get incidences													α	∅													B	∅													RC	RC													1	1
R1_FR4.5.1	Crawl social networks like Twitter and Facebook													α	∅													B	∅													RC	B													1	1
R1_FR4.5.2	Crawl blogs and webpages													α	∅													B	∅													RC	B													1	1
R1_FR5	Provide a system to persist the information													RC	α													RC	RC													1	1													1	1
R1_FR5.1	Provide a communication channel to the persistence solution													RC	α													RC	RC													1	1													1	1
R1_FR5.2	Provide a communication channel to CKAN storage systems													RC	α													RC	RC													1	1													1	1
R1_FR5.3	Data Transmission to the Server (for MOBA components)													∅	B													B	B													RC	1													1	1
R1_FR5.3.1	Secured data transmission for PAYT													∅	α													B	RC													RC	1													1	1
R1_FR5.3.2	Data transmission for real time reporting													∅	α													B	B													RC	1													1	1
R2_FR1	To manage the waste collection service													α	B													B	RC													RC	1													1	1
R2_FR1.1	To create the routes to follow every vehicle of the fleet													α	RC													B	RC													RC	1													1	1
R2_FR1.1.1	Depending of the fill level of the bins													α	1													B	RC													RC	RC													1	1
R2_FR1.1.2	Depending on the incidences declared													α	B													B	RC													RC	RC													1	1
R2_FR1.1.3	Depending on the vehicle and driver aviability													α	∅													B	RC													RC	RC													1	1

STATUS description

Deployment

- I Sensors are being integrated with the rest of solutions at the pilot site.
- T Sensors have been deployed and have been integrated. Tests are being carried out in real conditions.
- P Sensors have been deployed and work as expected.

Development

- ∅ The device has been designed but it was not started its assembly
- α Not all functionalities are implemented or some of them are in a "Wizard of Oz" type of implementation (the function exists but behaves trivially). Only partial test could be made.
- B All functionalities are implemented but some of them do not behave as expected. Obvious bugs are been found. The system is been tested in lab conditions.
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		2016											2017											2018											2019														
		1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12
		Use case analysis					M1	Preparatory Actions						M2	Deployment & Integration						M3	Preliminary Test			M4	Full Test				M5																			
		1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12	19	20	21	22	23	24	25	26	27	28	29	30	31	32	33	34	35	36	37	38	39	40	41	42												
		ref stat												ref stat												ref Estimate												ref Estimate											
R2_FR1.1.4	Depending on the planned traffic condition													α	∅													B	RC				RC	RC					1	1									
R2_FR1.2	Optimize the route of the fleet													α	B													B	RC				RC	1					1	1									
R2_FR1.2.1	Optimize the route minimizing the time													α	∅													B	RC				RC	1					1	1									
R2_FR1.2.2	Optimize the route minimizing the distance													α	∅													B	RC				RC	1					1	1									
R2_FR1.2.3	Optimize the route minimizing the cost													α	∅													B	RC				RC	1					1	1									
R2_FR1.2.4	Optimize the route minimizing the environmental impact													α	∅													B	RC				RC	1					1	1									
R2_FR1.2.5	Optimize the route with any combination of the above													α	α													B	RC				RC	1					1	1									
R2_FR2	Provide feedback to drivers													α	α													B	RC				RC	1					1	1									
R2_FR2.1	Provide turn-by-turn information to the driver													α	α													B	RC				RC	1					1	1									
R2_FR2.2	Provide tips to promote more sustainable driving													α	α													B	B				RC	RC					1	1									
R2_FR3	Calculate the taxes to be charge to the citizens (invoicing module)													∅	1													B	RC				RC	1					1	1									
R2_FR3.1	Be able to calculate taxes following different PAYT schemes													∅	1													B	RC				RC	1					1	1									
R2_FR3.1.1	Be able to calculate taxes following a PAYT scheme including incentives for the use of the different prevention and recycling actions													∅	1													B	RC				RC	1					1	1									
R2_FR3.1.2	Be able to calculate taxes following a PAYT scheme base on the amount of waste generated													∅	1													B	RC				RC	1					1	1									
R3_FR1	To support the long term planning													α														B	B				RC	RC					1	1									
R3_FR1.1	Provide visual tools to create predictive and explicative models													α	∅													B	B				RC	RC					1	1									
R3_FR1.2	Provide visuals tools to help in the creation of baselines and what-if scenarios													α	α													B	B				RC	RC					1	1									
R3_FR1.2.1	Allow to modify in what-if scenarios the projected population and their spatial distribution													α	∅													B	α				RC	RC					1	1									
R3_FR1.2.2	Allow to modify in what-if scenarios the waste type and quantity													α	α													B	α				RC	RC					1	1									
R3_FR1.2.3	Allow to modify in what-if scenarios the introduction of new treatment plants													α	∅													B	α				RC	RC					1	1									
R3_FR1.2.4	Allow to modify in what-if scenarios the introduction of new collection systems													α	α													B	α				RC	RC					1	1									
R3_FR1.2.5	Allow to modify in what-if scenarios the mean for waste collection (electric truck, etc.)													α	α													B	α				RC	RC					1	1									
R3_FR1.2.6	Allow to modify in what-if scenarios the localization of the collection spots													α	α													B	α				RC	RC					1	1									
R3_FR1.2.7	Allow to modify in what-if scenarios the prevention campains													α	∅													B	α				RC	RC					1	1									
R3_FR1.2.8	Allow to introduce and / or modify the economic instruments (tariff, PAYT, etc.)													α	∅													B	α				RC	RC					1	1									
R3_FR1.3	Perform long term simulations of the waste management system													α	α													B	B				RC	RC					1	1									
R3_FR1.3.1	Simulate the combination of collection system plus treatment plans													α	α													B	B				RC	RC					1	1									
R3_FR1.3.2	Simulate the localization and size of the collection points and treatment plans													α	B													B	B				RC	RC					1	1									
R3_FR1.3.3	Design and simulate combinations of prevention campains													α	∅													B	B				RC	B					1	1									
R3_FR1.3.4	Take into consideration multiple criteria (economical, environmental and social impacts)													α	B													B	B				RC	RC					1	1									
R3_FR1.3.5	Simulate different transport means for waste collection													α	B													B	RC				RC	RC					1	1									
R3_FR1.3.6	Simulate the effect of different combination of economic instruments													α	∅													B	α				RC	B					1	1									
R3_FR1.4	Allow the optimization of the waste collection for special events													α	∅													B	B				RC	B					1	1									
R3_FR1.5	Help in the creation of green procurements													α	∅													B	α				RC	B					1	1									
R3_FR1.5.1	To identify criteria for the tendering													α	B													B	α				RC	RC					1	1									
R3_FR1.5.2	To evaluate the applicants of the tender													α	∅													B	∅				RC	B					1	1									
R4_FR1	To foster circular economy opportunities													α	∅													B	B				RC	RC					1	1									
R4_FR1.1	Provide recommendation to foster circular economy													α	α													B	B				RC	RC					1	1									
R4_FR1.1.1	Allow to create baseline and what-if scenarios													α	α													B	α				RC	RC					1	1									
R4_FR1.1.2	Evaluate the impact that several best practices have to foster circular economy													α	∅													B	B				RC	RC					1	1									
R4_FR1.1.3	Search for viable circular economy best practices													α	B													B	B				RC	RC					1	1									

IMPLEMENTATION STATUS

Seveso Pilot	
R1_FR1	To monitor the waste generation
R1_FR1.1	Allow to identify the users to the collection system
R1_FR1.1.2	Allow to identify the user by an iBag (RFID)
R1_FR1.3	Allow to characterize the waste deposited
R1_FR1.3.1	Identify the type of waste deposited (information of manual characterizations)
R1_FR1.3.3	Get the amount of waste deposited
R1_FR1.3.4	Get the time when the waste is generated (deposited or surplus)
R1_FR1.3.5	Get the localization where the waste is deposited
R1_FR1.3.6	Get the number of iBags delivered to users
R1_FR1.3.7	Monitoring the waste deposited in Eco-events

		2016											2017											2018											2019														
		1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12
		Use case analysis					M1	Preparatory Actions											M2	Deployment & Integration											M3	Preliminary Test					M4	Full Test						M5					
		1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12	19	20	21	22	23	24	25	26	27	28	29	30	31	32	33	34	35	36	37	38	39	40	41	42												
														ref	stat													ref	stat						ref	Estimate							ref	Estimate					
R4_FR1.1.1	Allow to create baseline and what-if scenarios																											I	I						T	T							P						
R4_FR1.1.2	Evaluate the impact that several best practices have to foster circular economy																											I	I						T	T							P						
R4_FR1.1.3	Search for viable circular economy best practices																											I	I						T	T							P						
Cascais Pilot																																																	
R1_FR1	To monitor the waste generation																																																
R1_FR1.1	Allow to identify the users to the collection system																																																
R1_FR1.1.1	Allow to identify the users by an ID card (NFC)																											I	T						T	P							P						
R1_FR1.1.3	Allow to identify the bin by a RFID tag (D2D system)													P														I	P						T	P							P						
R1_FR1.2	Monitor the delivery of waste (control access)																																																
R1_FR1.2.1	Control the access to the containers with a black list mechanism																											I	I						T	P							P						
R1_FR1.2.2	Control the access to the containers with a white list mechanism																											I	I						T	P							P						
R1_FR1.2.3	Locks must be reprogrammables																											I	I						T	P							P						
R1_FR1.3	Allow to characterize the waste deposited																																																
R1_FR1.3.1	Identify the type of waste deposited (information of manual characterizations)													I														P	P						P	P							P						
R1_FR1.3.3	Get the amount of waste deposited																											I	n/a						T	T							P	P					
R1_FR1.3.4	Get the time when the waste is generated (deposited or surplus)																											I	T						T	T							P						
R1_FR1.3.5	Get the localization where the waste is deposited													P														I	P						T	P							P						
R1_FR1.4	Get information about the state of the deposit point and composting plants																																																
R1_FR1.4.1	Allows the monitorization of the filling level (Bins)																											I	P						T	P							P						
R1_FR1.5	Provide a fallback solution to publish information in the context broker																											I	I						T							P							
R1_FR2	Get information of a collection route																																																
R1_FR2.1	Get the total fuel consumption of a collection route																											I	T						T	P							P						
R1_FR2.2	Estimate the total environmental impact of a collection route																											I	T						T	P							P						
R1_FR2.3	Get the GPS Trace of a collection route													P														I	T						T	P							P						
R1_FR2.4	Get the FMS information from the CAN BUS																											I	T						T	P							P						
R1_FR2.6	Get the places where the bin have been collected													P														I	T						T	P							P						
R1_FR2.7	Get the time when the bin have been collected													P														I	T						T	P							P						
R1_FR2.8	Allow to emit a certification of the work done during the shift																											I	T						T	P							P						
R1_FR3	Allow to report issues																																																
R1_FR3.1	Allow to report the overfill of a container																											I	I						T	P							P						
R1_FR3.2	Allow to report vandalizing of a container																											I	I						T	P							P						
R1_FR3.3	Allow to report incorrect use of a container or bag																											I	I						T	P							P						
R1_FR3.3.1	Allows to report the presence of improper waste																											I	P						T	P							P						
R1_FR3.3.2	Allows to detect if a container is not inventoried																											I	P						T	P							P						
R1_FR3.3.3	Allow to report a missing container																											I	P						T	P							P						
R1_FR3.4	Allow to take evidences (photos or videos) of the incidences																											I	I						T	P							P						
R1_FR4	To display the state of the waste collection system																																																
R1_FR4.1	Allow to show the state of the waste collection system																											I	I						T	T							P						
R1_FR4.1.1	Allow to show the {past, current, planned} state of the system																											I	I						T	T							P						
R1_FR4.2	Detect anomalies in the waste generation patterns																											I	Ø						T	T							P						
R1_FR4.3	Allows to personalize the monitoring system																											I	I						T	P							P						
R1_FR4.3.1	Allows to filter the information provided by time, type and geographical distribution																											I	I						T	P							P						
R1_FR4.3.2	Allows to select and configure the KPIs to show																											I	I						T	P							P						
R1_FR4.3.3	Allows to define alerts																											I	I						T	P							P						
R1_FR4.4	Allows to create automatic reports in PDF, Excel and CSV																											I	I						T	P							P						
R1_FR4.5	The system must be able to crawl the web to get incidences																											I	Ø						T	T							P						
R1_FR4.5.1	Crawl social networks like Twitter and Facebook																											I	Ø						T	P							P						
R1_FR4.5.2	Crawl blogs and webpages																											I	Ø						T	P							P						
R1_FR5	Provide a system to persist the information																																																
R1_FR5.1	Provide a communication channel to the persistence solution																											I	I						T	T							P						
R1_FR5.2	Provide a communication channel to CKAN storage systems																											I	I						T	T							P						
R1_FR5.3	Data Transmission to the Server (for MOBA components)																											I	I						T	T							P						
R1_FR5.3.1	Secured data transmission for PAYT																											I	I						T	P							P						
R1_FR5.3.2	Data transmission for real time reporting																											I	I						T	P							P						
R2_FR1	To manage the waste collection service																																																
R2_FR1.1	To create the routes to follow every vehicle of the fleet													P														I						T	T							P							
R2_FR1.1.1	Depending of the fill level of the bins													P														I	P						T	T							P						
R2_FR1.1.2	Depending on the incidences declared																											I	P						T	T							P						
R2_FR1.1.3	Depending on the vehicle and driver aviability																											I	Ø						T	T							P						
R2_FR1.1.4	Depending on the planned traffic condition																											I	Ø						T	T							P						
R2_FR1.2	Optimize the route of the fleet																											I						T	T							P							
R2_FR1.2.1	Optimize the route minimizing the time																											I	P						T	T							P						
R2_FR1.2.2	Optimize the route minimizing the distance																											I	P						T	T							P						
R2_FR1.2.3	Optimize the route minimizing the cost																											I	Ø						T	T							P						
R2_FR1.2.4	Optimize the route minimizing the environmental impact																											I	Ø						T	T							P						
R2_FR1.2.5	Optimize the route with any combination of the above																											I	Ø						T	T							P						
R2_FR2	Provide feedback to drivers																																																

		2016												2017												2018												2019													
		1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12		
		Use case analysis						M1	Preparatory Actions						M2	Deployment & Integration						M3	Preliminary Test						M4	Full Test						M5															
		1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12	19	20	21	22	23	24	25	26	27	28	29	30	31	32	33	34	35	36	37	38	39	40	41	42														
		ref stat												ref stat												ref Estimate												ref Estimate													
R1_FR2.2	Estimate the total environmental impact of a collection route																																																		
R1_FR2.3	Get the GPS Trace of a collection route																																																		
R1_FR2.5	Get the total weight of waste collected																																																		
R1_FR2.6	Get the places where the bin have been collected																																																		
R1_FR2.7	Get the time when the bin have been collected																																																		
R1_FR3	Allow to report issues																																																		
R1_FR3.1	Allow to report the overfill of a container																																																		
R1_FR3.2	Allow to report vandalizing of a container																																																		
R1_FR3.3	Allow to report incorrect use of a container or bag																																																		
R1_FR3.3.1	Allows to report the presence of improper waste																																																		
R1_FR3.3.2	Allows to detect if a cointainer is not inventoried																																																		
R1_FR3.3.3	Allow to report a missing container																																																		
R1_FR3.4	Allow to take evidences (photos or videos) of the incidences																																																		
R1_FR3.5	Allow to request of specific collections (bulky waste)																																																		
R1_FR4	To display the state of the waste collection system																																																		
R1_FR4.1	Allow to show the state of the waste collection system																																																		
R1_FR4.1.1	Allow to show the {past, current, planned} state of the system																																																		
R1_FR4.2	Detect anomalies in the waste generation patterns																																																		
R1_FR4.3	Allows to personalize the monitoring system																																																		
R1_FR4.3.1	Allows to filter the information provided by time, type and geographical distribution																																																		
R1_FR4.3.2	Allows to select and configure the KPIs to show																																																		
R1_FR4.3.3	Allows to define alerts																																																		
R1_FR4.4	Allows to create automatic reports in PDF, Excel and CSV																																																		
R1_FR4.5	The system must be able to crawl the web to get incidences																																																		
R1_FR4.5.1	Crawl social networks like Twitter and Facebook																																																		
R1_FR4.5.2	Crawl blogs and webpages																																																		
R1_FR5	Provide a system to persist the information																																																		
R1_FR5.1	Provide a communication channel to the persistence solution																																																		
R1_FR5.2	Provide a communication channel to CKAN storage systems																																																		
R1_FR5.3	Data Transmission to the Server																																																		
R1_FR5.3.1	Secured data transmission for PAYT																																																		
R1_FR5.3.2	Data transmission for real time reporting																																																		
R2_FR3	Calculate the taxes to be charge to the citizens (invoicing module)																																																		
R2_FR3.1	Be able to calculate taxes following different PAYT schemes																																																		
R2_FR3.1.1	Be able to calculate taxes following a PAYT scheme including incentives for the use of the different prevention and recycling actions																																																		
R2_FR3.1.2	Be able to calculate taxes following a PAYT scheme base on the amount of waste generated																																																		
R3_FR1	To support the long term planning																																																		
R3_FR1.1	Provide visual tools to create predictive and explicative models																																																		
R3_FR1.2	Provide visuals tools to help in the creation of baselines and what-if scenarios																																																		
R3_FR1.2.1	Allow to modify in what-if scenarios the projected population and their spatial distribution																																																		
R3_FR1.2.2	Allow to modify in what-if scenarios the waste type and quantity																																																		
R3_FR1.2.3	Allow to modify in what-if scenarios the introduction of new treatment plants																																																		
R3_FR1.2.4	Allow to modify in what-if scenarios the introduction of new collection systems																																																		
R3_FR1.2.5	Allow to modify in what-if scenarios the mean for waste collection (electric truck, etc.)																																																		
R3_FR1.2.6	Allow to modify in what-if scenarios the localization of the collection spots																																																		
R3_FR1.2.7	Allow to modify in what-if scenarios the prevention campains																																																		
R3_FR1.2.8	Allow to introduce and / or modify the economic instruments (tariff, PAYT, etc.)																																																		
R3_FR1.3	Perform long term simulations of the waste management system																																																		
R3_FR1.3.1	Simulate the combination																																																		

		2016												2017												2018												2019												
		1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12	
		Use case analysis					M1	Preparatory Actions											M2	Deployment & Integration											M3	Preliminary Test					M4	Full Test							M5					
		1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12	19	20	21	22	23	24	25	26	27	28	29	30	31	32	33	34	35	36	37	38	39	40	41	42													
		ref stat												ref stat												ref Estimate												ref Estimate												
R4_FR1	To foster circular economy opportunities																																																	
R4_FR1.1	Provide recommendation to foster circular economy																									I	I													T	T								P	
R4_FR1.1.1	Allow to create baseline and what-if scenarios																									I	I													T	T								P	
R4_FR1.1.2	Evaluate the impact that several best practices have to foster circular economy																									I	I													T	T								P	
R4_FR1.1.3	Search for viable circular economy best practices																									I	I													T	T								P	
Halandri Pilot																																																		
R1_FR1	To monitor the waste generation																																																	
R1_FR1.1	Allow to identify the users to the collection system																																																	
R1_FR1.1.3	Allow to identify the bin by a RFID tag																									I	P													T	P								P	P
R1_FR1.3	Allow to characterize the waste deposited																																																	
R1_FR1.3.1	Identify the type of waste deposited (information of manual characterizations)																									I	I													P	P						P	P		
R1_FR1.5	Provide a fallback solution to publish information in the context broker																									I	I													T	T								P	P
R1_FR2	Get information of a collection route																																																	
R1_FR2.2	Estimate the total environmental impact of a collection route																									I	I													T	T								P	P
R1_FR2.3	Get the GPS Trace of a collection route																									I	I													T	T								P	P
R1_FR2.5	Get the total weight of waste collected																									I	I													T	T								P	P
R1_FR2.6	Get the places where the bin have been collected																									I	I													T	T								P	P
R1_FR2.7	Get the time when the bin have been collected																									I	I													T	T								P	P
R1_FR3	Allow to report issues																																																	
R1_FR3.1	Allow to report the overfill of a container																									I	∅													T	T								P	P
R1_FR3.2	Allow to report vandalizing of a container																									I	∅													T	T								P	P
R1_FR3.3	Allow to report incorrect use of a container or bag																									I	∅													T	T								P	P
R1_FR3.3.1	Allows to report the presence of improper waste																									I	T													T	T								P	P
R1_FR3.3.2	Allows to detect if a cointainer is not inventoried																									I	T													T	T								P	P
R1_FR3.3.3	Allow to report a missing container																									I	T													T	T								P	P
R1_FR3.4	Allow to take evidences (photos or videos) of the incidences																									I	∅													T	T								P	P
R1_FR4	To display the state of the waste collection system																																																	
R1_FR4.1	Allow to show the state of the waste collection system																									I	I													T	T								P	P
R1_FR4.1.1	Allow to show the {past, current, planned} state of the system																									I	I													T	T								P	P
R1_FR4.2	Detect anomalies in the waste generation patterns																									I	∅													T	I								P	P
R1_FR4.3	Allows to personalize the monitoring system																									I	I													T	T								P	P
R1_FR4.3.1	Allows to filter the information provided by time, type and geographical distribution																									I	∅													T	T								P	P
R1_FR4.3.2	Allows to select and configure the KPIs to show																									I	I													T	T								P	P
R1_FR4.3.3	Allows to define alerts																									I	I													T	T								P	P
R1_FR4.4	Allows to create automatic reports in PDF, Excel and CSV																									I	∅													T	T								P	P
R1_FR4.5	The system must be able to crawl the web to get incidences																									I	∅													T	I								P	P
R1_FR4.5.1	Crawl social networks like Twitter and Facebook																									I	∅													T	I								P	P
R1_FR4.5.2	Crawl blogs and webpages																									I	∅													T	I								P	P
R1_FR5	Provide a system to persist the information																																																	
R1_FR5.1	Provide a communication channel to the persistence solution																									I	T													T	P								P	
R1_FR5.2	Provide a communication channel to CKAN storage systems																									I	T													T	P								P	
R3_FR1	To support the long term planning																																																	
R3_FR1.1	Provide visual tools to create predictive and explicative models																									I	I													T	T								P	
R3_FR1.2	Provide visuals tools to help in the creation of baselines and what-if scenarios																									I	I													T	T								P	
R3_FR1.2.1	Allow to modify in what-if scenarios the projected population and their spatial distribution																									I	I													T	T								P	
R3_FR1.2.2	Allow to modify in what-if scenarios the waste type and quantity																									I	I													T	T								P	
R3_FR1.2.3	Allow to modify in what-if scenarios the introduction of new treatment plants																									I	I													T	T								P	
R3_FR1.2.4	Allow to modify in what-if scenarios the introduction of new collection systems																									I	I													T	T								P	
R3_FR1.2.5	Allow to modify in what-if scenarios the mean for waste collection (electric truck, etc.)																									I	I													T	T								P	
R3_FR1.2.6	Allow to modify in what-if scenarios the localization of the collection spots																									I	I													T	T								P	
R3_FR1.2.7	Allow to modify in what-if scenarios the prevention campains																									I	I													T	T								P	
R3_FR1.2.8	Allow to introduce and / or modify the economic instruments (tariff, PAYT, etc.)																									I	I													T	T								P	
R3_FR1.3	Perform long term simulations of the waste management system																									I	I													T	T								P	
R3_FR1.3.1	Simulate the combination of collection system plus treatment plans																									I	I													T	T								P	
R3_FR1.3.2	Simulate the localization and size of the collection points and treatment plans																									I	I													T	T								P	
R3_FR1.3.3	Design and simulate combinations of prevention campains																									I	I													T	T								P	
R3_FR1.3.4	Take into consideration multiple criteria (economical, environmental and social impacts)																									I	I													T	T								P	
R3_FR1.3.5	Simulate different transport means for waste collection																									I	I													T	T								P	
R3_FR1.3.6	Simulate the effect of different combination of economic instruments																									I	I													T	T								P	

		2016					2017					2018					2019																					
		1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	#	
		Use case analysis					Preparatory Actions					Deployment & Integration					Preliminary Test					Full Test																
		1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12	19	20	21	22	23	24	25	26	27	28	29	30	31	32	33	34	35	36	37	38	39	40	41	42	
																				ref	stat	ref	Estimate	ref	Estimate	ref	Estimate											
R3_FR1.4	Allow the optimization of the waste collection for special events																			I	I			T	T			P										
R3_FR1.5	Help in the creation of green procurements																			I	I			T	T			P										
R3_FR1.5.1	To identify criteria for the tendering																			I	I			T	T			P										
R3_FR1.5.2	To evaluate the applicants of the tender																			I	I			T	T			P										
R4_FR1	To foster circular economy opportunities																																					
R4_FR1.1	Provide recommendation to foster circular economy																			I	I			T	T			P										
R4_FR1.1.1	Allow to create baseline and what-if scenarios																			I	I			T	T			P										
R4_FR1.1.2	Evaluate the impact that several best practices have to foster circular economy																			I	I			T	T			P										
R4_FR1.1.3	Search for viable circular economy best practices																			I	I			T	T			P										

Annex 3. Level of development and implementation of the Apps expected per period and per pilot based on the fulfillment of every functional requirement and status at Milestone 3

2016												2017												2018												2019											
1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12
Use case analysis						M1	Preparatory Actions						M2	Deployment & Integration						M3	Preliminary Test						M4	Full Test						M5													
1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12	19	20	21	22	23	24	25	26	27	28	29	30	31	32	33	34	35	36	37	38	39	40	41	42												
ref stat												ref stat												ref Estimate												ref Estimate											

DEVELOPMENT STATUS		2016												2017												2018												2019																							
R5-6-7_FR1	Common functional requirements of the apps													α α												β β												RC RC												1 1											
R5-6-7_FR1.1	There are four profiles of users: generator, receptor, public administration, root													α α												β β												RC RC												1 1											
R5-6-7_FR1.1.1	The system should be able to use the municipal authentication system													α α												β α												RC RC												1 1											
R5-6-7_FR1.1.2	The system should be able to use OpenID authentication system													α α												β β												RC RC												1 1											
R5-6-7_FR1.1.3	The system should be able to use the authorization system of Android and iOS													α α												β N/A												RC N/A												1 N/A											
R5-6-7_FR1.2	Provide aggregated information to R1_FR4.1													α α												β α												RC RC												1 1											
R5-6-7_FR1.2.1	Provide aggregated information about the prevention campaigns to the monitoring system (R1_FR4.1)													α α												β α												RC RC												1 1											
R5-6-7_FR1.2.2	Provide aggregated information about the use of the app to the monitoring system (R1_FR4.1)													α α												β α												RC RC												1 1											
R5_FR1	Coordinate the collection of food for social kitchens to reduce the edible food waste													α α												β α												RC RC												1 1											
R5_FR1.2	To characterize the edible food waste (for domestic generators)													α α												β α												RC RC												1 1											
R5_FR1.2.1	Identify the generator													α α												β α												RC RC												1 1											
R5_FR1.2.2	Identify the place where the surplus is generated													α α												β α												RC RC												1 1											
R5_FR1.2.3	Record the time of publication of the surplus alert													α α												β α												RC RC												1 1											
R5_FR1.2.4	Assess the quality of the food waste													α α												β α												RC RC												1 1											
R5_FR1.2.4.1	Identify the type of food (cereals, roots and tubers, oil crops and pulses, fruits and vegetables, meat, fish or dairy)													α α												β α												RC RC												1 1											
R5_FR1.2.4.2	Identify if it was cooked/uncooked													α α												β α												RC RC												1 1											
R5_FR1.2.4.3	Identify the type of preservation that the food has had. The process comprising the most important steps from purchasing to handling leftovers (cold chain, food maintenance or cooking time, if applicable).													α α												β α												RC RC												1 1											
R5_FR1.2.4.4	Identify the reason for its discarding (overproduction, spoilage, trim waste, sell-by date expired, best before date expired, aesthetic reasons, other)													α α												β α												RC RC												1 1											
R5_FR1.2.4.5	Identify other relevant information (organic product)													α α												β α												RC RC												1 1											
R5_FR1.3	Provide suggestion of all the actions that can be done with the food waste													α α												β α												RC RC												1 1											
R5_FR1.3.1	Send the surplus alert to potential receptors													α α												β α												RC RC												1 1											
R5_FR1.3.2	Provide information on the nearest collection point (composting or valorization)													α α												β α												RC RC												1 1											
R5_FR1.3.3	Suggest recipes to reuse the food waste													α α												β α												RC RC												1 1											
R5_FR1.4	To record the traceability of all the transactions													α α												β α												RC RC												1 1											
R5_FR1.5	Analyze the food waste production to give personalized tips for improving the purchase and consumption of food													α α												β α												RC RC												1 1											
R6_FR1	To foster local trade, recycling and mutual learning													α α												β β												RC RC												1 1											
R6_FR1.1	Provide information about the way to get vouchers													α α												β N/A												RC N/A												1 N/A											
R6_FR1.2	Provide information about where to redeem the vouchers													α α												β N/A												RC N/A												1 N/A											
R6_FR1.3	Provide information about the environmental impact of product and services													α α												β α												RC β												1 1											
R6_FR1.4	Get and send information about the business that have implemented good practices													α α												β α												RC RC												1 1											
R6_FR1.5	Provide information about local cooperative actions to prevent the generation of waste													α α												β β												RC RC												1 1											
R6_FR1.5.1	Get the localization of the community composting sites													α α												β β												RC RC												1 1											
R6_FR1.5.2	Get the localization of the collection of reusable nappies													α α												β β												RC RC												1 1											
R6_FR1.5.3	Allow to report new collaborative prevention actions and good practices that are being carried on													α α												β β												RC RC												1 1											
R6_FR1.5.4	Provide aggregated information about the participation in cooperative actions to R1_FR4.1													α α												β β												RC RC												1 1											
R6_FR1.5.5	Provide integration with others providers of recycling products like Wallapop, Chicify, Vibbo, Milanuncios, etc.													α α												β N/A												RC N/A												1 N/A											
R7_FR1	To foster transparency and citizen participation													α α												β β												RC RC												1 1											
R7_FR1.1	Show information about the waste management system													α α												β β												RC RC												1 1											
R7_FR1.1.1	Show the public information about the state of the waste management system (R1_FR4.1)													α α												β β												RC RC												1 1											
R7_FR1.1.2	Localization of the nearest collection point													α α												β β												RC RC												1 1											
R7_FR1.1.3	Localization of the clean points													α α												β β												RC RC												1 1											
R7_FR1.2	Allow to report incidences from mobile devices (R1_FR3)													α α												β α												RC RC												1 1											
R7_FR1.3	Provide information to reduce the footprint													α α												β α												RC RC												1 1											
R7_FR1.3.1	Provide information to reduce the amount of waste generated													α α												β α												RC RC												1 1											
R7_FR1.3.2	Provide information about the correct way of sorting waste													α α												β α												RC RC												1 1											
R7_FR1.4	Provide information about the PAYT system implemented													α α												β α												RC RC												1 1											
R7_FR1.5	Provide access to the invoices													α α												β α												RC RC												1 1											
R7_FR1.5.1	Review the vouchers received and redeemed so far													α α												β N/A												RC N/A												1 N/A											
R7_FR1.5.2	Provide a gamification experiences to improve the awareness of the citizens													α α												β α												RC RC												1 1											

STATUS description	
Deployment	
I	Sensors are being integrated with the rest of solutions at the pilot site.
T	Sensors have been deployed and have been integrated. Tests are being carried out in real conditions.
P	Sensors have been deployed and work as expected.
Development	
∅	The device has been designed but it was not started its assembly
α	Not all functionalities are implemented or some of them are in a "Wizard of Oz" type of implementation (the function exists but behaves trivially). Only partial test could be made.
β	All functionalities are implemented but some of them do not behave as expected. Obvious bugs are been found. The system is been tested in lab conditions.
RC	All functionalities are implemented and behaves as expected. Obvious bugs have been ironed out. The system is been tested in real conditions.
1	All functionalities are working as expected. The system have been tested in real conditions.

IMPLEMENTATION STATUS		2016												2017												2018												2019																							
Seveso Pilot																																																													
R5-6-7_FR1	Common functional requirements of the apps																																					I I												P P											
R5-6-7_FR1.1	There are four profiles of users: generator, receptor, public administration, root																																					I I												P P											
R5-6-7_FR1.1.1	The system should be able to use the municipal authentication system																																					I I												P P											
R5-6-7_FR1.1.2	The system should be able to use OpenID authentication system																																					I I												P P											

Requirement ID	Description	2018 Q3	2018 Q4	2019 Q1	2019 Q2
R7_FR1.1.1	Show the public information about the state of the waste management system (R1_FR4.1)	I	I	P	P
R7_FR1.1.2	Localization of the nearest collection point	I	I	P	P
R7_FR1.1.3	Localization of the clean points	I	I	P	P
R7_FR1.2	Allow to report incidences from mobile devices (R1_FR3)	I	I	P	P
R7_FR1.3	Provide information to reduce the footprint	I	I	P	P
R7_FR1.3.1	Provide information to reduce the amount of waste generated	I	I	P	P
R7_FR1.3.2	Provide information about the correct way of sorting waste	I	I	P	P
R7_FR1.5	Provide access to the invoices	I	I	P	P
R7_FR1.5.2	Provide a gamification experiences to improve the awareness of the citizens	I	I	P	P

Annex 4 Level of development and implementation of the Social Actions expected per period and per pilot based on the fulfillment of every functional requirement and status at Milestone 3

2016												2017												2018												2019																							
1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12												
Use case analysis												Preparatory Actions												Deployment & Integration												Preliminary Test												Full Test											
M1												M2												M3												M4												M5											
1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12
ref												stat												ref												Estimate												ref											

DEVELOPMENT STATUS		2016												2017												2018												2019												
R17_FR1	To provide information and knowledge to the target groups on the social action in order to change habits and behaviours													a	B											B	RC											RC	RC											1
R17_FR1.1	Establishment of protocols to assure that the participation is confirmed													a	B											B	RC											RC	RC											1
R17_FR1.2	Establishment of protocols to monitor the impact of the innovative awareness action													RC	1											1	B											1	RC											1
R17_FR1.2.1	Establishment of specific protocols to collect the information needed to calculate the corresponding KPIs or other own indicators													RC	1											1	RC											1	RC											1
R17_FR1.2.2	Establishment of other monitoring actions to detect the impact of the action and the acquisition of knowledge or habits change (surveys)													RC	1											1	RC											1	RC											1
R17_FR1.3	Establishment of subactivities based on innovative awareness methods including the IT solutions													a	B											B	B											RC	RC											1
R17_FR1.4	To identify best practices													RC	1											1	1											1	1											1
R17_FR2	To monitor participation in the different actions													a	B											B	RC											RC	RC											1
R17_FR2.1	To monitor citizens participating in social campaigns													a	B											B	RC											RC	RC											1
R17_FR3	To prevent waste generation and to promote recycling among different sectors of the population													a	B											B	RC											RC	RC											1
R17_FR3.1	To prevent waste generation and to promote recycling among different sectors of the population													a	B											B	RC											RC	RC											1

DEPLOYMENT

- I Sensors are being integrated with the rest of solutions at the pilot site.
- T Sensors have been deployed and have been integrated. Tests are being carried out in real conditions.
- P Sensors have been deployed and work as expected.

Development

- 0 The device has been designed but it was not started its assembly
- a Not all functionalities are implemented or some of them are in a "Wizard of Oz" type of implementation (the function exists but behaves trivially). Only partial test could be made.
- B All functionalities are implemented but some of them do not behave as expected. Obvious bugs are been found. The system is been tested in lab conditions.
- RC All functionalities are implemented and behaves as expected. Obvious bugs have been ironed out. The system is been tested in real conditions.
- 1 All functionalities are working as expected. The system have been tested in real conditions.

IMPLEMENTATION STATUS		2016												2017												2018												2019												
Seveso Pilot																																																		
R17_FR1	To provide information and knowledge to the target groups on the social action in order to change habits and behaviours													T	T											P	P											P	P											
R17_FR1.1	Establishment of protocols to assure that the participation is confirmed													T	T											P	P											P	P											P
R17_FR1.2	Establishment of protocols to monitor the impact of the innovative awareness action													T	T											P	P											P	P											P
R17_FR1.2.1	Establishment of specific protocols to collect the information needed to calculate the corresponding KPIs or other own indicators													T	T											P	P											P	P											P
R17_FR1.2.2	Establishment of other monitoring actions to detect the impact of the action and the acquisition of knowledge or habits change (surveys)													T	T											P	P											P	P											P
R17_FR1.3	Establishment of subactivities based on innovative awareness methods including the IT solutions													P	T											P	T											P	T											P
R17_FR1.4	To identify best practices													P	P											P	P											P	P											P
R17_FR2	To monitor participation in the different actions													T	T											P	P											P	P											P
R17_FR2.1	To monitor citizens participating in social campaigns													T	T											P	P											P	P											P
R17_FR3	To prevent waste generation and to promote recycling among different sectors of the population													T	T											P	P											P	P											P
R17_FR3.1	To prevent waste generation and to promote recycling among different sectors of the population													T	T											P	P											P	P											P
Cascals Pilot																																																		
R17_FR1	To provide information and knowledge to the target groups on the social action in order to change habits and behaviours													I	I											T	P											P	P											P
R17_FR1.1	Establishment of protocols to assure that the participation is confirmed													I	I											T	P											P	P											P
R17_FR1.2	Establishment of protocols to monitor the impact of the innovative awareness action													I	I											T	P											P	P											P
R17_FR1.2.1	Establishment of specific protocols to collect the information needed to calculate the corresponding KPIs or other own indicators													I	I											T	P											P	P											P
R17_FR1.2.2	Establishment of other monitoring actions to detect the impact of the action and the acquisition of knowledge or habits change (surveys)													I	I											T	P											P	P											P
R17_FR1.3	Establishment of subactivities based on innovative awareness methods including the IT solutions													I	I											T	P											P	P											P
R17_FR1.4	To identify best practices													P	P											P	P											P	P											P
R17_FR2	To monitor participation in the different actions													I	I											T	P											P	P											P
R17_FR2.1	To monitor citizens participating in social campaigns													I	I											T	P											P	P											P
R17_FR3	To prevent waste generation and to promote recycling among different sectors of the population													I	I											T	T											P	P											P
R17_FR3.1	To prevent waste generation and to promote recycling among different sectors of the population													I	I											T	T											P	P											P
Zamudio Pilot																																																		
R17_FR1	To provide information and knowledge to the target groups on the social action in order to change habits and behaviours													I	I											T	P											P	P											P
R17_FR1.1	Establishment of protocols to assure that the participation is confirmed													I	I											T	P											P	P											P
R17_FR1.2	Establishment of protocols to monitor the impact of the innovative awareness action													I	I											T	P											P	P											P
R17_FR1.2.1	Establishment of specific protocols to collect the information needed to calculate the corresponding KPIs or other own indicators													I	I											T	P											P	P											P
R17_FR1.2.2	Establishment of other monitoring actions to detect the impact of the action and the acquisition of knowledge or habits change (surveys)													I	I											T	P											P	P											P
R17_FR1.3	Establishment of subactivities based on innovative awareness methods including the IT solutions													I	I											T	P											P	P											P
R17_FR1.4	To identify best practices													P	P											P	P											P	P											P
R17_FR2	To monitor participation in the different actions													I	I											T	P											P	P											P
R17_FR2.1	To monitor citizens participating in social campaigns													I	I											T	P											P	P											P
R17_FR3	To prevent waste generation and to promote recycling among different sectors of the population													I	I											T	T											P	P											P
R17_FR3.1	To prevent waste generation and to promote recycling among different sectors of the population													I	I											T	T											P	P											P
Halandri Pilot																																																		
R17_FR1	To provide information and knowledge to the target groups on the social action in order to change habits and behaviours													I	I											T	P											P	P											P
R17_FR1.1	Establishment of protocols to assure that the participation is confirmed													I	I											T	T											P	P											P
R17_FR1.2	Establishment of protocols to monitor the impact of the innovative awareness action													I	I											T	T											P	P											P
R17_FR1.2.1	Establishment of specific protocols to collect the information needed to calculate the corresponding KPIs or other own indicators													I	I											T	T											P	P											P
R17_FR1.2.2	Establishment of other monitoring actions to detect the impact of the action and the acquisition of knowledge or habits change (surveys)													I	I											T	P											P	P											P
R17_FR1.3	Establishment of subactivities based on innovative awareness methods including the IT solutions													I	I											T	I											P	P											P
R17_FR1.4	To identify best practices													P	P											P	P											P	P											P
R17_FR2	To monitor participation in the different actions													I	I											T	P											P	P											P
R17_FR2.1	To monitor citizens participating in social campaigns													I	I											T	P											P	P											P
R17_FR3	To prevent waste generation and to promote recycling among different sectors of the population													I	I											T	T											P	P											P
R17_FR3.1	To prevent waste generation and to promote recycling among different sectors of the population													I	I											T	T											P	P											P

Annex 4 Level of development and implementation of the Educational Materials expected per period and per pilot based on the fulfillment of every functional requirement and status at Milestone 3

2016												2017												2018												2019											
1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12
Use case analysis						M1	Preparatory Actions						M2	Deployment & Integration						M3	Preliminary Test						M4	Full Test						M5													
1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12	13	14	15	16	17	18	19	20	21	22	23	24	25	26	27	28	29	30	31	32	33	34	35	36	37	38	39	40	41	42						
ref												stat												ref												stat											

DEVELOPMENT STATUS	
R-ICT-SOCIAL_FR1	To teach on waste management and prevention actions
R-ICT-SOCIAL_FR1.1	To teach on waste management and prevention actions
R-ICT-SOCIAL_FR2	Track players and results
R-ICT-SOCIAL_FR2.1	Provide a complete log of the use of the tool
R-ICT-SOCIAL_FR2.1.1	Track authorship of every solution
R-ICT-SOCIAL_FR2.1.2	Register the selected KPIs for the evaluation of the solutions achieved
R-ICT-SOCIAL_FR2.1.3	Track the different created solutions to be later assessed or implemented
R-ICT-SOCIAL_FR2.2	Register the needed info to calculate the related KPIs
R-ICT-SOCIAL_FR2.3	Provide final information about the impact of the mistakes of separation at source
R-ICT-SOCIAL_FR2.3.1	product
R-ICT-SOCIAL_FR2.3.2	Provide information about the impact and results of the solutions
R-ICT-SOCIAL_FR2.4	Detect where the users have had more difficulties
R-ICT-SOCIAL_FR2.4.1	Coordinated with the performance of learning analytics
R-ICT-SOCIAL_FR2.4.2	Detect the repeated mistakes and doubts of the users about the correct separation
R8_FR1	To teach students in waste management and improving the center management system
R8_FR1.1	To teach students in waste management and improving the center management system
R8_FR1.2	Monitor the effect/impact on the students and the learned concepts/abilities, instruction for teachers evaluation
R8_FR1.3	Propose activities/ideas that later can be implemented and monitored in the center to improve the waste management
R8_FR1.4	Develop mobile games to improve waste management and to promote healthy lifestyle habits
R9_FR1	To teach in the separation at source and related impacts
R9_FR1.1	To teach in the separation at source and related impacts
R10_FR1	To teach in eco-design
R10_FR1.1	To teach in eco-design
R10_FR1.2	Include a selection of key products to be analysed
R11_FR1	To train collection managers and other technicians to optimize the system
R11_FR1.1	To train collection managers and other technicians to optimize the system
R11_FR1.2	Offer different solutions to optimize the system: technical, social, economic, etc.
R12_FR1	Teach about circular economy principles
R12_FR1.1	Teach about circular economy principles
R12_FR1.2	Provide info about the raw materials obtained to be reintroduced in the production chain of other products
R12_FR1.3	Provide info about the specific prevention actions developed for each pilot
R13-14-15_FR1	Facilitate the co-creation of solutions
R13-14-15_FR1.1	Provide a stage editor

DEPLOYMENT
I Sensors are being integrated with the rest of solutions at the pilot site.
T conditions.
P Sensors have been deployed and work as expected.

Development
∅ The device has been designed but it was not started its assembly
α not all functionalities are implemented or some of them are in a wizard or uz type or
β functionalities are implemented but some of them do not behave as expected. obvious
 bugs are been found. The system is been tested in lab conditions.
RC All functionalities are implemented and behaves as expected. Obvious bugs have been
 ironed out. The system is been tested in real conditions.
1 All functionalities are working as expected. The system have been tested in real
 conditions.

IMPLEMENTATION STATUS	
Seveso Pilot	
R-ICT-SOCIAL_FR1	To teach on waste management and prevention actions
R-ICT-SOCIAL_FR1.1	To teach on waste management and prevention actions
R-ICT-SOCIAL_FR2	Track players and results
R-ICT-SOCIAL_FR2.1	Provide a complete log of the use of the tool
R-ICT-SOCIAL_FR2.1.1	Track authorship of every solution
R-ICT-SOCIAL_FR2.1.2	Register the selected KPIs for the evaluation of the solutions achieved
R-ICT-SOCIAL_FR2.1.3	Track the different created solutions to be later assessed or implemented
R-ICT-SOCIAL_FR2.2	Register the needed info to calculate the related KPIs
R-ICT-SOCIAL_FR2.3	Provide final information about the impact of the mistakes of separation at source
R-ICT-SOCIAL_FR2.3.1	Provide information about the impact and recyclability of the materials to create a product
R-ICT-SOCIAL_FR2.3.2	Provide information about the impact and results of the solutions
R-ICT-SOCIAL_FR2.4	Detect where the users have had more difficulties
R-ICT-SOCIAL_FR2.4.1	Coordinated with the performance of learning analytics
R-ICT-SOCIAL_FR2.4.2	Detect the repeated mistakes and doubts of the users about the correct separation
R9_FR1	To teach in the separation at source and related impacts
R9_FR1.1	To teach in the separation at source and related impacts
R10_FR1	To teach in eco-design
R10_FR1.1	To teach in eco-design
R10_FR1.2	Include a selection of key products to be analysed
R11_FR1	To train collection managers and other technicians to optimize the system
R11_FR1.1	To train collection managers and other technicians to optimize the system
R11_FR1.2	Offer different solutions to optimize the system: technical, social, economic, etc.
R12_FR1	Teach about circular economy principles
R12_FR1.1	Teach about circular economy principles
R12_FR1.2	Provide info about the raw materials obtained to be reintroduced in the production chain of other products
R12_FR1.3	Provide info about the specific prevention actions developed for each pilot
R13-14-15_FR1	Facilitate the co-creation of solutions
R13-14-15_FR1.1	Provide a stage editor
Cascais Pilot	
R-ICT-SOCIAL_FR1	To teach on waste management and prevention actions
R-ICT-SOCIAL_FR1.1	To teach on waste management and prevention actions
R-ICT-SOCIAL_FR2	Track players and results
R-ICT-SOCIAL_FR2.1	Provide a complete log of the use of the tool
R-ICT-SOCIAL_FR2.1.1	Track authorship of every solution

Annex 5 Level of development and implementation of the New Treatment Plants expected per period and per pilot based on the fulfillment of every functional requirement and status at Milestone 3

2016												2017												2018												2019											
1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12
Use case analysis						Preparatory Actions						Deployment & Integration						Preliminary Test						Full Test																							
M1						M2						M3						M4						M5																							
1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12	13	14	15	16	17	18	19	20	21	22	23	24	25	26	27	28	29	30	31	32	33	34	35	36	37	38	39	40	41	42						
ref stat												ref stat												ref Estimate												ref											

DEVELOPMENT STATUS		ref stat		ref stat		ref Estimate		ref	
R19_FR1	Monitoring treatment plants (biowaste)	a	RC	β	1	RC	1	1	
R19_FR1.1	Recording the temperature of the Biowaste Treatment Unit (BTU)	a	RC	β	1	RC	1	1	
R19_FR1.2	Recording the moisture of the Biowaste Treatment Unit (BTU)	a	RC	β	1	RC	1	1	
R19_FR1.3	Monitoring of the treatment duration of Biowaste Treatment Unit (BTU)	a	RC	β	1	RC	1	1	
R19_FR2	Biomass product valorization	a	α	β	β	RC	RC	1	
R19_FR2.1	Quantity of biomass product loaded to bioreactor at NTUA (kg/day)	a	α	β	β	RC	RC	1	
R19_FR2.2	Monitoring the quantity of biofuel produced (m3 /day)	a	α	β	β	RC	RC	1	
R19_FR2.3	Monitoring the cost per collection route when collection truck runs with CNG (biofuel) (€/route)	a	θ	β	β	RC	RC	1	
R19_FR2.4	Monitoring the quantity and (possibly quality) of the outputs	a	β	β	β	RC	RC	1	
R19_FR2.4.1	Monitoring the quantity and (possibly quality) of HYTHANE produced per kg biomass product	a	θ	β	RC	RC	RC	1	
R19_FR2.4.2	Monitoring the quantity and (possibly quality) of METHANE produced per kg biomass product	a	β	β	1	RC	1	1	
R19_FR2.4.3	Monitoring the quantity and (possibly quality) of ETHANOL produced per kg biomass product	a	α	β	1	RC	RC	1	
R19_FR2.4.4	Monitoring the quantity and (possibly quality) of COMPOST produced per kg biomass product	a	β	β	RC	RC	1	1	
R19_FR2.4.5	Monitoring the quantity and (possibly quality) of PELLETS produced per kg biomass product	a	β	β	1	RC	1	1	
R19_FR2.4.6	Monitoring the quantity and (possibly quality) of ALTERNATIVE FUEL FOR CEMENT INDUSTRY produced per kg biomass product	a	β	β	β	RC	RC	1	
R19_FR2.4.7	Monitoring the quantity and (possibly quality) of BIOSORBENT produced per kg biomass product	a	β	β	1	RC	1	1	
R19_FR2.4.8	Monitoring the quantity and (possibly quality) of ELECTRICITY produced per kg biomass product through MFC technology	a	β	β	1	RC	1	1	
R19_FR2.4.9	Monitoring the quantity and (possibly quality) of ANIMAL FEED produced per kg biomass product	a	α	β	β	RC	RC	1	
R20_FR1	To treat the food waste and nappies	a	β	β	β	RC	RC	1	
R20_FR1.1	Allow you to temporarily store the disposable nappies, kitchen waste and/or expired food product (EFP)s	a	α	β	β	RC	RC	1	
R20_FR1.2	Allow you to co-treat disposable nappies, EFP and /or kitchen waste in the Waste Treatment Unit (WTU)	a	α	β	β	RC	RC	1	
R20_FR1.3	Allow you to compost the WTU sludge	a	θ	β	β	RC	RC	1	
R20_FR2	Monitoring treatment plants (nappies and biowaste)	a	β	β	β	RC	RC	1	
R20_FR2.1	Monitor and control the temperature of the Waste Treatment Unit (WTU)	a	β	β	β	RC	RC	1	
R20_FR2.2	Monitor and control the pressure of the Waste Treatment Unit (WTU)	a	β	β	β	RC	RC	1	
R20_FR2.3	Monitor the volume and composition of produced biogas in the WTU per kg of nappies and EFP fed in the system	a	β	β	β	RC	RC	1	
R20_FR2.4	Monitor the amount and quality of compost produced per kg of nappies and EFP treated in the WTU	a	θ	β	β	RC	RC	1	

DEPLOYMENT

- I** Sensors are being integrated with the rest of solutions at the pilot site.
- T** Sensors have been deployed and have been integrated. Tests are being carried out in real conditions.
- P** Sensors have been deployed and work as expected.

Development

- θ** The device has been designed but it was not started its assembly
- α** Not all functionalities are implemented or some of them are in a "Wizard of Oz" type of implementation (the function exists but behaves trivially). Only partial test could be made.
- β** All functionalities are implemented but some of them do not behave as expected. Obvious bugs are been found. The system is been tested in lab conditions.
- RC** All functionalities are implemented and behaves as expected. Obvious bugs have been ironed out. The system is been tested in real conditions.
- 1** All functionalities are working as expected. The system have been tested in real conditions.

IMPLEMENTATION STATUS		ref stat		ref stat		ref Estimate		ref	
Seveso Pilot									
Cascais Pilot									
Zamudio Pilot									
R19_FR1	Monitoring treatment plants (biowaste)	I	P	T	P	P	P	P	
R19_FR1.1	Recording the temperature of the Biowaste Treatment Unit (BTU)	I	P	T	P	P	P	P	
R19_FR1.2	Recording the moisture of the Biowaste Treatment Unit (BTU)	I	P	T	P	P	P	P	
R19_FR1.3	Monitoring of the treatment duration of Biowaste Treatment Unit (BTU)	I	P	T	P	P	P	P	
R19_FR1	Monitoring treatment plants (biowaste)	T		I		T		P	
R19_FR1.1	Recording the temperature of the Biowaste Treatment Unit (BTU)	T		I		T		P	
R19_FR1.2	Recording the moisture of the Biowaste Treatment Unit (BTU)	T		I		T		P	
R19_FR1.3	Monitoring of the treatment duration of Biowaste Treatment Unit (BTU)	T		I		T		P	
R19_FR2	Biomass product valorization	I	P	T	P	P	P	P	
R19_FR2.1	Quantity of biomass product loaded to bioreactor at biogas plant (kg/day)	I	P	T	P	P	P	P	
R19_FR2.2	Monitoring the quantity of biofuel produced in biogas (m3 /day)	I	P	T	P	P	P	P	
R19_FR2.3	Monitoring the cost per collection route when collection truck runs with CNG (biofuel) (€/route)	I	P	T	P	P	P	P	
R19_FR2.4	Monitoring the quantity and (possibly quality) of the outputs	I	P	T	P	P	P	P	
R19_FR2.4.1	Monitoring the quantity and (possibly quality) of HYTHANE produced per kg biomass product	I	P	T	P	P	P	P	
R19_FR2.4.2	Monitoring the quantity and (possibly quality) of METHANE produced per kg biomass product	I	P	T	P	P	P	P	
R19_FR2.4.3	Monitoring the quantity and (possibly quality) of ETHANOL produced per kg biomass product	I	P	T	P	P	P	P	
R19_FR2.4.4	Monitoring the quantity and (possibly quality) of COMPOST produced per kg biomass product	I	P	T	P	P	P	P	
R19_FR2.4.5	Monitoring the quantity and (possibly quality) of PELLETS produced per kg biomass product	I	P	T	P	P	P	P	
R19_FR2.4.6	Monitoring the quantity and (possibly quality) of ALTERNATIVE FUEL FOR CEMENT INDUSTRY produced per kg biomass product	I	P	T	P	P	P	P	
R19_FR2.4.7	Monitoring the quantity and (possibly quality) of BIOSORBENT produced per kg biomass product	I	P	T	P	P	P	P	
R19_FR2.4.8	Monitoring the quantity and (possibly quality) of ELECTRICITY produced per kg biomass product through MFC technology	I	P	T	P	P	P	P	
R19_FR2.4.9	Monitoring the quantity and (possibly quality) of ANIMAL FEED produced per kg biomass product	I	P	T	P	P	P	P	
R20_FR1	To treat the food waste and nappies	I	P	T	P	P	P	P	
R20_FR1.1	Allow you to temporarily store the disposable nappies, kitchen waste and/or expired food product (EFP)s	I	P	T	P	P	P	P	
R20_FR1.2	Allow you to co-treat disposable nappies, EFP and /or kitchen waste in the Waste Treatment Unit (WTU)	I	P	T	P	P	P	P	
R20_FR1.3	Allow you to compost the WTU sludge	I	P	T	P	P	P	P	
R20_FR2	Monitoring treatment plants (nappies and biowaste)	I	P	T	P	P	P	P	
R20_FR2.1	Monitor and control the temperature of the Waste Treatment Unit (WTU)	I	P	T	P	P	P	P	
R20_FR2.2	Monitor and control the pressure of the Waste Treatment Unit (WTU)	I	P	T	P	P	P	P	
R20_FR2.3	Monitor the volume and composition of produced biogas in the WTU per kg of nappies and EFP fed in the system	I	P	T	P	P	P	P	
R20_FR2.4	Monitor the amount and quality of compost produced per kg of nappies and EFP treated in the WTU	I	P	T	P	P	P	P	

Annex 6 Waste4Think Story Map

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European WASTE4Think Project

European WASTE4Think Project 2016-2019

Index:

- [1. European Context](#)
- [2. Waste4think Goals](#)
- [3. Partners](#)
- [4. Pilot site](#)
- [5. 20 eco-innovative solutions:](#)

European WASTE4Think Project

1. European Context

The European Union plays a key role in international efforts to promote sustainable development throughout the world. The environmental policy of the EU up to **2020** is guided by the **Seventh Environmental Action Programme**, of which the European institutions and the Member States are jointly responsible.

One of the main perspectives in the Europe 2020 Strategy is to further advance progress towards the achievement of a **Circular Economy (CE)**. The Waste4Think project promotes a major transformation of the current model of waste management so as to convert this model into the foundation of the principles of this new economy paradigm.

The CE aims to promote change towards a more **efficient economy** in the use of resources and an approach to development with low-carbon emissions. This new paradigm seeks to maintain the values of products materials and resources as long as possible.

In this regards, there is a need to implement specific actions to quantify the degree of attainment of these strategies at **municipal level**, mainly in terms of effective management of municipal waste because it accounts for about 10% of the total waste generated in the European Union.

2. Waste4think Goals

The main objective of Waste4Think is to move forward the current waste management practices into a Circular Economy motto demonstrating the value of integrating and validating 20 eco-innovative solutions that cover all the waste value chain. The benefits of these solutions will be enhanced by a holistic waste data management methodology and will be demonstrated in 4 complementary urban areas in Europe.

European WASTE4Think Project

2. Waste4think Goals

The main objective of **Waste4Think** is to move forward the current waste management practices into a Circular Economy motto demonstrating the value of integrating and validating **20 eco-innovative solutions** that cover all the waste value chain. The benefits of these solutions will be enhanced by a holistic waste data management methodology and will be demonstrated in **4 complementary urban areas** in Europe.

The main objective of Waste4Think is to move forward the current waste management practices into a circular economy motto demonstrating the value of integrating and validating **20 eco-innovative solutions** that cover all the waste value chain. The benefits of these solutions will be enhanced by a **holistic waste data management methodology**, and will be demonstrated in **4 complementary urban areas in Europe**.

Attached to this main objective a set of specific ones have been defined to indicate what the project will be focused into:

- To **reduce generation of waste** thanks to prevention campaigns and cooperative activities to promote reuse and eco-design solutions.
- To **promote behavioural changes** in the waste generators by awareness campaigns and new educational tools in order to foster more sustainable consumption and production habits and to increase the rate of waste sorting.
- To **improve the integral waste management services** reducing their management costs and the GHG (greenhouse gas) emissions.
- To **reduce the amount** of primary waste deposited in landfill to zero and to the maximum in case of secondary waste.
- To **identify the waste products** with a low potential for recycling and to propose eco-

European WASTE4Think Project

3. Partners

1. [DeustoTech](#)
2. [Zabala](#)
3. [City Council of Zamudio](#)
4. [Aclima](#)
5. [Green Technologies](#)
6. [EnBio](#)
7. [National Technical University of Athens](#)
8. [UPATRAS](#)
9. [Municipality of Halandri](#)
10. [Serious Games](#)
11. [ARS ambiente](#)
12. [Seveso municipality](#)
13. [Legambiente](#)
14. [SOFTline](#)
15. [MOBA](#)
16. [Virtualware](#)
17. [Cascais Ambiente](#)
18. [BCNecologia](#)
19. [Engineering](#)

MAPA DE VISTA
GENERAL

European WASTE4Think Project

4. Pilot site

The main objective of **Waste4Think** is to move forward the current waste management practices into a Circular Economy motto demonstrating the value of integrating and validating **20 eco-innovative solutions** that cover all the waste value chain. The benefits of these solutions will be enhanced by a holistic waste data management methodology and will be demonstrated in **4 complementary urban areas** in Europe.

Zamudio, Spain

[Pilot Site](#)

Located in the north of the Iberian Peninsula, is a municipality with around **3.200 inhabitants**,

European WASTE4Think Project

holistic waste data management methodology and will be demonstrated in **4 complementary urban areas** in Europe.

Zamudio, Spain

Pilot Site

Located in the north of the Iberian Peninsula, is a municipality with around **3.200 inhabitants**, characterised by a big enterprise ecosystem **7 industrial areas** including the biggest scientific technological park in the province, with **urban waste generation supposes a 68%** of the total waste generated.

Cascais, Portugal

 ATRÁS

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holistic waste data management methodology and will be demonstrated in **4 complementary urban areas** in Europe.

Zamudio, Spain

Pilot Site

Located in the north of the Iberian Peninsula, is a municipality with around **3.200 inhabitants**, characterised by a big enterprise ecosystem **7 industrial areas** including the biggest scientific technological park in the province, with **urban waste generation supposes a 68%** of the total waste generated.

Cascais, Portugal

ATRÁS

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Cascais, Portugal

[Pilot Site](#)

Located in Portugal, 30 km west of Lisbon. It is one of the richest municipalities and a very **touristic area**. The population is **206,479 inhabitants**, in an area of **97,40 Km²**.

Seveso, Italy

 ATRÁS

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Cascais, Portugal

[Pilot Site](#)

Located in Portugal, 30 km west of Lisbon. It is one of the richest municipalities and a very **touristic area**. The population is **206,479 inhabitants**, in an area of **97,40 Km²**.

Seveso, Italy

 ATRÁS

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S **Seveso, Italy**

Globe icon **Pilot Site**

Located in the Lombardia region of Italy, nearby Milan. The population is **22.000 inhabitants**. Currently, waste generation is around 9,000 tons year, and the **recycling rate was 64%** in 2013.

H **Halandry, Greece**

European WASTE4Think Project

Seveso, Italy

[Pilot Site](#)

Located in the Lombardia region of Italy, nearby Milan. The population is **22.000 inhabitants**. Currently, waste generation is around 9,000 tons year, and the **recycling rate was 64%** in 2013.

Halandry, Greece

 ATRÁS

European WASTE4Think Project

Halandry, Greece

Pilot Site

Located in the north/east of Attica basin, and it is considered the **largest suburban city of the capital of Athens** Greece, with more than **70,000 residents**. Halandry has a **wide range of business activities**, especially in the service sector and food industry, and it also hosts some multinational companies such as IBM, KPMG, GlaxoSmithkline, Vodafone. As consequence of this economical activity, Halandry attracts **15.000 commuters every day**.

5. 20 eco-innovative solutions

The main objective of Waste4Think is to move forward the current waste management practices into a Circular Economy motto demonstrating the value of integrating and validating 20 eco-innovative

European WASTE4Think Project

Halandry, Greece

[Pilot Site](#)

Located in the north/east of Attica basin, and it is considered the **largest suburban city of the capital of Athens** Greece, with more than **70,000 residents**. Halandri has a **wide range of business activities**, especially in the service sector and food industry, and it also hosts some multinational companies such as IBM, KPMG, GlaxoSmithkline, Vodafone. As consequence of this economical activity, Halandri attracts **15.000 commuters every day**.

5. 20 eco-innovative solutions

The main objective of **Waste4Think** is to move forward the current waste management practices into a Circular Economy motto demonstrating the value of integrating and validating 20 eco-innovative

European WASTE4Think Project

5. 20 eco-innovative solutions

The main objective of **Waste4Think** is to move forward the current waste management practices into a Circular Economy motto demonstrating the value of integrating and validating **20 eco-innovative solutions** that cover all the waste value chain. The benefits of these solutions will be enhanced by a holistic waste data management methodology and will be demonstrated in **4 complementary urban areas** in Europe.

The project will have a set of clearly identified eco-innovative results, all of them with a clear market orientation, given the nature of the Innovation Actions in H2020.

5.1 Operation and Planning Tools

Information Technology (IT):

Operation and Management Module:

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5.1 Operation and Planning Tools

Information Technology (IT):

Operation and Management Module:

 Observatory

 Complex event processing (Sandwich)

Pilot data Ingestion:

 Characterization

 Treatment deposit plant

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5.1 Operation and Planning Tools

Information Technology (IT):

Operation and Management Module:

Observatory

Complex event processing (Sandwich)

Pilot data Ingestion:

Characterization

Treatment deposit plant

Waste management KPIs

Information Technology (IT):

Operation and Management Module:

Baseline (Month 12). KPIs Results (12/2015)

Monitoring (Sept 2018)

Evolution of the High Level KPIs with respect to the baseline and monitoring (Sept/2018).

Seveso:

Baseline (Month 12). KPIs Results (04/2017)

 SANDWICH

MY SANDWICHES

PUBLIC SANDWICHES

Sandwich

Cook software by piling code ingredients

START

Sandwich

A service of DeustoTech Energy and Environment

Information Technology (IT):

*Operation and Management Module:***Baseline (Month 12). KPIs Results (04/2017)**

 > ZAMUDIO > Upload characterization

Sorting Type

 Choose your option

Characterization details for selected Sorting Type

Sample characterization	Description	kg
Biodegradable Kitchen and canteen waste avoidable food waste	Edible products not consumed originated in domestic kitchens or commercial and industrial canteens, including those products which preferential consumption date has expired but not their expiration date	kg
Biodegradable Kitchen and canteen waste non avoidable food waste	Edible products originated in domestic kitchens or commercial and industrial canteens. However these products have exceed their expiration date and they become inedible.	kg
Small size garden waste	Biodegradable waste originated in domestic or public gardens, parks or landscape elements	kg
Pruning waste	Biodegradable waste originated in domestic or public gardens, parks or landscape elements no included in other categories	kg
Other biodegradable waste	Biodegradable waste not included in the previous categories such as coffe, grounds, tea bags, corks	kg
Paper packaging	Packaging and wrapping paper	kg

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Information Technology (IT):

*Operation and Management Module:***Baseline (Month 12). KPIs Results (04/2017)**
 ATRÁS
 > ENBIO treatment plant > Upload measure

Date

Morning Batch

Weight of HFW (kg):

Weight of FORBI (kg) :

Electricity counter index (start of every cycle) (kW):

Electricity counter index (end of every cycle) (kW):

Energy consumption (kW) :

Afternoon Batch

Weight of HFW (kg)

Weight of FORBI (kg) :

Electricity counter index (start of every cycle) (kW):

Electricity counter index (end of every cycle) (kW):

Energy consumption (kW) :

 SUBM

European WASTE4Think Project

Characterization

Treatment deposit plant

Waste management KPIs

Cascais:

Baseline (Month 12). KPIs Results (02/2017)

Halandri:

Baseline (Month 12). KPIs Results (12/2015)

Monitoring (Sept 2018)

Evolution of the High Level KPIs with respect to the baseline and monitoring (Sept/2018).

Seveso:

Baseline (Month 12). KPIs Results (04/2017)

Monitoring (Nov 2017)

Evolution of the High Level KPIs with respect to the baseline and monitoring (Nov/2017).

Monitoring (Apr 2018)

Evolution of the High Level KPIs with respect to the baseline and monitoring (04/2018).

Zamudio:

Baseline (Month 12). KPIs Results (06/2017)

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[Caracterization](#)
[Treatment deposit plant](#)
Waste management KPIs
Cascais:
[Baseline \(Month 12\). KPIs Results \(02/2017\)](#)
Halandri:
[Baseline \(Month 12\). KPIs Results \(12/2015\)](#)
[Monitoring \(Sept 2018\)](#)
[Evolution of the High Level KPIs with respect to the baseline and monitoring \(Sept/2018\).](#)
Seveso:
[Baseline \(Month 12\). KPIs Results \(04/2017\)](#)
[Monitoring \(Nov 2017\)](#)
[Evolution of the High Level KPIs with respect to the baseline and monitoring \(Nov/2017\).](#)
[Monitoring \(Apr 2018\)](#)
[Evolution of the High Level KPIs with respect to the baseline and monitoring \(04/2018\).](#)
Zamudio:
[Baseline \(Month 12\). KPIs Results \(06/2017\)](#)
Collection Module:

D1.3. Sustainability Assessment Model									
ID Objectives	KPIs (High Level)	High Level KPIs Results	KPIs (Intermediate and Low Level)	Intermediate and Low Level KPIs Total results	RESIDUAL WASTE	SEPARATE COLLECTION CIRCUITS			
					WCC1	WCC5	WCC6	WCC7	
					Residual Waste	Plastic and Metal	Paper and Cardboard	Glass	
					domestic-Commercial	Domestic-Commercial	Domestic-Commercial	Domestic-Commercial	
Collective (street bins)	Collective (street bins)	Collective (street bins)	Collective (street bins)						
0.1	T.1. Average reduction of municipal waste generation	N/A	T.1.2. Real amount (level) of waste generated (RAG) (waste characterization %)		58,50% biowaste, 4% paper and cardboard, 1% glass 18,5% Light packaging 4% miscellaneous 5,25% Sanitary textile + nappies 0,15 % batteries 6,5 % 10 mm sieved fractions 2,1 % Others	100 % light packaging	100 % paper and cardboard	100 %glass	

European WASTE4Think Project

Baseline (Month 12). KPIs Results (06/2017)

Collection Module:

[Collection Optimization](#)

Seveso

Cascais

[Truck Data APP](#)

Planning Module:

[Environmental Impact Transport of Waste Collection \(Geosimulation\)](#)

[Zero Waste](#)

[Social Action](#)

Circular economy module:

[Circular economy](#)
 ATRÁS

 MAPA

 SELECCIONAR CLIENTE x

 SELECCIONAR SITIO x

 SITIO: DUNKIN DONUTS, LA RAMBLA, 89 (D01) x

Guardar

Cancelar

Salir

 Sitio: Dunkin Donuts, LA RAMBLA, 89 (D01)

DATOS PRINCIPALES

DATOS DIRECCIÓN

DATOS DE CONTACTO

CLIENTES

ELEMENTOS

EMPRESAS

N.I.F./C.I.F.:

* CÓDIGO 1:

18013

CÓDIGO 2:

75590

* TIPO SITIO:

Comercial

ACTIVIDAD:

* NOMBRE:

Dunkin Donuts

 LA POSICIÓN DE LOS ELEMENTOS CAMBIA SEGÚN LA DEL SITIO

LATITUD:

41,3821

LONGITUD:

2,17232

INFORMACIÓN ADICIONAL:

1233456789

European WASTE4Think Project

Baseline (Month 12). KPIs Results (06/2017)

Collection Module:

Collection Optimization

Seveso

Cascais

Truck Data APP

Planning Module:

Environmental Impact Transport of Waste Collection (Geosimulation)

Zero Waste

Social Action

Circular economy module:

Circular economy

Trasera 1 4590 DER

Date 25/08/2018 **Time** 12:05 **Latitude** 43.278733 **Longitude** -2.8805157

Route Operator1 **Person** Industrial **Tag** 01824 **Number** 25

Gross 53 **Net** 16 **Tare** 37

European WASTE4Think Project

Collection Optimization

Seveso

Cascais

Truck Data APP

Planning Module:

Environmental Impact Transport of Waste Collection (Geosimulation)

Zero Waste

Social Action

Circular economy module:

Circular economy

5.2 New Treatments

AGREGAR SECCIÓN

ORGANIZAR

European WASTE4Think Project

Planning Module:

 Environmental Impact Transport of Waste Collection (Geosimulation)

 Zero Waste

 Social Action

Circular economy module:

 Circular economy

5.2 New Treatments

Zero Waste Events

Create environmentally sustainable events

How: An environmentally sustainable event is one event that has been designed, organized and carried out in such a way that minimizes the potential negative impacts on the environment. A zero waste event is an event that has been designed, organized and developed with the aim of no generating wastes.

Why: The introduction of environmental criteria in this decision-making process of an event offers advantages at many levels: economic saves, social and environmental benefits, access to sponsoring and funding, improvement of the image, attendants environmental sensitization and satisfaction.

When: The environmental criteria, elements and activities should be introduced in the design, organization and development (including post-closure activities) phases of the event.

How: Elements to be included: sustainable consumption, prevention and waste management, minimization of the water/energy

European WASTE4Think Project

Planning Module:

[Environmental Impact Transport of Waste Collection \(Geosimulation\)](#)

[Zero Waste](#)

[Social Action](#)

Circular economy module:

[Circular economy](#)

5.2 New Treatments

<input type="checkbox"/>	Name	Short description	Start date	End date
<input type="checkbox"/>	H3.1.1 Food separate collection and treatment		-	-
<input type="checkbox"/>	H1.2 Gymnasium	The educational program is focusing on four main working areas: - Waste monitoring - Waste Management prevention/reuse - Home composting - Food Waste The program is constructed in the framework of the "Environmental Program" which is implemented in 2017-2018 in the school and is a non-typical form of education that is approved by the Ministry of Education on a yearly basis. The program started in December 2017, after having faced some difficulties. The main activity of the school has been composting. A series of lessons have been delivered in class, and students have presented individual research on the topic. A presentation has also taken place from the NTUA team in the school, along with the installation of the composter and the initial loading with biowaste, brought by the students from home, and prunings from the school's garden. Monitoring instruments have also been given to the school by the municipality. The process has faced some problems, with the initial batch of the compost going wrong, and a second one as well. The process has been abandoned for this year. Also, actions have been taken to monitor the waste generated in the class. A form has been filled, describing certain types of waste typically found in a class bin (paper, plastic bottles, food packaging, aluminum cans, food, gums, other), and the amount of each type was measured. This will be done again, this time measuring the weight and volume of each type, and also examining bins found outside the class, in other areas of the school.	Dec. 1, 2017	2018
<input type="checkbox"/>	H1.1 3erd Vocational	The educational program is focusing on four main working areas: - Waste monitoring - Waste Management prevention/reuse - Home composting - Food Waste The program is constructed in the framework of the "Research on Technology" and "Environmental Program" which are implemented in 2017-2018 in the school and are non-typical forms of education that are approved by the Ministry of Education. It started on October 21, and has culminated so far to 6 homework packages which have been presented in class. The actions take place each week, and have been covering 3 of the main working areas, and recycling (secondary working area): Waste Monitoring, Home composting, Food waste, Recycling, Waste management, Citizen Science demonstration, Reuse/Prevention	Nov. 1, 2017	2018
<input type="checkbox"/>	Z8.3.1 Arimen Gaba	The citizens dressed up and paraded through the streets of Zamudio with the candles they made with used cooking oil. There was also a theater set in the day of the souls. Afterwards, a drink and pumpkin pies were distributed and at the same time there was a demonstration of how to make candles with used cooking oil.	Oct. 31, 2017	2018
<input type="checkbox"/>	Z8.2.1 Lagatzu Eco-	In June, Basque Culture Association from Zamudio celebrates during the weekend different fostering actions. They make a popular lunch on	June	2018

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5.2 New Treatments

Bio -Fuel and Compost Production Plant

Predried and shredded Bio-Waste

5.3 Educational Materials

← ATRÁS

Bio -Fuel and Compost Production Plant

Video: [Pilot Plant for the disposable nappies and expired food products exploitation](#)

5.3 Educational Materials

Serious games

- Sorting game
- Eco-desing game
- Mayor's table
- Virtual city game

Learning materials

- Digital projects:

WASTE 4think.eu

Serious games

- [Sorting game](#)
- [Eco-designing game](#)
- [Mayor's table](#)
- [Virtual city game](#)

Learning materials

- Digital projects:
 - [After the concert](#)
 - [Where is wastey?](#)
- Steam Lesson:
 - [What has happened?](#)
 - [What has happened?](#)
 - [How can the guilty be found?](#)
 - [Wastey blushes us](#)
- Mobile Games:
 - [0waste](#)
 - [Sunflower](#)

WASTE4THINK
Ways2Sort

WASTE4THINK
Eco Designer

European WASTE4Think Project

 Mayor's table

 Virtual city game

Learning materials

 Digital projects:

- [After the concert](#)
- [Where is wastey?](#)

 Steam Lesson:

- [What has happened?](#)
- [What has happened?](#)
- [How can the guilty be found?](#)
- [Wastey blushes us](#)

 Mobile Games:

 [Owaste](#)
 [Sunflower](#)
 [Treasure machine](#)
 ATRÁS

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5.4 Citizen Science

- Mapping session and collect data with forms:

Halandri

Zamudio

5.5 Apps

European WASTE4Think Project

5.4 Citizen Science

- Mapping session and collect data with forms:

Halandri

Zamudio

5.5 Apps

	Title	Description	Related project
	Waste4Think Field work Amenities		WASTE4THINK: Moving towards Life Cycle Thinking by integrating Advanced Waste Management Systems
	Waste4Think Field work House Numbers		WASTE4THINK: Moving towards Life Cycle Thinking by integrating Advanced Waste Management Systems
	Waste4Think Field work Waste		WASTE4THINK: Moving towards Life Cycle Thinking by integrating

European WASTE4Think Project

5.5 Apps

5.6 Prevention and Best Practices

Best Practices:

Innovative awareness actions including web-based tools for dissemination of best practices and foster mutual learning:

5.6 Prevention and Best Practices

Best Practices:

Innovative awareness actions including web-based tools for dissemination of best practices and foster mutual learning:

AC.1. School Canteens Contest

Type of campaign:

- **Waste fraction:** Food waste
- **Waste management stage:** Prevention
- **Target group:** Students

AC.2. Packaging advisory

Type of campaign:

- **Waste fraction:** All packaging
- **Waste management stage:** Redesigning
- **Target group:** SME, Industrial Generator

European WASTE4Think Project

AC.2. Packaging advisory

Type of campaign:

- **Waste fraction:** All packaging
- **Waste management stage:** Redesigning
- **Target group:** SME, Industrial Generator

AC.3. Community composting in Pallars Sobirà

Type of campaign:

- **Waste fraction:** Food waste
- **Waste management stage:** On site treatment
- **Target group:** Domestic Generator

← ATRÁS

AC4 Community Composting in Pallars Sobira

Community Composting is a pioneering initiative in Catalonia that involves the management of the organic fraction of a village. It involves the cooperation of all residents as they become their own managers. The campaign is aimed specially for villages with less than 100 inhabitants.

European WASTE4Think Project

Best Practice Book

This written handbook collecting the best practices on waste management detected and applied during the project. The aim is to compile and transfer the best waste management solutions tested in the four pilots.

European WASTE4Think Project

Claves para conseguir los objetivos de prevención y reciclaje de residuo municipales: sistemas de recogida, educación ambiental y fiscalidad

Key factors to meet prevention & recycling targets for municipal solid waste: collection systems, environmental education programmes and taxation

Ainhoa Alonso, Iraia Oribe, Cruz Borges, Marta Vila, Gemma Nohales, Michele Giavini

ISBN 978-84-94942-51-4

Economic Instruments

[Regolamento per la disciplina dell'imposta unica comunale. IUC 2017 Seveso](#)

Community Waste4Think

TITOLO I – PRINCIPI GENERALI

Art. 1 - Oggetto del Regolamento

1. Il presente Regolamento, adottato nell'ambito della potestà regolamentare prevista dall'articolo 52 del Decreto Legislativo 15/12/1997 n. 446, ha per oggetto la disciplina della TARI diretta alla copertura dei costi del servizio di raccolta e smaltimento rifiuti, prevista dall'art. 1 comma 639 della Legge n. 147 del 27 dicembre 2013.
2. Per quanto non previsto dal presente regolamento si applicano le disposizioni di legge vigenti.

Art. 2 - Istituzione della TARI a misura

1. Per la copertura integrale dei costi relativi alla gestione dei rifiuti urbani e di quelli assimilati, è istituita sul territorio comunale la TARI a Misura.

Art. 3 - Determinazione della tariffa

1. La tariffa è determinata sulla base del metodo normalizzato approvato con D.P.R. 27.04.1999, n. 158, come integrato dal presente Regolamento e di misurazioni puntuali del rifiuto indifferenziato conferito per singola utenza, suddivisa in quota fissa e quota variabile ed articolata in utenze domestiche e non domestiche.
2. La tariffa è deliberata dal Consiglio Comunale, in conformità al Piano Finanziario del servizio di gestione dei rifiuti urbani, di cui all'art.1 comma 683 della Legge n. 147/2013, a valere per l'anno di riferimento. Il Piano Finanziario è redatto secondo le indicazioni del D.P.R. 27.04.1999, n. 158, ed è approvato dal Consiglio Comunale. In caso di mancata deliberazione si intende prorogata la tariffa precedentemente deliberata ed in vigore.
3. La ripartizione dei costi totali del servizio tra utenze domestiche e non domestiche è stabilita dal Consiglio Comunale, contestualmente all'approvazione della tariffa per la gestione dei rifiuti urbani e assimilati.
4. La tariffa è composta da una quota determinata in relazione alle componenti essenziali del costo del servizio di gestione dei rifiuti e da una quota rapportata alle quantità di rifiuti conferiti, al servizio fornito e all'entità dei costi di gestione, in modo che sia assicurata la copertura integrale dei costi di investimento e di esercizio.
5. È fatta salva ai sensi del comma 666 art. 1 Legge 147/2013 l'applicazione del tributo provinciale per l'esercizio delle funzioni di tutela, protezione ed igiene dell'ambiente di cui all'articolo 29 del decreto legislativo 30 dicembre 2002, n. 504. Il tributo provinciale, commisurato alla superficie dei locali ed aree assoggettabili a tributo, è applicato nella misura percentuale deliberata dalla provincia sull'importo del tributo.
6. La TARI a Misura è applicata e riscossa dal Comune di Seveso, che è anche titolare del credito dell'utenza.
7. La gestione dei rifiuti urbani comprende la raccolta, il trasporto, il recupero e lo smaltimento dei rifiuti urbani e assimilati, i servizi di spazzamento e di igiene, le azioni di prevenzione rifiuti e costituisce un servizio di pubblico interesse, svolto in regime di privativa sull'intero territorio comunale.
8. Il servizio è disciplinato dalle disposizioni del Decreto Legislativo 3 aprile 2006, n. 152, del Regolamento comunale di igiene urbana e gestione dei rifiuti, nonché dalle disposizioni previste nel presente regolamento.

Art. 4 - Presupposti per l'applicazione della tariffa

1. La tariffa è dovuta da chiunque, persona fisica o giuridica, possieda, occupi o detenga a qualsiasi titolo locali o aree scoperte ad uso privato o pubblico, a qualsiasi uso adibiti esistenti nel territorio comunale, che producano o che potenzialmente siano suscettibili di produrre rifiuti urbani e/o assimilati, con vincolo di solidarietà tra i componenti del nucleo familiare e tra coloro che usano in comune i locali e le aree stesse.
2. Fino all'attuazione delle disposizioni di cui al comma 647 dell'art. 1 della Legge 147/2013, la superficie delle unità immobiliari a destinazione ordinaria iscritte o iscrivibili nel catasto edilizio urbano assoggettabile al tributo è costituita da quella calpestabile dei locali e delle aree suscettibili di produrre rifiuti urbani e assimilati. Ai fini dell'applicazione della tariffa si considerano le superfici dichiarate o accertate ai fini della Tar, L. 147/2013. Per le altre unità immobiliari, la superficie da utilizzare per il calcolo della TARI, ai sensi del comma 648 dell'art. 1 della Legge 147/2013, è pari a quella calpestabile.
3. La superficie calpestabile viene misurata come segue:
 - a) la superficie dei locali assoggettabile a TARI è misurata al netto dei muri, escludendo i balconi e le terrazze;
 - b) la superficie delle aree esterne assoggettabile a TARI è misurata sul perimetro interno delle stesse, al netto di eventuali costruzioni su di esse esistenti. Per la sua determinazione si può tenere conto di quella risultante dall'atto di provenienza o del contratto di affitto, se si tratta di aree di proprietà privata, ovvero dell'atto di concessione se si tratta di aree di proprietà pubblica;
 - c) nel calcolare il totale delle superfici, le frazioni di metro quadrato inferiori a 0,50 vanno trascurate, quelle pari o superiori vanno arrotondate ad un metro quadrato;
 - d) la superficie dei locali e delle aree assoggettabili a TARI è desunta dalla planimetria catastale o da altra analogo (ad esempio planimetria sottoscritta da un tecnico abilitato iscritto all'Albo professionale) o da misurazione diretta. Per la sua determinazione si può tenere conto di quella risultante dall'atto di provenienza o del contratto di affitto se si tratta di aree di proprietà privata o dell'atto di concessione se si tratta di aree di proprietà pubblica.
4. Nel caso di locali in multiproprietà e di centri commerciali integrati, il soggetto che gestisce i servizi comuni è responsabile del versamento della tariffa dovuta per i locali ed aree scoperte di uso comune e per i locali ed aree scoperte in uso esclusivo ai singoli occupanti o detentori, fermi restando nei confronti di questi ultimi, gli altri obblighi o diritti derivanti dal rapporto tributario riguardante i locali e le aree in uso esclusivo. E' fatto obbligo al soggetto responsabile del pagamento di presentare all'Ufficio Tributi del Comune, solo in caso di variazioni, entro il 20 gennaio dell'anno successivo, l'elenco degli occupanti o detentori dei locali in multiproprietà e del centro commerciale integrato.
5. Ai fini dell'attività di accertamento, il comune, per le unità immobiliari a destinazione ordinaria iscritte o iscrivibili nel catasto edilizio urbano, può considerare, sino all'attuazione delle procedure di allineamento tra dati catastali e i dati relativi alla toponomastica e la numerazione civica interna ed esterna, come superficie assoggettabile al tributo quella pari all'80 per cento della superficie catastale determinata secondo i criteri stabiliti dal regolamento di cui al decreto del Presidente della Repubblica 23 marzo 1998, n. 138.
6. La tariffa è commisurata all'intero anno solare ed è dovuta limitatamente al periodo dell'anno nel quale si verificano le condizioni di cui al comma 1, cui corrisponde un'autonomia obbligatoria tributaria.

Art. 5 - Superfici soggette a tariffa

1. Sono soggetti a tariffa tutti i locali comunque denominati, esistenti in qualsiasi specie di costruzione stabilmente infissa al suolo o nel suolo, chiusi o chiusibili da ogni lato qualunque sia la loro destinazione a prescindere dalla loro regolarità in relazione alle disposizioni di carattere urbanistico-edilizio, compresi quelli accessori o pertinenziali, e qualunque sia il loro uso, purché suscettibili di produrre rifiuti urbani, esistenti interamente o prevalentemente nel territorio del Comune. Si considerano soggetti tutti i locali predisposti all'uso anche se di fatto non utilizzati, considerando tali quelli dotati di almeno un'utenza attiva ai servizi di rete (acqua, energia elettrica, gas) o di arredamento e, per i locali ad uso non domestico, quelli forniti di impianti, attrezzature o, comunque, non quellevoche è ufficialmente consentito l'esercizio di un'attività nei locali medesimi.
2. Sono altresì soggette a tariffa tutte le aree scoperte operative occupate o detenute, a qualsiasi uso adibite, la cui superficie insiste interamente o prevalentemente nel territorio comunale, considerandosi tali anche quelle coperte da tettoie o altre strutture e aperte su almeno un lato, comprese quelle accessorie e pertinenziali.
3. La mancata utilizzazione del servizio di gestione dei rifiuti urbani e assimilati o l'interruzione temporanea dello stesso non comportano esonero o riduzione del tributo.

Art. 6 - Superfici non soggette a tariffa

European WASTE4Think Project

Marta Vila, Gemma Nohales, Michele Giavini

Economics Instruments

Normativa Seveso

Community Waste4Think

4think

European WASTE4Think Project 2016-2019

Moving towards Life Cycle Thinking by integrating Advanced Waste Management Systems

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Moving towards Life Cycle Thinking by integrating Advanced Waste Management Systems

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LA IMPLEMENTACIÓN DEL PAGO POR GENERACIÓN JUNTO A UN INTENSO PROGRAMA DE EDUCACION AMBIENTAL EN SEVESO, ITALIA

Giavini, Michele; Vila, Marta;

Implementation in Seveso, an Italian municipality of about 21.000 inhabitants, of a Pay-As-You-Throw system associated to a structured program of social activities to sensitize citizens. The action has been implemented in the framework of the HORIZON2020 Waste4Think project.

Uploaded on November 27, 2018

November 27, 2018 (v1) **Project deliverable** **Open Access**

[View](#)

D4 .2. Implementation of R17: ICT based Innovative Social Actions

BCNecologia;

This report describes the environmental education strategies to be followed during the implementation of each pilot, including the most innovative social actions that use ICT platform developed in this project (R1-R15) to reach a high level of awareness and change in habits from the different target.

Uploaded on November 27, 2018

October 24, 2018 (v1) **Book** **Open Access**

[View](#)

Key factors to meet prevention and recycling targets for municipal solid waste: collection systems, environmental education programmes and taxation

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Community

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Annex 7 Social Actions Gantt Chart

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement 688995

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Modifications:

Z2: Some actions implemented (composting modules, workshop for reuse of cooking oil), delay in the application of the STEAM lessons

Z3: Preparatory activities (survey) Dec '17

Z4: Preparatory activities during the last months of the year, initial activities Feb'18

Z6.4 Industrial activities participation will be delayed 4-6 months

Forecast for the development of the action

	2016												2017												2018												2019											
	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12
	Use case analysis							M1					Preparatory Actions							M2					Deployment & Integration						M3			Preliminary Test			M4			Full Test						M5		
	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12	13	14	15	16	17	18	19	20	21	22	23	24	25	26	27	28	29	30	31	32	33	34	35	36	37	38	39	40	41	42						
Seveso Pilot																																																
SE1 Citizens Sensitization. Funny door to door																																																
SE1.1 Dinner or Lunch with waste																																																
SE1.2 Sensitization activity in public spaces or existing activities																																																
SE1.3 Elderly people house activities																																																
SE1.4 Sensitization in schools																																																
SE1.5 Sensitization in summer camps with children																																																
SE1.6 sensitization in private courtyards																																																
SE2 Campaign "virtuous households"																																																
SE2.1 Citizens involvement																																																
SE2.2 Training and monitoring period Recycling focus																																																
SE2.3 Feedback activities																																																
SE2.4 - second stage: VH focusing on waste prevention																																																
SE3 Ecoevents																																																
SE3.1 Preparation of the criteria, tendering and purchasing																																																
SE3.2 Celebration and monitoring of the Ecoevents.																																																
SE4 PAYT																																																
SE4.1 Monitoring RFID bags, tax calculations and preparation of the campaign																																																
SE4.2 Implementation campaign.																																																
SE4.3 Incidences resolution and feedback to citizens																																																
SE4.4 Littering monitoring and dedicated campaign																																																
SE4.5 Other complementary activities																																																
SE5 Campaign of reusable nappies families																																																
SE5.1 Engagement of local stakeholders																																																
SE5.2 Campaign and training development																																																
SE5.3 Feedback to participants and general citizens																																																
SE6. Reusable nappies in a nursery																																																
SE6.1 Stakeholders engagement (nursery + washing service)																																																
SE6.2 Implementation																																																
SE6.3 Feedback to participants																																																

Modifications:

SE2: Delayed until March-April 2018

SE5: Preparatory activities in Sep '17, main activities will start in January '18

SE6: Delayed until June 18

SE1 : New actions added

 Forecast for the development of the action

	2016												2017												2018												2019																						
	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12											
	Use case analysis						M1						Preparatory Actions						M2						Deployment & Integration						M3						Preliminary Test						M4						Full Test						M5				
	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12	13	14	15	16	17	18	19	20	21	22	23	24	25	26	27	28	29	30	31	32	33	34	35	36	37	38	39	40	41	42																	
Halandri pilot																																																											
H1 Educational Centers activities																																																											
<i>H1.1 Vocational School</i>																																																											
<i>H1.2 Gymnasium</i>																																																											
H2 Actions at the technical university																																																											
<i>H2.1 Ecodesign modul introduction.</i>																																																											
<i>H2.2 Use of the Ecodesign game</i>																																																											
H3 Foodwaste separate collection																																																											
<i>H3.1 Initial seminars and campaign.</i>																																																											
<i>H3.2 Starting campaign.</i>																																																											
<i>H3.3 Feedback to the citizens.</i>																																																											
<i>H3.4 Extension of the new collection.</i>																																																											
H4 Commercial Activities campaign																																																											
<i>H4.1 Citizens science.</i>																																																											
<i>H4.2 Promotion of best consumption habits and waste handling in local commerce.</i>																																																											
H5 Nappies collection																																																											
<i>H5.1 Contact with nappies producers</i>																																																											
<i>H5.2 Start of the collection & treatment</i>																																																											
<i>H5.3 Feedback actions to participants</i>																																																											

H3. New action added, extension of the biowaste collection

 Forecast for the development of the action

	2016												2017												2018												2019																						
	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12											
	Use case analysis						M1						Preparatory Actions						M2						Deployment & Integration						M3						Preliminary Test						M4						Full Test						M5				
	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12	13	14	15	16	17	18	19	20	21	22	23	24	25	26	27	28	29	30	31	32	33	34	35	36	37	38	39	40	41	42																	
Seveso Pilot																																																											
C1 ID/PAYT containers system																																																											
<i>C1.2 Implementation campaign – condominium meetings</i>																																																											
<i>C1.3 Implementation campaign- workshops and Dtd visits</i>																																																											
<i>C1.4 Gammification-Award system</i>																																																											
<i>C1.5 Promotion of the W4T Apps and games</i>																																																											
<i>C1.6 Feedback to citizens</i>																																																											
C2 Tourist engagement																																																											
<i>C2.1 Information to landlords</i>																																																											
<i>C2.2 Dedicated campaign</i>																																																											
C3 W4T schools																																																											
<i>C3.1 Learning materials (mobile games and STEAM lessons)</i>																																																											
<i>C3.2 Sorting game (primary) and Virtual and Planning game (secondary)</i>																																																											
<i>C3.3 EMAC own activities</i>																																																											

 Forecast for the development of the action

Annex 8 Social Actions Results until Milestone 3

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement 688995

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Horizon 2020
European Union Funding
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Z3.4 Food Redistribution

Z3. Food Waste Prevention Campaign

Description

Zamudio municipality has signed an agreement with Aunar non-profitable organization. With this agreement, Zamudio municipality will support (paying Aunar services) the re-introduction of catering food which would otherwise be

Lessons learnt

This action has not been enough time implemented to have main conclusions, but we would like to reach to more people.

Communication Tools

AUNAR has a lot of background in this area and they have a well protocolized process.

Success key points

AUNAR has a lot of background in this area and they have a well protocolized process.

Social Action implementation: Z3.4.1 Aunar agreement

Start date: 2018-03-01 **End date:**

Success of the action (0-5): 0

Location: Zamudio municipality

Short description: Since last 1st of March, the solidary food storage container, will allow to collect surpluses from collective and professional kitchens of the local area to distribute them among a dozen families in the locality. The Vizcaya School participates in the donation of surpluses.

Food deliveries will be weekly, and this will be delivered frozen and packed in a non-returnable pack, suitable for freezing and microwaves. The surplus of food will be subjected to a rigorous sanitary control. Also, the food will be frozen in containers with all the guarantees and will be delivered to the beneficiaries in isothermal bags in which there will be enough food for a week. These bags will be delivered at the beginning of the initiative, and the beneficiaries must carry them at the time of collection to ensure the maintenance of the cold chain.

Keywords

Monitoring methodology

AUNAR annual report

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Z5.2 Increase of knowledge about compost

Z5. Composting

Description

Increase of the knowledge about compost as key message to understand circular economy, foodwaste cycle, etc. It includes some activities where compost will be distributed. For example, compost will be used by the

Lessons learnt

It needs to be published the innovation before the event in ZamudiOrain magazine.

Communication Tools

What is free.

Success key points

What is free.

Social Action implementation: Z5.2.1 Balcony flower competition

Start date: 2018-05-12 **End date:** 2018-05-12

Success of the action (0-5):

Location: Bidekoetxe park

Short description: Every year in Zamudio the flowers are distributed to the citizens for the balcony ornamentation competition. This year, in addition to the flowers, they have distributed compost (from Bizkaia composting plant) in 250 compostable bags to all participants of the competition. In this way, 250 plastic bags have not been generated.

Keywords

Monitoring methodology

Waste volume.

How many people have been distributed the compost.

Total biowaste amount managed in each ecoevent.

Monitoring the temperature of the composter with the thermometer.

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Z6.2 Citizens Participation Process

Z6. PAYT

Description

Citizens participation process. When we made a survey and project presentation, municipality invite inhabitants to take part in the participation process. Those people, who want to take part, will be called to ensure their

Lessons learnt

In order to reach to more citizens, we will need to use public communication tools. It is important to have better rates of participation in the next meeting, where we are going to start with PAYT scheme.

Communication Tools

We hire a participation enterprise in order to make a more productive meeting. They prepare 2 dynamics, which were effective to let people

Success key points

We hire a participation enterprise in order to make a more productive meeting. They prepare 2 dynamics, which were effective to let people participate.

Social Action implementation: Z6.2.1 Workshop 1 - Citizens participation

Start date: 2017-02-01 **End date:** 2018-12-31

Success of the action (0-5):

Location: Zamudio Public School

Short description: During this first participation meeting, we discuss about the new collection and monitoring system. During the first 15-20 minutes, the major explained the novelties of the new collection system. The first dynamic was about the redaction of what citizens would want to read about Zamudio's recycling rates some years after the project. After that, we divide citizens into 3 groups. In those small groups, they should find what are the new collection system troubles, and who they would solve them. Finally, they got together, and they shared

Social Action implementation: Z6.2.1 Workshop 1 - Citizens participation

Start date: 2017-02-01 **End date:** 2018-12-31

Success of the action (0-5): 4

Location: Zamudio Public School

Short description: During this first participation meeting, we discuss about the new collection and monitoring system. During the first 15-20 minutes, the major explained the novelties of the new collection system. The first dynamic was about the redaction of what citizens would want to read about Zamudio's recycling rates some years after the project. After that, we divide citizens into 3 groups. In those small groups, they should find what are the new collection system troubles, and who they would solve them. Finally, they got together, and they shared each group conclusions.

Social Action implementation: Z6.2.3 Workshop 3 - Citizens participation

Start date: 2017-02-01 **End date:** 2018-12-31

Success of the action (0-5): 4

Location: Zamudio Public School

Short description: It was the second PAYT scheme meeting. The aim of this meeting was approved the last version we modified due to the previous contributions of citizens. The major explained the variable and fixed part of the tax in 20 minutes, and after that, we divided in groups to discuss the rates presented previously (40 minutes). Questions to answer were (show attached PAYT scheme and uses cases).

Keywords

Monitoring methodology

After conclusions, the enterprise delivered to each citizen a survey asking about dynamic drivers, the workshop, the place and used materials.

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Z8.1 Day festivals Ecoevents

Z8. Zero Waste Events

Description

Organization of Zero Waste Events in “Day” festivals: fairs, demonstrations, running race...

Lessons learnt

It needs to be published before the event that is an ecoevent to be more successful. Compel the participants and sellers to use only compostable tableware.

Communication Tools

The separation of garbage did not succeed.

Success key points

The separation of garbage did not succeed.

Social Action implementation: Z8.1.1 V Zamudio's Chocolate, Sweet and Craft Fair and XXV Basque Country Limousine Breed Championship

Start date: 2017-11-04 **End date:** 2017-11-05

Success of the action (0-5): 0

Location: Parking of Avenida Pinoa (Zamudio)

Short description: For the drinks it uses PLA compostable glasses and for the food were used compostable plates. It wanted to be thrown the cups in the organic (brown) bin (that was opened) to make compost. But people are not aware and for this reason people throw the waste to the organic bin and as a result it isn't possible to make compost. It is true that it is a little confusing because in Bizkaia in the brown container can only throw remains of vegetables origin, but in this case, they should also throw remains of animal origin (posters were placed in the containers to know that). The separation of glass and plastic containers was done quite well.

Social Action implementation: Z8.1.2 Nekazamudio Fair

Start date: 2018-05-05 **End date:** 2018-05-05

Success of the action (0-5): 5

Location: Cultural Center

Short description: Fair of agricultural and artisanal products of Zamudio. Monthly the producers of Zamudio make a fair to show and sell their products.

Social Action implementation: Z8.1.3 Santi Mami Neighborhood festivals

Start date: 2017-06-01 **End date:** 2017-06-30

Success of the action (0-5): 0

Location: Santi Mami neighborhood

Short description: Santi Mami is a neighborhood of Zamudio and their festivals are on August. After the success of the Lagatzu eco-event, municipality proposed to Santi Mami Festivals organizers, taking some eco-event measures. They did not take so many measures because of the lack of time and organization (festivals are in the middle of the summer vacations). They just put different fraction containers in the stand and on the festival area with explanatory poster where it was explained which type of items should be thrown in each container.

Keywords

Zerowaste-event, ecoevent

Monitoring methodology

Volume of each sorting fraction.

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Z8.2 Popular meals

Z8. Zero Waste Events

Description

Organization of Zero Waste Events in Popular meals

Lessons learnt

We have a lot of things to improve.

We need to speak with all events organizers together.

Communication Tools

It is a well-known popular event

Municipality workers participate actively during the organization and the lunch day.

Success key points

It is a well-known popular event

Municipality workers participate actively during the organization and the lunch day.

Social Action implementation: Z8.2.1 Lagatzu Eco-Event

Start date: 2017-06-01 End date: 2017-06-30

Success of the action (0-5): 0

Location Sabino Arana Square

Short description In June, Basque Culture Association from Zamudio celebrates during the weekend different fostering actions. They make a popular lunch on Sunday where participate 600 people approximately. It has an enormous success, and they come a lot of people from Zamudio and from the valley also.

Municipality social fostering worker, talked with the association so as to become the popular lunch in an eco-event.

They used a compostable dinner service in order to explain to people which was the main of using it, they print a short explanation on the tablecloth. After the lunch, they collected organic waste cautiously not to contaminate it.

For the recycling goal, municipality order to collection service to put a container island in the area. To use containers properly, municipality printed A3 posters to put on the containers, explaining which type of item people could throw in each fraction: organic, light-packaging, paper-cardboard and glass waste. Urban solid waste container could not be used by citizens. Only organizers had permission to open it. As well, municipality prepared a project flag to indicate where the island was.

After the event, the organic waste was transported to communitarian composting plant

Keywords

Zero waste event, eco-event

Monitoring methodology

Participation rate.

Volume of each sorting fraction.

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Z8.3 Night Festivals

Z8. Zero Waste Events

Description

Organization of Zero Waste Events in Night festivals : concerts, drinking bars,...

Lessons learnt

It needs to be published before the event that it is an eco-event to be more successful.

Communication Tools

The separation of garbage did not succeed

Success key points

The separation of garbage did not succeed

Social Action implementation: Z8.3.1 Arimen Gaba

Start date: 2017-10-31 **End date:** 2017-10-31

Success of the action (0-5): 0

Location: Cultural center

Short description The citizens dressed up and paraded through the streets of Zamudio with the candles they made with used cooking oil. There was also a theater set in the day of the souls. Afterwards, a drink and pumpkin pies were distributed and at the same time there was a demonstration of how to make candles with used cooking oil.

Keywords

Zero waste event, eco-event

Monitoring methodology

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Z9.2 Halloween

Z9. Miscellaneous

Description

Zamudio want to foster a different Halloween. Our history says that Basque people, because of the relationship with the Celts, celebrated a souls' festival, where people disguised themselves. So, municipality has proposed making a parade in the streets.

Lessons learnt

Communication Tools

Children like to do new and creative things. Children absorb a lot of information and then pass it on to family members.

Success key points

Children like to do new and creative things. Children absorb a lot of information and then pass it on to family members.

Social Action implementation: Z9.2.1 Candle workshop in Zamudio Public School

Start date: 2017-11-17 **End date:** 2017-11-24

Success of the action (0-5): 0

Location: Zamudio Public School

Short description The workshop it done with the students of 3-12 years, once to each class. At the beginning of the workshop a small presentation is made to raise awareness of the problem that involves pouring the oil through the sink. The students brought used cooking oil from home and with that oil the candles were made. For the rest of material, was used the one that was purchased from the Portuguese company Greatest candle in the world. Each student was also given a kit with the necessary material to make another 5 candles at home with instructions in Spanish and Basque. The objective of this workshop is to raise awareness of the problem of oil and teach a way to reuse the oil.

Keywords

Cooking-oil

Monitoring methodology

satisfaction survey for teachers running the candle workshop

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SE1.1 Lunch/Dinner with Waste

SE1. Citizens' Sensitization - Funny Door to Door Sensitization

Description

Self-organized dinner; participants bringing food and tableware to share. Sorting game performed and facilitators explaining.

Lessons learnt

Delivery of environmental messages in a friendly setup is easier and participation is higher.

Communication Tools

Conviviality and user-friendliness.

Success key points

Conviviality and user-friendliness.

Social Action implementation: SE1.1.1 Lunch/Dinner with Waste

Start date: End date:

Success of the action (0-5): 4

Location:

Short description: Self-organized dinner; participants bringing food and tableware to share. Sorting game performed and facilitators explaining.

KPIs

Average reduction percentage of the RFID bag set out by the users before sensitization: 3700

Average reduction percentage of the RFID bag set out by the users after sensitization: 2800

Increase of quality of the separate collection: light packaging/metal:17,8%; food waste: 1,58%

Number of questionnaires completed and returned: 2834

SE1.2 Public Spaces/Activities

SE1. Citizens' Sensitization - Funny Door to Door Sensitization

Description

Facilitators in a stand

Lessons learnt

Listening to citizen's need face to face allowed to accelerate some improvements (e.g. the introduction of the free orange bag for nappies was anticipated to august 2017 following the high request by citizens).

Communication Tools

Effective support "on the road" to the ecology office, direct contact with citizens, accelerated the improvement of the waste collection and PAYT

Success key points

Effective support "on the road" to the ecology office, direct contact with citizens, accelerated the improvement of the waste collection and PAYT

Social Action implementation: SE1.2.1 Public Spaces/Activities

Start date: End date:

Success of the action (0-5): 4

Location:

Short description: Facilitators in a stand

Keywords

Monitoring methodology

By now, estimation according to the satisfaction after receiving support.

SE1.3 Elderly People House activities

SE1. Citizens' Sensitization - Funny Door to Door Sensitization

Description

preparatory events with staff, sorting game during social events, such as lunches and dinners organized by the old people centre, information desk

Lessons learnt

to disseminate the project information in waste management and in PAYT in an effective way to specific target, it's necessary to use specific tools, in order to be sure to reach them.

Communication Tools

PAYT explanation to a target with difficulties to understand the new service payment.

Success key points

PAYT explanation to a target with difficulties to understand the new service payment.

Social Action implementation:

Start date: End date:

Success of the action (0-5): 4

Location: Old people centre

Short description: Preparatory events with staff, sorting game during social events, such as lunches and dinners organized by the old people centre, information desk

Keywords **Monitoring methodology**

By now, estimation according to the satisfaction after receiving support.

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SE1.4 Sensitization in schools

SE1. Citizens' Sensitization - Funny Door to Door Sensitization

Description

Presentation to the headmaster of the project and the action, preliminary meetings with teachers, school interventions in each classroom in the primary schools, events with sorting games theatre and clean up the world campaign.

Lessons learnt

the effectiveness of the action depends on the personal involvement and availability of teachers and school janitors.

Communication Tools

to have involved all the stakeholders in school management

Success key points

to have involved all the stakeholders in school management

Social Action implementation: SE1.4.1 Sensitization in schools

Start date: End date:

Success of the action (0-5): 4

Location: Primary School “Enrico Toti” and Primary school “Carlo Collodi”, Secondary school “Don Giussani”

Short description: Presentation to the headmaster of the project and the action, preliminary meetings with teachers, school interventions in each classroom in the primary schools, events with sorting games theatre and clean up the world campaign.

Specific training meeting for school janitors. Delivery of waste containers in each classroom and in corridors to improve the separation.

Site inspections ante and post interventions.

Keywords **Monitoring methodology**

By now, estimation according to site inspections.

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SE3.1 Preparation of criteria, tendering & purchasing

SE3. Zero Waste Events

Description

Without the proper planning huge amounts of catering and lightweight packaging waste are generated at the events. The municipality, in order to promote Zero-Waste events, set up a new regulation, entrusted the

Lessons learnt

association have to be informed and sensitized in order to obtain their commitment in organizing eco-events. In fact, this imply a behavioral change and a strong effort especially in the starting phase.

Communication Tools

defining specific criteria with a regulation, meeting associations explaining the new strategy in organizing events and purchasing long-lasting equipment and

Success key points

defining specific criteria with a regulation, meeting associations explaining the new strategy in organizing events and purchasing long-lasting equipment and

Social Action implementation: SE3.1.1 New regulation for events in Seveso

Start date: 2017-04-01 **End date:** 2017-04-01

Success of the action (0-5): 4

Location: Tent for summer events in Redipuglia Street, Seveso

Short description: The municipality of Seveso get up a new regulation defining specific criteria for the management of the tent for summer events sited in Via Redipuglia, in order to reach environmental and social objectives, as:

- Reduce waste production during events
- Increase the separate collection
- Minimize costs for waste management

Social Action implementation: SE3.1.2 Public tender for managing the tent

Start date: 2017-03-22 **End date:** 2017-04-03

Success of the action (0-5): 5

Location: Tent for summer events in Redipuglia Street, Seveso

Short description. With the public tender, the municipality of Seveso assigned the management of the tent located in Via Redipuglia for the period 2017-2020, where during the summer season several Associations promote events consisting in lunches or dinners in order to finance their activities.

Social Action implementation: SE3.1.3 Purchasing equipment and goods for Eco-events 2017

Start date: 2017-04-01 **End date:** 2017-09-01

Success of the action (0-5): 5

Location: Tent for summer events in Redipuglia Street, Seveso

Short description: The municipality of Seveso purchased the necessary equipment to support eco-events, specially aiming at using washable catering (dishes, cutlery and glass) and a dishwasher suitable to wash a large number of items in a short time. Also the association winning the public tender was in charge to provide some necessary items to realize the first eco-event.

Keywords

Zerowaste, eco-event

Monitoring methodology

No specific monitoring provided

SE1.5 Sensitization in Summer camps with children

SE1. Citizens' Sensitization - Funny Door to Door Sensitization

Description

A sorting game “where should I throw this” has been done with children and educators. This was done in 2 rounds: at the beginning and in the end of the camp.

Lessons learnt

the results show that on average no one improved his behavior after one month. This activity should be reconsidered for next year.

Communication Tools

High interest by adult referents, all children participated

Success key points

High interest by adult referents, all children participated

Social Action implementation: SE1.5.1 Sensitization in Summer camps with children

Start date: End date:

Success of the action (0-5): 2

Location: Parishes of Seveso

Short description: A sorting game “where should I throw this” has been done with children and educators. This was done in 2 rounds: at the beginning and in the end of the camp.

summer 2017

Keywords

Monitoring methodology

Percentage of right answers to the game

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SE2.1 Citizens involvement

SE2. Zero Waste Campaigns -Virtuous Households

Description

Identification of families agreeing to participate to the social action

Lessons learnt

the public recruiting phase would have been longer in order to spread more the action towards citizens and allows a more consistent participation.

Communication Tools

participation of a panel of families (with newborns too) well representing the social patterns of Seveso; all the families recruited had already before the

Success key points

participation of a panel of families (with newborns too) well representing the social patterns of Seveso; all the families recruited had already before the actions a virtuous behavior on waste management; availability of a young

Social Action implementation: SE2.1.1 Families recruiting activity “Differenzia al Massimo”

Start date: 2018-04-23 **End date:** 2018-05-13

Success of the action (0-5):

Location: Six mono or bi-family houses and two condominiums with more than 10 apartments located in Seveso municipality

Short description: Families were recruited by a public tender published on municipal website. Since the deadline for applying was too short, some families have been directly contacted by municipality and by ARS staff.

Keywords

Monitoring methodology

A specific person was trained by ARS in order to follow the recruiting phase and in particular to verify the respect of specific requirements of the regulation.

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SE2.2 Training and monitoring period

SE2. Zero Waste Campaigns -Virtuous Households

Description

Virtuous households families have to periodically weight their waste streams (organic, multi-material, paper, glass, unsorted waste, all waste carried to the municipal ecological platform) and communicate it during the action.

Lessons learnt

The maximum level of separate collection in the families reached 95% and the per capita unsorted waste production about 5-10 kg/inhabitant year, much lower than the current Seveso average. This means that, despite the very high

Communication Tools

Guaranteeing a technical support during all the action, awarding the families with a little economic reward.

Success key points

Guaranteeing a technical support during all the action, awarding the families with a little economic reward.

Social Action implementation: SE2.2.1 Families contest “Differenzia al Massimo”

Start date: 2018-05-13 **End date:** 2018-07-13

Success of the action (0-5):

Location: Six mono or bi-family houses and two condominiums with more than 10 apartments located in Seveso municipality.

Short description: Virtuous households families have to periodically weight their waste streams (organic, multi-material, paper, glass, unsorted waste, all waste carried to the municipal ecological platform) and communicate it during the action. ARS was in charge to verify if this activity was carried out by all the family at least one a week. Each family recruited received a dynamometer to weight their waste.

Keywords

Monitoring methodology

an excel monitoring sheets (shared by google drive) was given to all participants with the scope to register their waste weights during the period (at least one a week). A young people, in collaboration with ARS

SE2.3 Feedback activities

SE2. Zero Waste Campaigns -Virtuous Households

Description

Once close the monitoring period, it's necessary to give feedbacks to participating families and spread the results of the action towards all the citizens if possible with a peer-to-peer event.

Lessons learnt

feedbacks of the actions have to be numerous in order to reach the largest amount of citizens. Many communication channels have to be used (web and paper press, social media, public events).

Communication Tools

peer-to-peer event

Success key points

peer-to-peer event

Social Action implementation: SE2.3.1 Peer-to-peer event and awarding families "FAMIGLIE SUPER-RICICLONE"

Start date: 2018-11-24 **End date:** 2018-11-24

Success of the action (0-5): 5

Location: Bosco delle Querce, Seveso Municipality

Short description: An event has been organized during the EWWR (European Week for Waste Reduction) 2018 in Seveso in order to give feedbacks to citizens about the "Famiglie super-riciclone" contest, to award the families participating and to let them explain to other people their experience.

Keywords

Monitoring methodology

The data collected by the during the activity were the data used for feedback towards citizens and towards the municipality. All the data published are anonymous.

SE3.2 Celebration & monitoring of ecoevents

SE3. Zero Waste Events

Description

Organization and implementarion of eco-event

Lessons learnt

Associations organizing eco-events, especially for the first time, have to be adequately trained and motivated. Even if they could raise some doubts or see only obstacles, the good results of the event, also in terms of economic and

Communication Tools

Good commitment of organizing association, volunteers training, presence of public authority (Seveso's Major), sensitization action in support by

Success key points

Good commitment of organizing association, volunteers training, presence of public authority (Seveso's Major), sensitization action in support by

Social Action implementation: SE3.2.1 Celebration & monitoring of ecoevents-Valtellinese Festival

Start date: 2017-08-31 **End date:** 2017-08-31

Success of the action (0-5):

Location: Public covered space for municipal event (Street Redipuglia, Seveso)

Short description: Organization of the first eco-event during the four-day long Valtellinese Festival. People was served with washable dishes and cutlery and was informed about environmental benefits of an eco-event and sensitized on separate collection and waste production.

This was only the first trial event for Seveso Municipality that during the summer season hosts many events. The aim for the next year is to spread the good practice experimented to a more number of events, sensitizing a great number of people of Seveso and municipalities.

Social Action implementation: SE3.2.2 Sagra Valtellinese Eco-event (2018)

Start date: 2018-09-05 **End date:** 2018-09-05

Success of the action (0-5):

Location: Public covered space for municipal event (Street Redipuglia, Seveso)

Short description: Organization of the first eco-event during the four-day long Valtellinese Festival by ASD - Associazione Sportiva Dilettantistica of Seveso with 20-30 volunteers. People was served with washable dishes and cutlery and was informed about environmental benefits of an eco-event and sensitized on separate collection and waste production.

KPIs

Rate of separate collection: 32.2

Rate of separate collection: Quantity collected of light packagin per capita.: 97.8

Keywords

Monitoring methodology

For all the events organized in the months of August and September 2017 in Seveso, ARS with the collaboration of the municipality set up a monitoring system based on a detailed reporting on: number of participants (KPI), waste management (separate collection)

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SE4.2 Implementation of the PAYT system

SE4. PAYT Introduction - Communication

Description

After the approval of the local regulation by the City Council, starting from 1^o May 17, the blue bags with RFID started to be counted in order to introduce PAYT in Seveso. The payment of the collecting waste fee has been divided in

Lessons learnt

To be successful is needed:

- Political commitment

Communication Tools

Seveso has successfully introduced the PAYT thanks to the introduction, some years ago, of the ibag. The experimentation with ibag before the tax is a key

Success key points

Seveso has successfully introduced the PAYT thanks to the introduction, some years ago, of the ibag. The experimentation with ibag before the tax is a key

Social Action implementation: Implementation activities of the PAYT system to all the domestic and non-domestic users in Seveso

Start date: 2017-05-01 **End date:**

Success of the action (0-5): 0

Location: Seveso

Short description: Implementation activities of the PAYT system to all the domestic and non-domestic users in Seveso

Keywords

Monitoring methodology

Data on waste collection (separate collection rate, weight of all the fractions, number of bag, zero-waste producers, etc.) and PAYT payments are regularly collected by municipality and waste management company in their databases.

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H1.2 Gymnasium

H1. Educational Centers Activities

Description

The educational program is focusing on four main working areas:

- Waste monitoring

Lessons learnt

The motivation of the teachers and the administration of the school is critical for the success of the program, as well as the continuity from one year to the other. As this is the case, we have to examine ways to present moral incentives to motivate

Communication Tools

Success key points

Social Action implementation: H1.2.1 6th Gymnasium of Halandri

Start date: 2017-12-01 **End date:**

Success of the action (0-5): 2

Location: 6th Gymnasium of Halandri

Short description The main activity of the school has been composting. A series of lessons have been delivered in class, and students have presented individual research on the topic. A presentation has also taken place from the NTUA team in the school, along with the installation of the composter and the initial loading with biowaste, brought by the students from home, and prunings from the school's garden. Monitoring instruments have also been given to the school by the municipality.

The process has faced some problems, with the initial batch of the compost going wrong, and a second one as well. The process has been abandoned for this year.

Also, actions have been taken to monitor the waste generated in the class. A form has been filled, describing certain types of waste typically found in a class bin (paper, plastic bottles, food packaging, aluminum cans, food, gums, other), and the amount of each type was measured.

This will be done again, this time measuring the weight and volume of each type, and also examining bins found outside the class, in other areas of the school.

The 6th gymnasium was originally scheduled to undertake a full educational program for this year. However, there were significant changes in the school's administration and key personnel which were involved in the process since last year, and the transition proved to be difficult.

Social Action implementation: H1.1.2 Home composting

Start date: 2018-02-02 **End date:** 2018-05-31

Success of the action (0-5):

Location:

Short description: A composter has been provided to the school by the municipality. The students brought presorted biowaste from their home, and gathered prunings from the school yard and leftovers from the school canteen. They have been measuring the temperature, the humidity and pH of the compost. The students have responded extremely well to this project and have installed a second composter. A short research paper has been prepared as homework.

H1.1 Vocational School

H1. Educational Centers Activities

Description

The program is constructed in the framework of the “Research on Technology” and “Environmental Program” which are implemented in 2017-2018 in the school and are non-typical forms of education that are approved by the Ministry of Education.

Lessons learnt

The main difficulty in working with a vocational school is the fact that vocational schools traditionally attract students with lower expectations and educational ambitions. Sometimes, this is also reflected on the teachers.

Communication Tools

1. The teacher who has undertaken the task is very motivated and willing to take initiatives and push things. She also has a background in engineering, so is

Success key points

1. The teacher who has undertaken the task is very motivated and willing to take initiatives and push things. She also has a background in engineering, so is

Social Action implementation: H1.1.1 Waste Monitoring

Start date: 2017-10-20 **End date:** 2018-10-31

Success of the action (0-5): 5

Location: 3rd Vocational Highschool

Short description: The students have measured, characterized and classified waste generated within the school premises, both commingled and recycling bins. The students have used maps so they have been familiarized with basic mapping techniques, they have been using formulas for volume of different shapes (i.e. a bag modeled as a cylinder), measured weight and learned as well notions such as density. A baseline has been established as well for the above, registering the amount of total waste and percentage of recyclables. A short research paper has

Social Action implementation: H1.1.2 Home composting

Start date: 2018-02-02 **End date:** 2018-05-31

Success of the action (0-5):

Location: 3rd Vocational Highschool

Short description: A composter has been provided to the school by the municipality. The students brought presorted biowaste from their home, and gathered prunings from the school yard and leftovers from the school canteen. They have been measuring the temperature, the humidity and pH of the compost. The students have responded extremely well to this project and have installed a second composter. A short research paper has been prepared as homework.

Social Action implementation: H1.1.3 Visit to food waste collection and plant

Start date: **End date:**

Success of the action (0-5):

Location:

Short description: The students have visited the municipality’s facilities, where the key issues of household biowaste have been presented, and the Waste4Think process has been demonstrated. Also, a brown bin has been provided to the school where a demonstration of the collection system also took place. The students collected and measured the weight of biowaste from school bins, the school canteen and a nearby restaurant. A short research paper has been prepared as homework.

Keywords

Monitoring methodology

Students use forms to register data they collect.

Students are given homeworks and projects relevant to the specific actions.

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H3.1 Initial Seminars - Campaign

H3. Food Separate Collection and Treatment

Description

The first decision regarding the participation of the citizens was that volunteers were to be selected from the entire municipality and not just one neighborhood. This was expected to have the following advantages:

Lessons learnt

1. We find that collection twice a week is adequate and citizens are satisfied with it (i.e. acceptable odors).

Communication Tools

1. The separate collection in the households is done in a way that minimizes the change in the daily routine, so it is easily adopted.

Success key points

1. The separate collection in the households is done in a way that minimizes the change in the daily routine, so it is easily adopted.

Social Action implementation: H3.1.1 Selection campaign

Start date: End date:

Success of the action (0-5): 5

Location:

Short description: The first decision regarding the participation of the citizens was that volunteers were to be selected from the entire municipality and not just one neighborhood.

- earlier reach of the target of 240 households

- easier scaling up of the project

- we would avoid negative feelings and reactions from neighborhoods not participating.

The biggest disadvantage would be that the collection routes were going to be longer, both in distance and in time.

Social Action implementation: H3.1.2 Inaugural meeting

Start date: 2016-12-12 **End date:** 2016-12-12

Success of the action (0-5): 0

Location:

Short description: We held the inaugural meeting with the volunteers on December 12, 2016. Participants were notified by email and telephone calls. About 70% were able to attend. The meeting was presided by prof. Gerasimos Lyberatos, who is also a city counselor and responsible for waste management strategy development. He gave a presentation of the Waste4Think Project and described the specifics of separate collection of food waste.

The mayor of Halandri, Simos Roussos, also intervened to present the municipality's action plan regarding waste management, and how Waste4Think is planned to be an integral part and a driver of this.

Keywords

Monitoring methodology

1. Each bin is weighted at collection. The total amount of biowaste treated is also weighed for cross reference reasons. This way, it is possible to calculate the mean production of organics per citizen.

2. A sampling took place in November, studying wast

C1.1 Preparation activities

C1. ID/PAYT Containers System

Description

to engage citizens in the target area in the project as participants and beneficiaries of the project.

Lessons learnt

direct contact will surpass multiple questions or doubts from participants. It will increase confidence between stakeholders.

Communication Tools

direct contact and conversation to explain issues

Success key points

direct contact and conversation to explain issues

Social Action implementation: C1.1.1 Door-to-Door campaign

Start date: 2018-07-15 **End date:** 2018-09-15

Success of the action (0-5):

Location: Target area in Carcavelos, Cascais

Short description: Direct contact with potential participants (target audience) to present the project and its benefits. Register the participants.

Social Action implementation: C1.1.2 Green awards

Start date: **End date:**

Success of the action (0-5):

Location: Target area in Carcavelos, Cascais

Short description: To engage participants and have a continuous relationship (proximity) Staff members will go door to door to give some useful utensils to participants. utensils (eco bags for recycling, reusable fruitbags, to be defined)

KPIs

Keywords

Monitoring methodology

Surveys and registration account